

SmartCHP
COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

D 6.1

Market Assessment

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EU long Term Strategy aims to climate-neutrality by 2050, i.e. aiming to become an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. The European Green Deal, sets EU-wide targets and policy objectives for the period up to 2030, which translate into ⁽¹⁾: *at least 40% cuts in greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990 levels), at least 32% share for renewable energy, and at least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency.*

The EU Funded **SmartCHP** project is fully contributing to it, its scope being the development of a highly flexible small-scale Combined Heat and Power (CHP) system (0.1 - 1 MW_e), fuelled with Fast Pyrolysis Bio Oil (FPBO) produced from different types of lignocellulosic biomass and/or residues.

SmartCHP addresses targets set by the Green-Deal and the EU “Vision to 2050” through (a) its contribution to the improvement of Energy Efficiency, as CHP is by definition an efficient technology, thus (b) contributing to the reduction of GHG emissions per unit of energy used, whereas (c) it uses at the same time a RE fuel -Fast Pyrolysis Bio-oil -for the production of which, biomass is the source.

This Market Assessment has been prepared in the frame of the HORIZON 2020 funded project **“Smart and flexible heat and power from biomass derived liquids for small-scale CHP application”**.

This study aims to allow understanding of the size of the potential for the application of the SmartCHP technology offering in the European Market. As this study runs in parallel with other tasks of the project (e.g. the biomass feedstock potential in EU countries, or the enabling environment) there is interaction between them and will be further elaborated in the course of the project. Such interactions are displayed and explained in Chapter 1.

The methodology adopted for the study is described in Chapter 2 of this study and involves **market trends and factors affecting the employment of CHP technology**, the **quantification of the CHP / SmartCHP market** as well as the existing or upcoming technology competitors.

The **share of CHP in total electricity generation at EU-27** level has been moving around **11.5%** during last decade, varying between 11% and 12,4%. Such variations could be attributed to a combination of reasons, such as the variations of the international primary fuel prices or the increasing penetration of the electricity produced from RE sources. During the same period, the **overall CHP electrical capacity has increased by approximately 20%**, while CHP thermal capacity has virtually remained the same, leading to a reduction -at EU-27 level- of the Heat-to-Power Ratio. The share of both the share of CHP in total gross electricity generation as well the actual installed electrical (and thermal) capacity displays large differences between European countries. At the same time the Heat-to-Power ratio displays large differences between countries, indicating differences in terms of priorities (e.g. CHP for district heating) or the technology mix employed in CHP. in each country.

Chapter 3 highlights the increasing penetration of RES and Waste as CHP fuels along with the **increasing share of biogas and biofuels in the electricity generation in EU-27**. Small scale CHP (up to 1 MW_e), which is the segment being

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/strategies/2030_en

addressed by SmartCHP technology, displays large differences between countries in Europe, not only in terms of number of units and installed capacity, but also in terms of the availability of information, which is scattered and dispersed. The small-scale CHP potential which is evaluated in Chapter 6 of this study compared with current CHP penetration levels provide the grounds for assessing the potential market gap, significant part of which SmartCHP can cover.

There are **several factors driving CHP market**, ranging from purely **technical and inherent to CHP factors** up to the **normative/legislative environment** including also any incentives in favour of CHP. These are described in Chapter 4, which provides an overview of the CHP market trends through an analysis of the factors driving CHP development in EU27, e.g. **Policy actions and support schemes, or barriers affecting the employment of CHP**. Policy expressed at central EU level or local/country level has proven to be a prime market driver. CHP penetration has largely been supported by incentives such as **Feed-in-tariff and Feed-in Premium schemes as in Germany, Hungary or Italy, Loans or grants as for instance in Finland, Germany or Slovenia, Tax mechanisms as in Belgium, Poland or Greece**, among others. Such schemes combined with the inherent to CHP higher than conventional technologies efficiency improvement, thus reduction of fuel related operating costs, supported by awareness actions have proven to be key drivers for the penetration of CHP. On the other hand, regulatory and legislative uncertainty or inconsistency (e.g. removal of incentives before market becomes self-sustained), or the volatility of primary fuel prices (driving also the electricity prices) can decelerate CHP penetration or even reduce its share at local or EU level. Such dependence of the CHP share on fuel prices has been observed in the past years with the decline of international oil prices. SmartCHP, although it can potentially be affected by the policy framework, it seems that it can overcome the pressure by the volatile primary energy fluctuations, under the condition that biomass and consequently bio-oil are available in the market at favourable prices.

For testing and assessing the efficiency and effectiveness of the SmartCHP technological proposal, **five focus countries have been selected**. The selection process is described in Chapter 5 and has been based i) on any **existing support schemes**, through the analysis of the existing legislative framework and policies, ii) the **Electricity prices** for the tertiary/commercial, household and industrial sectors for the period 2008-2017, iii) the **share of CHP** in the each country's overall electricity production, iv) the **geographical characteristics** of the countries or v) the **availability or lack or availability of biomass** in the countries. The latter will allow the research team to evaluate any logistical issues involved in the supply chain of the bio-oil. The countries selected are **Croatia, Greece, the Netherlands, Romania and Sweden**.

The **CHP market potential** (Chapter 6) in these five countries is quite high across several sectors of the economy including **Health sector, the Hotel sector, Office buildings, Education in the tertiary sector, as well as the residential sector and agriculture through the energy needs of greenhouses**. Overall CHP potential in terms of number of units in the range between 0.1 and 1 MW_e has been calculated in tens of thousands of units, meaning in substance a high commercial potential, as well as the FPBO quantity per tonne, needed for a SmartCHP unit with capacity of 0.1 kW_e and 1 MW_e. This amount certainly does not constitute a fully exploitable potential since there are **several restricting factors**, related to the **energy load structure**, such as **seasonality for the Hotel sector, space**

availability in the office buildings sector, middle to low utilization factor in the education sector, among others. In addition, SmartCHP market potential could be limited by the **fuel availability** at large quantities and the **logistics and limitations involved in its supply chain**. Such issues have not been addressed within the scope of this study and will be addressed in the course of other tasks of the SmartCHP project to feed the market assessment at a later stage.

Within the CHP market, SmartCHP faces competition at two levels, the technology level including conventional, tested and mature technologies, such as engine or gas turbine driven CHP and the system wise level, i.e. high efficiency systems supplying separately heat or electricity, such as heat pumps. Chapter 7 provides an overview of the direct, i.e. **competing technologies or indirect competition**, which refers to the supply chain of the biomass reaching the Fast Pyrolysis production facilities and consequently the final users of SmartCHP.

This **market analysis** aims to **assess and quantify the gross market potential of CHP and consequently SmartCHP** at sectoral (i.e. user) and regional (i.e. country) level. Its value relies in the wide collection of market and contextual data combining a double perspective – geographical and end customer centered. Proxies and calculation steps have been documented so that fine tuning based on more precise values on market parameters could be made.

As a starting point five focus countries have been studied indicating a significant potential for CHP and SmartCHP applications expressed in thousands of units, a potential which will be further assessed following the feasibility analyses of cases, which will be implemented in the course of the SmartCHP project. Such market potential by just considering the so-called 'incremental' market segments (the ones that are already acquainted with conventional cogeneration systems), could then be easily **scaled-up by exploring countries beyond the five focus countries**.

Beyond the market potential, for further implementation of effective go-to-market strategies, next investigation efforts will focus on the **system economics of a SmartCHP** system in the specific context of a given energy end-user and a given region for the supply side: the future techno-economic studies will complement this assessment on a local / use case basis

The **distinctive value of SmartCHP** when compared to other cogeneration systems is also confirmed. SmartCHP aims to become a **leading technological proposal for cogeneration** which, through its flexible nature can provide heat and electricity at high efficiency, while at the same time contributing to the significant reduction of the carbon footprint both at user, country and European level.

List of Abbreviations

CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
EC	Energy Community
EEC	European Economic Community
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
FPBO	Fast Pyrolysis Bio Oil
FiT	Feed-in-Tariff
GHG	Greenhouse Gas Emissions
IEA	International Energy Agency
IFHE	International Federation for Home Economics
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MWH	Mega Watt hours
NPV	Net Present Value
OPEX	Operating Expenses
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
OWR	Organic Waste Residues
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
REFIT	Renewable Energy Feed-In-Tariff Scheme
RES	Renewable Energy Sources

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1. Introduction

1.1 The SmartCHP project

Small scale biomass-based Combined Heat and Power (CHP) has the potential to contribute significantly to the challenges Europe faces while pursuing to make its energy system smart, clean, flexible, secure, cost competitive and efficient.

The SmartCHP solution enables higher levels of renewable energy resources (RES) in the electricity system by providing a flexible, responsive and intelligent solution, as well as high efficiency rate by combining heat and power generation. It inherits the advantages of cogeneration and of renewable generation. Furthermore, it can contribute to secure continuous electricity supply by balancing demand with the supply of Heat and Electricity from a renewable energy source (i.e. bio-oil) with intermittent wind and solar electricity generation. To that purpose, it is advantageous if the CHP system is flexible enough to adjust its fuel load rapidly. This is achievable particularly with liquid fuels such as fast pyrolysis bio oil (FPBO), used by the SmartCHP system, fast pyrolysis referring to the conversion process of a wide variety of biomass resources into a uniform and homogeneous liquid fuel of standard characteristics called FPBO. Another intrinsic characteristic of SmartCHP is the local anchorage resulting from the biomass feedstock. Short supply circuits will clearly constitute boundary conditions for SmartCHP system economics. This recurrent factor will pave the both market assessment developed in this report and the future techno-economic studies to be carried out with in the project.

The overall objective of SmartCHP project is to develop a small-scale combined heat and power (CHP) system (100 – 1,000 kW_e), combining a diesel engine and a flue gas boiler, both fueled with FPBO originating from different types of lignocellulosic biomasses and/or residues. These residues could be agricultural residues (AR), forestry residues (FR) and organic waste residues (OWR, which are food and feed processing side streams, such as olive stones).

Expected benefits of the SmartCHP technology are multi-fold and include technical, economic, environmental, and social benefits and of interests for various stakeholders ranging from the energy end users to the citizen. Such assets indeed result from the energy density of the fuel, high flexibility of heat and power ratio, reduction of GHG emissions, reduction of pollution (NO_x, SO_x, particles, etc.), reduction of grid costs (reinforcement and losses), or compliance with the EU REDII as regards the sustainability criteria, among others.

1.2 Aim of the document

Assessing a market potential of SmartCHP requires to simultaneously capture an understanding of cogeneration market potential and trends, as well as the supply-side constraints of biomass-to-oil conversion economics requiring a focus on a selection of regional markets.

The aim of this document is first to provide an overview of the CHP market and its trends in the short/mid-term horizon in EU-27, in order to allow understanding and evaluation of the potential for FPBO fueled CHP systems in the European market.

To this end the document provides information covering the following areas:

- Overview of the relevant policy framework in the European countries;
- Outline and analysis of market factors driving CHP market growth;
- Market barriers for CHP installations;
- Evolution of the CHP market in Europe in terms of size and used fuels.

The second goal of the document is to consider the regional dimension. By identifying and defining the market potential of the SmartCHP technology in Europe and in each European country separately, in order to lead to the selection of a number of “focus countries” where SmartCHP technology could be effectively applied and tested.

1.3 Interaction with other project tasks

The options developed within the scope of this project, in terms of technical design and sizing, require an analysis of the upstream and downstream parts of the supply chain. To this end, this market analysis aims to interact between the different work packages (WP) of the project in a direct or indirect manner, feeding and being fed with input by other work packages of the project, and assist project and product development considering both resource availability and current / expected market conditions.

As displayed in Figure 1.1, WP6 (i.e. Market assessment) is closely linked to WP2, which is related to biomass feedstock potential in EU countries and WP4, which in fact provides input to WP6 for the feasibility assessment of real case studies. In addition, through the analysis of the market (size of market, enabling environment, market conditions, etc) and assessment of resource availability in EU-27, WP6 aims to identify the countries that could host SmartCHP test cases, allowing technology and financial assessment in real conditions.

2. Methodology

2.1 General approach

Figure 2.1 below displays the steps of the methodology adopted for the market assessment. The task consists in the following activities, which are further described in following chapters. Three pillars constitute the backbone of the market assessment.

- **Identification of target market and market trends**
This first pillar sets the general framework and aim at delimitating the big picture with regard to the future SmartCHP systems with the goal to assess the current market size, the general trends, its organisation in market segments and studying the factors driving the market (support schemes, electricity prices, etc.) and market barriers. The general analysis is given in chapters 3 (current market) and 4 (trends), while chapter 5 details the process followed to define, the priority areas for SmartCHP. These priority areas are set geographically in the form of focus countries are selected according to their potential and risks.
- **Potential customers and estimated market share**
The second pillar addresses a lower granularity considering the specificity of the energy and user. It first focuses on customer segmentation, customer referring here to energy use (electricity and heat) in order to assess the market potential in terms of SmartCHP system for each of the most promising segments, combined to the focus countries resulting from chapter 5 analysis. This is the object of chapter 6. To that purpose, the analysis is based on source analysis, validation interviews and participation to one workshop within the Cogen Europe Virtual Annual Conference held in 12-13 October 2020. It is expected that this assessment will be further fine-tuned through the techno-economic analysis to be deployed in the project.
- **Competition and competitive advantages**
The third pillar concentrates on the description of direct and indirect competition, their current advantages and disadvantages in comparison to SmartCHP technology, the expected result being to formalise the unique selling point of the SmartCHP solution related to competing technologies. Chapter 7 details such analysis.

Overall, the following picture reminds the three pillars, that are closely related.

Figure 2.1: Presentation of the market assessment content

One of the complexities of the assessment was to handle a segmentation at two dimensions: region-wise and end-user wise. The analysis is performed at both levels, the regional level and the demand as described below:

- **Region wise level / Regional Criteria**

Region wise level analysis consists in a top-down approach, which allows the identification of five "focus countries" best suited for the initial adoption of SmartCHP technology. The analysis was provided by a team comprising experts from BTG, CAPAX, Dowel and Exergia. Following analysis of EU countries, the team has first qualified ten countries, of which five have been selected as "focus countries". The region wise analysis is based on the identification of various regional criteria detailed in section 5 and including:

- National regulatory context, analyzing the existence of public support schemes in support of CHP
- Energy Markets and trade, presenting and analysing the evolution of electricity prices for the household and industrial sectors, the electricity production and compliance to CO₂ targets
- Local energy context, presenting feedback as regards the availability of biomass feedstock in each EU country and the presence of any insular territories.

- **End-user level:**

The adopted approach consists in assessing the energy demand profiles of potential CHP users, in order to investigate on the one hand matching user needs with the SmartCHP technology offering and on the other to assess SmartCHP against competing technologies.

2.2 Sources of data and information

Starting point for the market analysis presented is the official information published from the European union in the Eurostat data portal (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/browse-statistics-by-theme>).

Several other data and information sources have been consulted, a selection of which is indicatively given in the following table.

Item	Source used in the document	Last update of source
CHP and energy use in the EU	Eurostat	August 2019
Energy product prices for households and the industry	Eurostat	September 2019
Compliance of EU-27 to the Paris climate agreement	"Off Target", Climate Action Network Europe	June 2018
National public support schemes to CHP	RES LEGAL Europe ² CODE2 project ³ Cross Border Bioenergy Project ⁴	November 2019
Biomass availability	SmartCHP project internal sources of information	January 2020
CHP capacities in the Netherlands	Inventory cogeneration Flanders	2016
Market segments	EU Buildings Database	Nov. 2020
CHP market	COGEN Europe National Snapshot survey	Nov. 2020
Energy	ODYSSEE-MURE	
Cordis database on relevant FP7 and H2020 funded projects		
IEA reports		

Table 2-1: A selection of sources of data and information

Highlights chapter 2:

The proposed market assessment is based on a multi-source analysis complemented by expert views from both the market side (energy managers or users from specific segments as well as cogeneration specialists through the support of Cogen Europe and the feedstock side including the project members.

The market analysis is performed at both levels, the regional level by selecting 5 focus countries and the demand by a customer segmentation.

² <http://www.res-legal.eu/about-res-legal-europe/>

³ <http://www.code2-project.eu/>

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/intelligent/projects/sites/iee-projects/files/projects/documents/crossborderbioenergy_chp_eu_market_handbook_en.pdf

3. CHP market in EU27

3.1 Current CHP market

This section presents an analysis of the evolution on the CHP technology share in the European Union, how much it contributes to the electricity generation, which are the primary fuels used and their trends, but also the use of CHP in the electricity (primarily) generation mix of the European countries.

3.1.1 Cogeneration in the power system

During last years, cogeneration has remained fairly stable at EU level, despite the fact that CHP systems have in general an overall higher efficiency for the conversion of fuel to heat and electricity, in comparison to other technologies. The share of cogeneration in the total electricity generation in EU-27 from 2009 to 2017 is presented in the Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Share of CHP in total electricity generation in EU-27

In the graph above, the share of CHP in total electricity generation at EU level displays small variations during the period from 2009 to 2017 and ranges between 11% (in 2014) and 12,4% (in 2010).

The drops in the CHP share have their origin in combinations of reasons. As such, the international oil prices or the increased penetration of RE electricity can be named amongst others. The international oil prices in the period 2005-2019 are given in Figure 3.2⁵. The slight drop in the CHP share observed in 2011 and 2014 coincides with the decline in the international oil prices, as highlighted in the graph below.

⁵ <https://www.macrotrends.net/1369/crude-oil-price-history-chart>

Figure 3.2: International Oil prices(2006-2020)

At the same time the penetration of renewable energy in the electricity generation mix has seen continuous increase, expressed through the increasing generation from RE (mainly solar and wind) as displayed in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Electricity generation from different sources in EU-27 in TWh (2009-2018)

As shown in the figure above, during last decade the use of biogas or biofuels displays a smooth but continuous share increase in the electricity generation mix.

Following this period, and until 2017, CHP share increases to reach 11,8% of the total electricity generation. Figure 3.4 displays the CHP utilization factor⁶ until 2016. It is noted that the utilization factor besides a stabilization period and a sharp drop in 2014, displays a smooth increase in the following years, which could be

⁶ **Utilization or capacity factor** expresses the ratio of actual thermal or electrical energy generation to the amount of heat or electricity that would be generated if the system operated at full load during all hours of the year.

partly attributed to the increase of the international oil (i.e. primary energy) prices between 2014 and 2018.

Figure 3.4: CHP Heat & Electricity Utilization Factors (2009-2017)

During the same period, EU and country level initiatives should be noted, for a more favourable and enabling environment for CHP in terms of the legislative and regulatory framework. These are presented in more detail in Chapter 5.3.

The CHP electrical and heat capacity at EU-27 and at country level are detailed in the following figures.

Figure 3.5: CHP electrical and heat capacity in GW in EU-28

The installed electrical and heat capacities of CHP units do not display large year by year variations between 2009 and 2017⁷.

Next section covers these capacities geographic wise.

⁷ For 2009 according to the Eurostat database approximately 40 GW of additional thermal capacity in Italy were declared as CHP_{th}

3.1.2 Cogeneration capacities in EU27

The electricity and heat capacity of installed CHP systems in European countries is illustrated in the following graph.

Figure 3.6: CHP electrical and heat capacity in GW by country (2017)

The ratio of produced heat over generated electricity differs largely between countries as displayed in Figure 3.7. Heat to electricity ratio can be an indirect indicator of each country’s “priorities” and uses of CHP technology, e.g. CHP driven district heating, as it happens for instance in Denmark, Slovenia, Romania, among others, or an indirect indicator of the technology mix employed for CHP in each country as different CHP technologies are characterized by different power-to-heat ratios⁸.

⁸ The **Power-to-heat ratio** (= C) is a characteristic of each CHP unit. It represents the ratio between electricity from cogeneration and useful heat when operating in full cogeneration mode.
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/38154/42195/Final_CHP_reporting_instructions_reference_year_2016_onwards_30052017.pdf/f114b673-ae3-499b-bf38-f58998b40fe6

Figure 3.7: CHP electrical and heat capacity in GW by country (2017)

(<https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/1.DHCpotentials.pdf>)

3.1.3 Cogeneration fossil and non-fossil fuels in EU27

In terms of CHP capacity in 2017, Germany has the largest installed capacity from all European countries, with approximately 40GW_e electrical capacity. In the Czech Republic, Poland, Finland, France or the Netherlands, CHP electrical capacity is approximately 10 GW, whereas for the rest of other EU-27 countries CHP_e capacity is much lower.

The use of various fuels for CHP systems in EU during the period from 2009 to 2017 is depicted in the following figure.

Figure 3.8: Evolution of CHP sources of energy(i.e. fuels) in the EU (2009 - 2017)

Fuels used by CHP systems/plants use different sources of primary energy, such as solid fuels and peat, oil and oil products, natural gas, RES and other fuels (including industrial wastes and coal gases). Natural gas is the main fuel used for CHP. However, from 2009 to 2017, there is a slight decrease in the usage of natural gas (from 48.3% in 2009 to 44.5% in 2017). In the same way, there is a significant decrease in the use of solid fossil fuels and peat (from 22.4% in 2009 to 16.2% in 2017), as well as in the use of oil and oil products (from 6.5% to 4.9%) and other fuels (from 9.2% to 6.3%). During the same period the share of RES and waste has more than doubled in the total fuel mix (from 13.7% in 2009 to 28% in 2017).

CHP fuel mix by country is presented in Figure 3.9 for 2017. It should be noted that this fuel mix refers to the installed CHP capacity only.

Figure 3.9: CHP fuel mix by country (2017)

As presented in Figure 3.9 above, natural gas has the largest share as a fuel source for CHP in several EU countries as for example in Malta, Netherlands, Spain, Hungary, Croatia, etc. An important fact displayed in this figure is the large share of renewables in some countries, reaching or exceeding 50% in the Scandinavian countries (i.e. Sweden (60%), Finland (62.4%) and Denmark (50.8%)), mainly attributed to the use of biomass. The high RES share in Cyprus (93.8%) is mainly attributed to several biogas plants (also considered as renewable fuel) in the country.

The share of CHP in total gross electricity generation in 2017 for the EU27 is presented in Figure 3.10. In all countries CHP technology participates in the electricity generation mix. The highest share of CHP in total gross electricity generation in 2017 was in Denmark (38%), Finland (32%), Netherlands (~ 27%) and Latvia (38%). This is primarily attributed to the fact that CHP units (mainly large scale) are used for district heating. (Note: In the following graphs red bars indicate the countries which have been selected as "focus" countries in section 5).

Figure 3.10: Share of CHP in total gross electricity generation in EU-27* (2017)⁹

Figure 3.11: Share of RES used for CHP in EU-27 (2017)

The % share of RES CHPs in total electricity generation depends on the share of CHP in total gross electricity generation and the % RES used for CHP. So, taking this into consideration, the % share of RES CHPs in total electricity generation is presented in Figure 3.12. Among the EU-27 countries, four countries display a RES CHP share higher than 10%, i.e. Denmark and Finland (~ 20%), Latvia (16%) and Lithuania (13%), mainly due to the use of biomass.

⁹ Eurostat statistics

* Red bars refer to the 5 focus countries

Figure 3.12: Share of RES CHPs in total electricity generation in EU-27 (2017)

Highlights chapter 3.1:

- A fairly stable penetration of CHP at EU level, reaching a CHP share of 11.8% in total electricity generation (EU27, 2017)
- A smooth but continuous share increase of use of biogas or biofuels in the electricity generation mix during last decades
- A CHP Heat and Electricity utilization factors appear quite correlated and ranging from 0.25 to 0.4: after a sharp drop in 2014 we notice a smooth increase in the following years, due probably to oil price evolution
- No large variation of the installed electrical and heat capacities of CHP units between 2008-2017
- Ratio of produced heat over generated electricity differs largely between countries, Heat to electricity ratio could be considered as an indirect indicator of each country's "priorities" and uses of CHP technology (e.g. District heating) and reflects the power mix of the country
- The share of CHP in total gross electricity generation in 2017 varies a lot from country to country for the EU27: the highest share of CHP in total gross electricity generation in 2017 was in Denmark (38%), Finland (32%), Netherlands (~ 27%) and Latvia (38%).
- These relative values have to be considered with absolute data: in terms of CHP capacity in 2017, Germany has the largest installed capacity from all European countries, with approximately 40 GW_e electrical capacity. In the Czech Republic, Poland, Finland, France or the Netherlands, CHP electrical capacity is approximately 10 GW_e, whereas for the rest of other EU-27 countries CHP_e capacity remains much lower.

3.2 Medium and large-scale CHP market

The medium and large-scale CHP installations (i.e. installations with an electrical output $> 1\text{MW}_e$) concern mainly the medium-large industrial sector and the electricity generation sector combined also with District Heating networks, which is a common practice in several European countries. This paragraph provides information on the medium & large CHP market segment, i.e. CHP units whose capacity is $>1\text{MW}_e$, having in mind such capacity is above the sizing range of SmartCHP.

Concerning countries with CHP already well adopted, as indicated in figure 3.6, **Germany** developed the largest capacities in terms of CHP over the last few years. Out of 36.600 units in total at the end of 2019, 1.332 units (i.e. 3,6% of the total number of units) have an installed capacity above 1MW_e corresponding to 22GW_e , i.e. 83% of the installed capacity.

Denmark and Spain are part of the second group leading group as we could see in figures 3.6. In **Denmark**, at the end of 2017, 22 large scale units (out of 659 in total CHP units) with a total capacity of 4,6 GW were operating, representing approximately 70% of the installed CHP electrical capacity of the country. As per the "ENERGY STATISTICS 2017", published by the Danish Energy Agency, "*district heating production is generated at large scale CHP units, small-scale CHP units, district heating units and by auto producers such as industrial companies, horticulture and waste treatment facilities*". In **Spain**, the fleet of medium/largescale units ($>1\text{MW}$) represents 65% of the total number of CHP Units in 2016 and 97,5% of the total CHP installed capacity in the country.

Finally, countries with few CHP capacities reveal a large adoption of medium and large-scale units. In Belgium, out of the 2,25 GW (2016) approximately 1,5 GW concerned medium/large CHP in 68 (i.e.10%) out of a total of 683 CHP installations. In Bulgaria, the number of medium/large units at the end of 2017 were 68 units (high and low efficiency, i.e. 63 with efficiency $>75\%$ and total electrical output of 930 MW and 5 with efficiency $<75\%$ and a total electrical output of 116 MW). In addition, a few units (11) between 1 and 2 MW were operating by IPPs at the end of 2017 with a total electrical capacity of 27,6 MW, serving industrial or agricultural facilities (e.g. greenhouses)

3.3 Small-scale CHP market

As per directive 2004/8/EC of 11 February 2004 on the promotion of cogeneration, "**small scale cogeneration**" means cogeneration units with an installed capacity below 1MW_e , which is exactly the scope of SmartCHP. In addition, micro-cogeneration unit means a cogeneration unit with a maximum capacity below 50kW_e ¹⁰

This part of the study provides information on the number and installed capacity of the CHP fleet in several countries of Europe with varying CHP share in the electricity generation. Best practices for CHP data collection is to consider representative countries such as Spain or the United Kingdom, which provide information in a concise and well-organized manner. Available information does not necessarily refer to the same year (e.g. 2017 or 2018) but to the year of the most recent data collection. The collection of information on the number and capacity of CHP

installations in the European countries has also revealed the necessity of a centralized CHP registry in each country which would collect and present information for all countries in a uniform manner.

As per directive 2004/8/EC of 11 February 2004 on the promotion of cogeneration, “**small scale cogeneration**” means cogeneration units with an installed capacity below 1 MW_e, which is exactly the scope of SmartCHP. In addition, micro-cogeneration unit means a cogeneration unit with a maximum capacity below 50 kW.¹¹

The table below presents the number of small-scale CHP units in some of the countries with the largest installed capacities, such as Germany, France, Denmark. Germany largely developed its small scale capacities, while France has only 100 MW_e developed. This difference can be explained by the adoption of CHP in residential sector in some EU countries, while other countries still present an unexploited potential for this type of CHP units.

Countries (last update)	Number of small scale CHP Units	Total capacity (MWe)
Germany (2019)	35270	4470
Denmark (2018)	637	1914
Italy (2016)	1403	1535
Belgium (2016)	615	637,6
United Kingdom (2018)	1960	395
Spain (2016)	229	142
France (2019)	-	100
Luxemburg (2014)	86	83
Latvia (2017)	110	72,9
Slovenia (2017)	446	60
Ireland (2015)	145	22,5
Bulgaria (2019)	6	2
Greece (2014)	3	1

Table 3-1: Number of small-scale CHP units and total capacity in selected countries

Figure 3.13 and Figure 3.14 present the number of small-scale CHP units (and relevant electrical capacity) for selected EU countries in terms of number and total capacities.¹²

¹¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2004:052:0050:0060:EN:PDF>

¹² It should be noted that for some of the countries data are not given specifically for small-scale CHP with capacity < 1MW, but also include larger units of more than 1 MW (e.g. 3-5 MW), e.g. Denmark.

Figure 3.13: Number of Small-scale CHP units

Figure 3.14: Small-scale CHP units in capacities

The detailed analysis per country is provided below.

In **Belgium**, at the end of 2016, the total number of CHP installations in Belgium was 683 distributed in 563 sites. Of these 683 installations 134 were installations with micro-motors (total 1,6 MWe) with an average capacity of 12 kWe and 481 engine-driven installations (total 636 MW) with an average capacity per installation 1,2 MW^(13, 14).

In **Bulgaria**, at the end of 2019, 6 CHP units below 1 MWe were operational in Bulgaria with electrical capacities ranging between 104 and 835 kWe. These units have been installed between 2002 and 2011¹⁵.

In **Germany**, as per the official register of the German Government, the number of installed and operating CHP units with a capacity less than 1 MWe in Germany

¹³ [Inventaris Vlaanderen](#)

¹⁴ <https://www.cogenvlaanderen.be/over-wkk/publicaties?types=5b6823bbd1798f6eac0070d4>

¹⁵ <https://portal.dker.bg/upload/files/16/reg-cert-final-jan2019.xlsx>

<https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/5049/electricity-and-heat-production-and-capacity-chp-units>

was 35.270 at the end of 2019¹⁶. The number of CHP installations per year in the country is given in Figure 3.15. The majority of these units (22.400 units) are units with an installed capacity of less than 50 kW_e. Approximately 25% of the less than 1MW installed units use biomass as primary fuel. Most of these units have been installed between 2004 and 2013.

Figure 3.15: Number of CHP installations in Germany since 1980

In **Denmark**, the number of small-scale CHP units at the end of 2018 was 637, with a total electricity capacity of 1914 MW and heat capacity 2442 MW.¹⁷ As indicated in the "Power and Gas sector outlook for infrastructure planning 2018" : "The total installed capacity of decentral CHP plants totalled around 2,400 MW at the beginning of 2018, representing around 1,000 larger or smaller plants. This capacity is expected to be reduced to around 1,700 MW by 2030 and around 1,470 MW by 2040, corresponding to a reduction of around 40% up to 2040. Among the reasons for this reduction the following among others are included: the removal of the basic-amount support scheme; the spot price of electricity which is expected to continue being relatively low in the future due to increased price pressure from the deployment of RE; or the expected increase in NG prices.¹⁸"

In **Spain**, out of the 651 operational CHP units, 229 units have an installed electrical capacity <1 MW_e as displayed in Figure 3.16. The information are provided by IDAE¹⁹ and refer to the end of 2016²⁰.

¹⁶ <https://www.marktstammdatenregister.de/>

¹⁷ <https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Statistik/energystatistics2017.pdf>

¹⁸ https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Analyser/power_and_gas_sector_outlook_for_infrastructure_planning_2018_o.pdf

¹⁹ Instituto para la Diversificación y ahorro de la Energía - Institute for the Diversification and Energy Saving

²⁰ [IDEA Estudios y estadísticas](#)

Figure 3.16: Number and capacity of CHP units in Spain (2016)

(Note: Information displayed in the graph refer to average capacities)

In **Ireland**, the total number of CHP installations at the end of 2015 was 385 (representing 342 MW), related to 366 units in 2014 (representing 339 MW), from which 104 units (representing 29.2 MW) were not operational. The number of small-scale installations were 145 (from 50 kW_e up to 1 MW_e), out of 281 operational and the capacity 25.2 MW, respectively.²¹

In **France**, at the beginning of 2019, there were already 1.024 CHP installation in France with a total capacity of 4,86 GW. Of this total installed capacity, approximately 100 MW concerned CHP installations with a capacity of less than 1 MW and approximately 5 MW concerned CHP installations of less than 250 kW²².

As regards **Greece**, in 2014, only 32 out of the 128 applications to the Greek Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE) have capacity from 100 kW to 1 MW. Although the low number of applications, the operating small-scale CHP units are only 3.

In **Italy**, at the end of 2016 the total number of CHP installations in Italy was 1.584. Of these installations 1403 CHP were engine-driven units with an average electrical capacity of 1 MW and 30 micro-turbine driven CHP units with an average electrical capacity of 130 kW. The total electrical capacity of the engine driven units reached 1.531 MW, whereas the total capacity of the micro-turbine driven units represented 4 MW. It must be noted that 245 engine-driven units and 11 micro-turbine-driven units were connected and were supplying heat to District Heating networks.²³

In **Luxembourg**, at the end of 2014 the total number of CHP installations was 133 (116,495 MW). The majority of these systems ranged from 150 to 1500 kW, 86 out of 133 in total and the relevant installed capacity was 83,816 MW).²⁴

In **Latvia**, the number of small-scale CHP installations (from 200 kW to 1 MW) in 2017 was 110 and below 200 kW was 28, out of 204 in total. The respective amount

²¹ <https://www.seai.ie/publications/Combined%20Heat%20and%20Power%20in%20Ireland%20Update%202016>

²² <https://atee.fr/system/files/2020-03/journ%C3%A9e%20micro%20cog%C3%A9%202019%20Intervention%20Club%20Cog%C3%A9.pdf>

²³ <https://www.mise.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/IT-RELAZIONE-ANNUALE-COGENERAZIONE-2018.pdf>

²⁴ <http://www.code2-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/CODE2-CHP-Roadmap-Luxembourg.pdf>

of total installed electrical capacity was 72.8 MW. There were also 59 CHP units from 1 up to 5 MW, 3 units from 5 to 20 MW and 4 units exceeding 20 MW²⁵.

In **Slovenia**, in 2017, the small-scale CHP units (from 50 kW_e to 1 MW_e) was 101, out of 466 in total. The majority of these units are micro systems (345) up to 50 kW²⁶ but small-scale CHP units amounts for the largest share of the installed capacity.

Finally, in **UK**, at the end of 2018, 1.960 installations with capacity less than 1 MW were operational in the United Kingdom with a total capacity of 395 MW. Of these CHP units, 679 had a capacity less than 100 kW_e (44 MW in total) and 1281 had a capacity between 100 kW and 1 MW (351 MW in total), as displayed in Table 3-2. It should be noted that microCHP schemes installed under FIT are not included in the table. At the end of 2017 a number of 515 such schemes were registered on Ofgem Central FIT Register totalling a capacity of 0.54 MW_e.

CHP installations by capacity and size range²⁷					
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Number of Schemes	2,071	2,130	2,224	2,409	2,473
<= 100 kW _e	607	615	642	671	679
> 100 kW _e to 1 MWe	1,099	1,129	1,183	1,244	1,281
>1 MWe to 2 MWe	132	141	151	189	200
> 2 MWe to 10 MWe	168	179	180	237	246
> 10 MWe +	65	66	68	68	67
Total Capacity	5,888	5,708	5,625	5,919	5,985
<= 100 kW _e	39	40	41	43	44
> 100 kW _e to 1 MWe	279	296	309	339	351
>1 MWe to 2 MWe	190	206	218	279	295
> 2 MWe to 10 MWe	778	818	824	1,054	1,091
> 10 MWe +	4,601	4,348	4,232	4,204	4,204

Table 3-2: CHP installations by capacity and size range

COGEN Europe²⁸ provided recent assumptions regarding market outlook for CHP technologies. Concerning small-scale CHP (50 kW_e – 1 MW_e), the following maps indicate the current trend and the outlook to 2024.

²⁵ <https://www.csb.gov.lv/en/statistics/statistics-by-theme/environment-energy/energy/search-in-theme/2401-activities-chp-plants-2017>

²⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/strokovne_podlage_porocilo_-24_en.pdf

²⁷ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/820736/DUKES_7.1.xls and <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/combined-heat-and-power-chapter-7-digest-of-united-kingdom-energy-statistics-dukes>

²⁸ COGEN Europe National Snapshot survey, November 2020

Figure 3.17: CHP market developments in Europe

Central Europe countries (France, Germany, Netherlands, etc) have interesting growth perspectives, while Spain and Portugal should be constant, and Italy and Greece could decline.

Highlights chapter 3.3:

- Definition of “small scale cogeneration” proposed by Directive 2004/8/EC defines, which reflects exactly the scope of SmartCHP
- Germany has the highest number of small-scale CHP units, the highest total capacity, respectively and a share of approx. 25% use biomass as a primary fuel
- Germany followed by Italy, Denmark in terms of CHP units
- In Belgium, at 2016 around 70% of CHP installations are engine-driven
- In Spain, more than one third of CHP units have an installed capacity below 1 MW
- According to COGEN Europe, the next years, Central Europe countries will focus more on CHP, followed by a possible growth

4. CHP Market Trends in EU27

4.1 Factors driving the market development

Factors driving the market development of a SmartCHP derive directly from the factors driving CHP market growth that are of various types, ranging from exclusive technical and inherent CHP factors to normative and financial support. Such factors include higher energy efficiency leading to lower operating costs, environmental regulations and policy support schemes and mechanisms. We organized them into six main types.

1. Policy support schemes and mechanisms as well as environmental Regulations

Several relevant regulations and legislations, including support schemes (subsidies and loans, etc.) and financial incentives have contributed to encourage the CHP market. Since the founding CHP Directive published in February 2004²⁹, European policies and legislation focused on encouraging the wider use of CHP. The main scope of this Directive was to promote high-efficiency cogeneration (minimum share of 10% of primary energy savings). In 2012, the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EC (EED) was issued and replaced Directive 2004/8/EC, introducing more specific measures related to CHP development in the EU countries.

Most EU countries, in order to meet their clean energy goals and to increase the share of CHPs fueled by RES in total electricity generation, have already developed new regulations or updated their existing ones in support of CHP. The support schemes existing in various EU Member include:

- Investment subsidies for potential demonstration projects, as in Belgium, Greece and Hungary
- Feed-in-tariff and feed-in premium schemes, such as in Germany, Hungary, Italy
- Loans or grants, e.g. in Finland, Germany, Slovenia
- Green certificates scheme, e.g. in Belgium, Romania
- Tax mechanisms, e.g. in Belgium, Poland, Greece.

The implementation of policy support schemes and mechanisms was the main reason for the CHP market growth in several countries. Such countries are **Belgium** (subsidies, green certificate scheme, tax reduction), **Luxembourg** (feed-in-tariff, grants), **Denmark** (tax exemption, feed-in-tariffs and feed-in-premiums, grants), **Germany** (loans, premium tariff) and **Italy** (premium tariff).

2. Lower Operating Costs

In comparison with the conventional power generation systems, CHP, by reducing energy intensity, yields monetary savings to the energy user. CHPs systems require less primary energy source for the same quantity of power and thermal energy output, which could reach approximately 40%, due to the higher overall efficiency of the CHP systems.

²⁹ **Directive 2004/8/EC** of the European Parliament and of the Council on the promotion of cogeneration based on a useful heat demand in the internal energy market and amending Directive 92/42/EEC

3. Reduction of energy consumption through increased efficiency

An advantage of using CHP systems is to increase the efficiency in both heat and electricity production, in comparison with the majority of fossil fired power plants. Moreover, key energy players in the CHP sector do not seem to share the same level of awareness as regard the role CHP can play at EU economy level, which is linked to the primary energy savings.

4. Market and Awareness actions

Relevant stakeholders, i.e. governmental authorities, energy agencies, International financing institutions, in cooperation with potential end-users (SMEs, industries, etc.) create several market and awareness actions, campaigns, etc. and take further actions in promoting and disseminating CHP benefits, whereas at the same time they encourage all the people to invest in CHP technology. In this way, it is created a more active and vibrant CHP community with a great influence to support the develop the sustainability of relevant regulatory and legislative environment.

5. Competition within CHP industry

Manufacturers have the potential to make CHP technology more attractive in terms of CAPEX, allowing energy managers to acquire robust and competitive systems.

6. Clean energy transition

This should impact positively the emergence of cogeneration solutions, and furthermore green supply for CHP. These systems can contribute for the reduction of GHG emissions and for the mitigation of emissions of air pollutants (NO_x, HC, PM). The reduction in GHG emissions achieved through the usage of lower quantity of fossil fuels, needed for the combustion. In addition, CHP systems can reduce air emissions of NO_x and HC, through the development of state-of-the-art CHP equipment.

The impacts of key factors in support of the promotion of CHP systems that can lead to CHP market growth are presented in the following table.

Factors driving the CHP market growth		Impact on the CHP sector
<i>REGUL</i>	Policy support schemes and mechanisms as well as environmental Regulations	+++++
<i>OPEX</i>	Lower Operating Costs	++++
<i>EFF</i>	Reduction of energy consumption through increased efficiency	+++
<i>MARKET</i>	Market and Awareness actions	++
<i>INDUSTRY</i>	Competitiveness of CHP industry	+++
<i>TRANSITION</i>	Clean energy transition	++++

Table 4-1: Factors driving the CHP market growth and estimation of their impact (+++++ most important, + less important)

The analysis of factors proves that there are different levels towards the enhancement of the further penetration and presence of CHP in the energy mix of each individual country and the EU.

- At a first level, central EU policy constitutes a fundamental tool setting the directions and the targets at EU and country level.
- Furthermore, at a second level, and in addition to the inherent financial advantages of CHP expressed through the reduction of the energy cost borne by the energy users, support schemes play a pivotal role towards such an increase of CHP penetration in the market, allowing users to assume short/medium term benefits through e.g. demand stimulation tools.
- Finally, market driven competition among technology suppliers offering a multiplicity of technological options addressed to different types and sizes of users, but also dissemination actions allow energy users to get acquainted with CHP technology and its benefits, be it e.g. financial or environmental.

This framework of factors constitutes a key entry analysis for the future go-to-market approaches and the techno-economic assessment foreseen in the future deployment of SmartCHP project.

Highlights chapter 4.1:

- Six types of factors (REGUL, OPEX, EFF, MARKET, INDUSTRY, TRANSITION) could speed up or hinder the market access
- As a whole they constitute a framework paving the way of future techno-economic assessment and go-to-market strategy for SmartCHP in a given area.

4.2 Cogeneration at mid-term horizon in Europe

4.2.1 The legislative and regulatory context

The evolution of the CHP market has been largely affected by the EU policies and legislative framework, developed among the last two decades. Since the CHP Directive published in February 2004³⁰, European policies and legislation, presented in the following, focused on encouraging the wider use of CHP. The main scope of this Directive was to promote high-efficiency cogeneration (with a minimum share of 10% of primary energy savings). Together with the Directive, a package of laws was adopted in 2007 and ratified in 2009 to meet the energy targets for the year 2020.

In 2012, the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EC (EED), published in order to replace the CHP Directive of 2004, introduced more specific measures, related to CHP development in the EU countries. The EED scope's is to promote CHP, by activating the EU countries to make an assessment of their potential CHP periodically (every 5 years)³¹. On 4 March 2019, the EC has adopted the Regulation 2019/826 amending Annexes VIII and IX to Directive 2012/27/EU of the European

³⁰ Already mentioned: Directive 2004/8/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the promotion of cogeneration based on a useful heat demand in the internal energy market and amending Directive 92/42/EEC

³¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:315:0001:0056:en:PDF>

Parliament and of the Council on the contents of comprehensive assessments of the potential for efficient heating and cooling.³²

In addition to the above Directive, a set of other Directives also came into force in order to encourage the promotion of the CHP market, i.e. the RE Directive (2009/28/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources), the EPBD Directive (2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings) and the Ecodesign Directive (2009/125/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for the setting of eco-design requirements for energy-related products).

As regards the long-term vision for a more climate friendly world and in the context of the Paris Agreement, the EU has already thought numerous ambitious targets to ensure that European countries are driving towards this way. First of all, the most important is to develop a stable legislative and regulatory framework in order to encourage potential end-users to invest in CHP and other sustainable energy projects, aimed to reduce the carbon intensity and improve the efficiency of each consumer. CHP units are used in different sectors (industries, households, hospitals, SMEs, etc.) and at the end of 2017, the CHP share of electricity and heat generation across the EU countries was 11% and 15%, respectively, and reduce more than 200 million tons of CO₂³³.

The 2030 climate and energy framework, adopted in 2014 and revised in 2018, include EU-wide targets and policy objectives for the period from 2021 to 2030³⁴. These key targets are: at least 40% cuts in greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990 levels); at least 32% share for renewable energy, and at least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency.

Considering the above targets and the huge potential in CHP sector, the contribution of these type of investments could play a significant role in reaching the target of 40% reduce in greenhouse gas emissions.

4.2.2 The cogeneration industry perspective

In this general policy context, COGEN Europe, as a key player in cogeneration industry, built a long-term vision until the 2050-time horizon.

Beyond 2030 and up to 2050, according to COGEN Europe, the CHP sector is expected to be considered as the main technology for the electricity generation and its capacity should be doubled, by increasing the share of renewable energy used.

This position was further clarified during the Cogen Europe Virtual Annual Conference held in 12-13 October 2020 involving high-level stakeholders and high-experience experts. These key messages are favourable to cogeneration in general but to SmartCHP in particular. We retained the following ones dealing with technical and non-technical impacts when considering higher penetration of cogeneration:

- Energy systems integration supported by EC in directives, communication or in the Vision 2050 of power system creates a huge opportunity for cogeneration. For the Committee on Industry, Research and Energy,

³² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019R0826&from=EN>

³³ https://www.cogeneurope.eu/images/COGEN_Europe_Input_Inception_Roadmap_Strategy_for_long-term_EU_greenhouse_gas_emissions_reductions_1.pdf

³⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/strategies/2030_en

European Parliament, Strategy on Energy Systems Integration will be important part of green recovery.

- Job creation. International Energy Agency estimates that 1 trillion of investments in EE and RES will create 9 million jobs for the next 3 years.
- Transport electrification. All electric is not feasible. We need efficient use of green molecules to complement electrification on our road to climate neutrality 2050.
- Towards a carbon neutral energy system. In terms of technology, with hydrogen readiness, cogeneration is expected to be the backbone technology to enable a carbon neutral energy system.

Figure 4.1: Long-term vision up to 2050 (COGEN Europe)

Highlights chapter 4.2:

- The EU “Vision to 2050” sets the targets for Renewable Energy penetration in Europe's Energy mix, the improvements in Energy Efficiency as well as the reduction in GHG emissions.
- The technological proposal expressed through SmartCHP addresses all three areas of this vision. It contributes to the improvement of Energy Efficiency, as it is by definition an Efficient Technology, thus contributing to the reduction of GHG emissions per unit of energy used, whereas it uses at the same time a RE fuel - Fast Pyrolysis Bio-oil - for the production of which, biomass is the source.

4.3 Market barriers for CHP installations

While the above market factors influence the facility to reach the market, market barriers refer to technical and non-technical objectives that could prevent from reaching them.

For further development of CHP installations, several barriers should be removed in order to achieve a significant increase in the total CHP share of electricity generation in each country. It should be noticed that these barriers have a local/regional character and are dynamically evolving, creating thus uncertainty for the market agents.

Cogeneration system economics is usually bound to regulatory and legislative context and to energy prices. For SmartCHP the supply chain matters which adds the specific barrier on biomass availability.

Figure 4.2: Overview of market barriers for cogeneration and SmartCHP

1. Regulatory and legislative uncertainty

Several countries have not developed a legislative and institutional framework and tooling for the CHP sector development. Despite the fact that countries promote renewable energy investments, they often exclude CHP installations, or suddenly interrupt support for new renewable energy power plants. As a result of this lack of regulations and support schemes they reach a low CHP share in total electricity generation³⁵.

Although, at European level, there is a large set of regulations and Directives, which aim to promote the CHP sector, at state level, governments follow different approaches, impeding the development of adoption CHP facilities. Another important factor for developing such large and complicated systems, is the existing legal, regulatory environment as well as the institutional arrangements and the permitting procedures.

2. Biomass availability

Considering that for the production of fast pyrolysis oil, three lignocellulosic feedstock categories should be used, which are agricultural residues, forest residues and organic waste residues. So, for the successful implementation of the project, it is crucial that the countries have sufficient quantity of biomass available for use. Most of the EU countries have a significant potential in biomass (at least

³⁵ For example, countries with lack of support schemes are Bulgaria, Cyprus (provides support schemes mostly for CHPs fuelled by biogas), Latvia, etc.

in one of the three categories mentioned). Such countries are Austria, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, etc. In the opposite side, there are a lot of countries that they do not have large quantities of biomass available for use, such as Cyprus, Ireland, Luxembourg, Malta, etc.

However, in addition to the biomass availability, it is significant to evaluate also the biomass competition in the country. For example, in France and in Italy, there is sufficient quantity on feedstock availability, but competition is extremely fierce due to a large number of CHP projects. So, the implementation of such a project in these two countries would face several difficulties. Another important thing needed to be evaluated, is land availability. For example, in Croatia, due to the recent war, there are large unexploited pieces of land, which can be used for dedicated biomass crops (e.g. Miscanthus). Another example is Slovakia in which a large land potential has not yet been exploited.

3. Energy prices uncertainty

The cost of primary energy (oil, natural gas, etc) or the electricity market prices affect the rate of CHP usage as CHP competes with conventional technological offerings.

Figure 4.3: Evolution of CHP share and electricity production in EU-27 (2009-17)

Error! Reference source not found. displays the CHP-generated electricity (as % of total electricity generation in EU27 and in GWh) in relation to the average EU-27 Natural Gas and electricity prices applying to the industrial sector³⁶. **Error! Reference source not found.**⁴⁴ **Error! Reference source not found.** It is observed that the CHP share follows an opposite trend with the Natural Gas prices in EU-27, i.e. with increasing NG prices CHP share displays a decline, as the cost of CHP-produced electricity is increasing, while at the same time the cost of the electricity in the market is kept fairly stable.

The trends described above provide indications of the correlation between the CHP share and the prevailing energy prices. **Error! Reference source not**

³⁶ the average electricity price is expressed in €/MWh multiplied x 3 and the NG price in €/Gigajoule multiplied x 20. These multiplications have been made for presentation purposes.

found.⁴⁵Error! Reference source not found.⁴⁶Error! Reference source not found.⁴⁷

Highlights chapter 4.3:

SmartCHP has to overcome several barriers for further market penetration including the regulatory framework, which needs to become effective and consistent, the availability of feedstock for the production of FPBO, as well as the price volatility of primary competing fuels or energy products.

Although FPBO availability may become a barrier to SmartCHP market penetration, its independence from the pricing trends of competing energy sources may lay the grounds and enhance the dynamics of the SmartCHP technology.

5. Definition of priority areas for SmartCHP

5.1 Analysis of the EU27 countries

5.1.1 Criteria for identifying priority areas

A multi-criteria methodology to identify priority areas was developed to select countries for further analysis considering CHP-type criteria such as support schemes, electricity price, biomass availability etc. and regional parameters.

The following table provides an overview of the criteria to be considered for identifying priority areas. The level of impact for the market potential of SmartCHP is detailed for each criterion. Criteria are organized according to four categories labelled **L** (Local energy context), **M** (energy Markets and trade), **N** (National/regional legal and regulatory context), and **O** that include all endogenous parameters (including FPBO plans and SmartCHP parameters).

Criteria considered in other related tasks of the projects have been highlighted in blue colour in the following table.

Id	Category	Criterion	Type	Impact for SmartCHP market assessment	Use in the project (T2.1; WP6)
L1	The local energy context	Availability of feedstock in the collecting range	Exogeneous	Go / No Go	Different parameters need to be considered: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of ligno-cellulosic feedstocks (e.g. wheat straw, wood, olive stones, ...) • Theoretic quantitative availability versus realistic • Competitive usages, realistic availability • Pricing, future prices • Distance to the BTG pyrolysis conversion plant (75-100km) • Accessibility of pyrolysis plant (road, train, water) • Distance from pyrolysis plant to CHP • Industrial symbiosis potential • Performance/conversion in BTG pyrolysis plant • Sustainability/LCA aspects (RED, OSS)
L2		Current penetration of CHP in the area	Exogeneous	Modulating factor	Included in T2.1

Id	Category	Criterion	Type	Impact for SmartCHP market assessment	Use in the project (T2.1; WP6)
L3		Energy mindset of citizens in the area	Exogeneous	Modulating factor	Impacting criterion for go-to-market strategy
L4		Strength of competition in the area (flexibility solutions or other competing technologies of SmartCHP)	Exogeneous	Modulating factor	Impacting criterion for go-to-market strategy
L5		Presence of insular territories	Exogeneous	Modulating factor	Included in T2.1
M1	Energy Markets and trade	Price of electricity: households	Exogeneous	High impact factor	Included in T2.1
M2		Price of electricity: industry	Exogeneous	High impact factor	Included in T2.1
M1 and M2		Electricity market trends	Exogeneous	High impact factor	Based on existing studies
M3		Price of gas: households	Exogeneous	Modulating factor	Impacting criterion for go-to-market strategy
M4		Price of gas: industry	Exogeneous	Modulating factor	Impacting criterion for go-to-market strategy
M5		Price of CO2	Exogeneous	Modulating factor	Impacting criterion for go-to-market strategy
M6		Compliance to the CO2 targets	Exogeneous	Modulating factor	Included in T2.1
N1		National /regional regulatory context	Existence of National public support schemes to CHP	Exogeneous	High impact factor
N2	Existence of National public support schemes to biomass industry		Exogeneous	High impact factor	Included in WP6 assessment
O1	FPBO and SmartCHP	Plans for FPBO in the area	Endogenous	High impact factor	Included in WP6 assessment

Id	Category	Criterion	Type	Impact for SmartCHP market assessment	Use in the project (T2.1; WP6)
O2	related parameters	Matching of SmartCHP offer to the local energy needs	Endogenous	High impact factor	Included in WP6 assessment

Table 5-1: Criteria used for identifying priority areas

5.2 Policy framework in EU27

A comprehensive presentation of support schemes for CHP in EU27 with renewable fuels available in the EU countries is given. In more detail, this chapter reviews and analyses the existing legislative framework and policies applicable for energy from CHP fuelled with renewable sources at an EU and regional level.

Numerous support schemes exist in various EU Member States that support the promotion of the CHP market. These are:

- Investment subsidies for potential demonstration projects. Examples of such countries are Belgium, Greece and Hungary
- Feed-in-tariff and feed-in premium schemes, i.e. Germany, Hungary, Italy
- Loan or grants, i.e. Finland, Germany, Slovenia
- Green certificates scheme, i.e. Belgium, Romania
- Tax mechanisms, i.e. Belgium, Poland, Greece
- Quota system, i.e. Sweden, Romania.

However, several barriers hinder the development of the market such as the uncertainty of the regulatory and legislative framework and issues related to grid connection, permitting and bureaucracy. Policy framework parameters are identified in above table as L2 and N1.

5.3 EU support schemes

In order to provide the current situation of the CHP regulatory framework in EU countries, a grouping of countries was considered based on their geographical location of each country. This initial categorization is based on similar climate characteristics, CHP conditions and logistical infrastructure. A similar categorization was carried out in Cogeneration Observatory and Dissemination Europe (CODE2) project. The countries in each region are presented below:

- North-Western Europe: Belgium, Ireland, Luxembourg and Netherlands
- Northern Europe: Austria, Denmark, Finland, Germany and Sweden
- Eastern Europe: Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Croatia and Poland
- South-West Europe: France, Italy, Malta, Portugal and Spain
- South-East Europe: Bulgaria, Cyprus, Greece and Romania.

5.3.1 North-Western Europe

Belgium

The most common fuel type for CHP plants is natural gas, however in Wallonia region, renewables are the dominating “fuel”. The share of renewables in CHP for

Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels was about 15% in 2010. In 2010, Wallonia had the highest percentage of CHP plants fuelled with renewables of the 3 regions with more than 50%, while in Brussels and Flanders, the percentage was around 1% and 5% respectively. In 2017, at country level the total share of CHP fuelled by RES was 15.4%.

The **CHP market in Belgium is growing during the last 15 years** with an installed capacity of more than 2,000 MW in 2016. This market growth is largely attributed to the development of policy issues related to investment support, **in the form of subsidies** (grants, Brussels and Walloon region) and **green certificate schemes** (Flanders region), adopted in 2005. The green certificates issued in all regions in Belgium, but practical implementation is different between the regions. In general, CHP certificates operates as an award of CO2 savings in comparison to a reference installation. Each owner receives a number of certificates every month and he can sell them to the electricity suppliers for a price, relevant to the market. The suppliers have the obligation to buy a minimum number of these.

At country level, financial support is provided through a **reduction of the taxable profits with an amount of 14.5% of the investment**. In more specific, the Brussels region issues an investment subsidy in the form of a grant, ranging from 3,500 to 4,500 EUR, depending on the income category. In the Flemish region, the granting of certificates has been issued since 2005. Certificates are granted per MWh of primary energy savings and one green certificate for each MWh of green electricity. **After the development of this support scheme, a large number of certificates were sold with the lowest price, related to the market price**. The financial support for each CHP end-user depends on the number and the market value of certificates. The range of the certificates is between 31 and 41 EUR per certificate. A CHP plant is able to receive 1 certificate per 1000 kWh of primary energy savings. For power plants that generate more than 200 kW of electricity from RES, a green certificate can be obtained only if an inspection report of the installation is submitted to the Flemish Energy Agency. In the Flanders region, there is a similar financial support scheme, where the so-called Green Electricity Certificates can be traded. An important factor for CHPs fuelled with renewables is that they can obtain **both CHP and Green Electricity Certificates**.

In the Walloon region, a **green certificate for CHP** investments is issued, depending on the electricity production of the investment and the amount of CO2 reduction in comparison to a reference installation. Consequently, one green certificate is issued for a reduction of 456 kg of CO2 emissions. In case of CHPs fuelled with renewables, the reduction is expected to be significant, therefore more certificates are expected to be granted. The certificates have a validity of 5 years. The region has also set a warranty price for each green certificate which equals to 65 EUR.

Ireland

The installed CHP capacity in Ireland has a **slight increase during the period from 2005 to 2016**. In 2016, the installed capacity was 330 MW, related to almost 110 MW in 2005. According to Eurostat, the most dominant fuel for CHP plants is natural gas, representing more than 90% of the capacity and the largest share of operational capacity is in industry, despite the majority of installed units located in the service sector, i.e. hospitals, hotels, etc., while RES represents 3.3%.

Among the last 5 years, the government of Ireland made several attempts to support the CHP market through incentives but **unfortunately without success**. Electricity from RES was promoted through a renewable energy feed-in-tariff scheme (REFIT). In the past, there were three REFIT schemes, establishing support for various sources of energy. REFIT 1, 2 and 3 supported technologies until the end of 2015, and currently are closed for new applications. The government of Ireland announced a new renewable energy support scheme which is expected to be issued this year. No further information is available though.

Luxembourg

Luxembourg has more than 130 operational CHP plants, mostly with a capacity up to 1.5 MW (more than 50%) and the total electricity generation was around 15.5% in 2017, related to 10.1% in 2005. In 2017, the share of CHP fuelled by RES was 38.6%, compared to 0% in 2005.

The government of Luxembourg has implemented an investment support scheme for CHP plants per each category (small, medium and big) in the form of a **feed-in tariff mechanism**. This **mechanism promotes all renewable technologies** and the amount depends on the size and type of fuel of each plant. The feed-in tariff is guaranteed for an eligibility period of 15 years. For example, the amount for a biomass plant with a nominal capacity up to 1 MW equals to 16.2 EUR/kWh.

In addition, an **investment grant is given to industrial companies which invest in electricity generation from RES**. The amount of grants may be **up to 45%** of the additional costs arising from the use of renewable energy related to non-renewable.

The Netherlands

Netherlands has a large installed CHP capacity compared to other technologies, mainly located in industry and the district heating sector. The total CHP electricity generation is stagnated during the last 10 years, in a range of 30 TWh to 35 TWh, representing around 27% of the total electricity generation, while the most common fuel for CHP plants is natural gas (around 80% out of total number of CHP plants), related to a share of 8.6% for CHP plants fuelled by RES.

In Netherlands, a **feed-in premium subsidy is provided in CHPs fuelled with renewables**. This subsidy is given through the Sustainable Energy Incentive Scheme Plus (SDE+)³⁷. The SDE+ promotes renewable energy by offsetting the financial gap between production expenses and renewable power market prices. The premium is paid for a period of up to 12 years, starting at the date of commissioning of the plant and is eligible for all end-users, i.e. private individuals, companies, institutions, etc. The premium tariff is 0.073 EUR/kWh for CHP plants higher or equal to 0.5 MW and smaller or equal to 100 MW.

Conclusions

Most of the countries located in North-Western Europe, have a very active CHP market and the sector is widespread. Following this trend and for their continuous

³⁷ <https://www.rvo.nl/subsidies-regelingen/stimulering-duurzame-energieproductie/categorie%C3%ABn/biomassa-sde>

growth in this sector, governments make several attempts for the further development. Except Ireland, Belgium and the Netherlands have already introduced a number of support schemes and the introduction of CHP installations fuelled by RES seems to be attractive.

5.3.2 Northern Europe

Austria

The **development of CHP in Austria was stable** due to the limited number of governmental support, despite the huge potential. The share of CHP in total electricity generation was around 13.5% (10 TWh) in 2017 and those fuelled by RES represented more than 40% (40.3%) out of the total CHP plants, while the hydropower share was more than half.

The first CHP act for providing investment support expired in 2012. Following this Act, a **feed-in-tariff support scheme for CHPs fuelled with biofuels**, natural gas or LPG was applied. All the plants should be registered in a database for green electricity plants³⁸. The subsidy amount for CHP plants differs and it is based on the year of the installation of the facility. For 2019, the subsidy amount equals to 5.4 EUR/kWh³⁹.

Denmark

Denmark has one of the **most developed CHP markets** among all EU member states, with a total power production of about 40% and the total CHP electricity generation is around 12 TWh in 2017 (38.1% share in total electricity generation). The **CHP fuelled with RES represents more than 50% out of the total**. The main goal of the country is to expand the CHP fuelled by RES, in order to replace natural gas and coal.

Denmark started the development of CHP in the decade of 1980, as a reaction to the oil crisis. Due to governmental efforts in energy efficiency, including CHP technology, Denmark is energy self-sufficient the last 20 years. The high share of CHP is mainly due to a far developed district heating network. In the past, there were a number of support schemes for CHP installations, such as tax exemption, feed-in-tariffs and feed-in-premiums, subsidies in the form of grants.

However, in 2019 in Denmark there is a lack of support schemes related to CHP market. The existing incentives focus mainly on solar and wind energy or on small scale biomass plants (up to 6 kW).

Finland

Finland is rated as one of the **top countries in CHP industry**, with a share of more than 32% in total electricity production (around 22 TWh) in 2017, while the share of CHP fuelled by RES is 62.4% and the CHP share in industrial sector was around 85% in 2011.

In Finland there is a **state grant**, the so-called “energy aid”, for RES installations which promote the use or production of renewable energy and reduce the environmental effect. The energy aid can be granted to all end-users, i.e.

³⁸<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=20007386>

³⁹<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=20010106>

companies, municipalities and other communities. The amount of the energy aid depends on the project's scope. The minimum support for RE production facilities can be **30% of the total project's value**. In the case of an investment project, the energy aid may be increased by 10% (total 40%) in case the project incorporates new technology⁴⁰. In addition, the grant of energy aid received by a CHP plant shall finance at least 25% of the project with non-public funding.

Germany

From the beginning of this century and until 2017, **CHP has a positive trend**. The total CHP electricity generation in 2017 was around 95 TWh and the respective share 14.4%. The total share of CHP plants fuelled by RES in 2017 was 23.4%.

In Germany, the **BMU** – Innovation Programme which supports large installations with the potential to reduce environmental impact, is one of the main support schemes. This scheme provides a **low-interest loan of 70% of the overall investment costs or a subsidy of 30% of the investment costs**. The loan should be paid off in a period of 30 years maximum, including a maximum 5-year repayment-free start-up period and it is charged a commitment fee of 0.25% per month.

According to the Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz - Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) published in 2017, the **premium tariff** has become the **main support scheme for electricity from RES**. The amount of the premium tariff ranges from 5.71 to 13.32 EUR/kWh. For power plants with a rated capacity up to 500 kW, the amount is 11.49 EUR/kWh.⁴¹ Also, according to the EEG, the plant operator is obliged to present a copy of record of the type, quantity and origin of the substances used and provide evidences that these are the only substances used in the power plant.

Sweden

In Sweden, from 2010 to 2016, there is a slight decrease in total CHP electricity generation (from 18.5 TWh in 2010 to 9.01 TWh in 2017 and the share was declined up to 5.5% in 2017, from 12.5% in 2010. Despite this decrease during the last years, the share of CHP fueled by RES was 60% in 2017.

Sweden **supports renewables** through the Act No. 2011:1200 (Lag om elcertifikat – Electricity Certificates Act). **A quota system is used**, in which end-users receive renewable energy certificates based on their consumption in a specific date. The quota will be calculated by multiplying the number of MWh of electricity used during the calculation year with the quota obligation for the calculation year. The amount of the quota obligation per MWh of electricity consumed for the period from 2018 to 2045, is defined in the Act No. 2011:1200, Chapter 4, Section 4 § 5b.⁴² Indicatively, the amounts for 2019 and 2020 equal to 0.305 EUR/MWh and 0.288 EUR/MWh, respectively.

Conclusions

⁴⁰ <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/2012/20121063#P7>

⁴¹ https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/eeg_2014/BJNR106610014.html

⁴² https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-20111200-om-elcertifikat_sfs-2011-1200

Based on the above, it is evident that there are different approaches for each country. The most promising countries in this region, according to the CHP share and the existing support schemes are mainly **Germany, Denmark and Finland**. Austria, despite its significant potential, has no well-developed support scheme.

5.3.3 Eastern Europe

Czech Republic

Despite Czech Republic is one of the most promising member state among the EU countries with a long tradition in CHP market and a well-developed small-scale CHP market, the government stopped the support for new RES plants from the beginning of 2014. This was the main factor for the decrease in electricity generation to 7.99 TWh in 2017 (9.2% share in total electricity generation), instead of 11.8 TWh in 2014 (13.7% share in total electricity generation). However, the total share of CHP fuelled by RES in 2017 was 14.6%, related to 12.7% in 2014. Nowadays, the only support scheme for CHP plants is a tax regulation mechanism, which exempts the CHP operator from the real estate tax⁴³.

Estonia

The share of CHP plants in electricity generation at country level was around 8.4% in 2017. **RES is the most dominant fuel for CHP plants with a share of more than 65% in 2017, compared to 0% fuelled by natural gas and 9.3% by oil.** The CHP market in Estonia has a **long cogeneration tradition** and growth of CHP plants is driven through the use of RES instead of traditional fossil fuels. Estonia introduced the **first support scheme for electricity production from CHP plants, using RES** in 1998. Due to growth of natural gas prices, the support schemes focused on CHP development, fuelled by RES.

The Ministry of Economics and Communication (MKM) will announce in 2019 (still pending), public tenders, in the form of reverse auctions, to reach the national objectives in electricity consumption of RES by 2020. According to the ELTS (Elektrituruseadus RT I 2003, 25, 153 – Electricity Market Act)⁴⁴, the government of Estonia supports by means of reverse auction, investments using RES with a capacity up to 1 MW. **The scope of these tenders is to have 10% of the final electricity consumption produced by CHP plants by the end of 2020.**

Hungary

Until 2016, the CHP market in Hungary was decreasing due to the expansion of nuclear power and the decrease of heat demand. Compared to 8.43 TWh (21.1%) of CHP electricity generation in 2008, the respective number in 2017 was 4.65 TWh (14.1%). The total share of RES CHP plants represented 14% out of the total in 2017.

However, in the last years the government attempts to reach a **share of at least 20% of electricity generation in 2030 from micro- and bio-CHP**. In this context, the government promotes **support schemes, in the form of subsidies for installations up to 1 MW**.

⁴³ <https://www.zakonyprolidi.cz/cs/1992-338>

⁴⁴ <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/527122016001/consolide/current>

According to the Decree No. 299/2017⁴⁵, which came into force in 2017, different forms of subsidies are provided for RE plants with capacity between 50 – 500 kW and 500 kW – 1 MW. For power plants of the first category, the end-user may choose between the **feed-in-tariff** or the **feed-in-premium (green premium)**. In more detail, the feed-in-tariff for plants up to 500 kW is around 0.1105 EUR/kW during the peak period (06:00 to 22:00), 0.0989 EUR/kW in valley period (22:00 to 01:30 and 05:00 to 06:00) and 0.0404 EUR per kW in deep-valley period (01:30 to 05:00). The amount of feed-in-tariff depends on the time period of the day, the geographical area where the electricity is generated; it varies between weekdays and weekends and also between summer and winter time.

The **feed-in-premium**, came into force the beginning of 2017 and is eligible for renewable power plants up to 1 MW. Related to this form of subsidy, power plants of more than 500 kW are promoted without tendering. The amount of feed-in-premium is stable during the whole year and is 0.0989 EUR/kW.

Latvia

Latvia from 2005 to 2017 increased its CHP capacity and currently is one of the **top EU countries** with a share of 37.7% in electricity generation (around 3 TWh) and the **share of CHP fuelled by RES is 44.1%**.

Although, Latvia is one of the most developing countries regarding CHP capacity, there is a lack of support schemes. A **feed-in-tariff subsidy was in force from 2007, but unfortunately suspended until the end of 2019**. In addition, and according to Energy Development Guidelines 2016-2020, the government of Latvia planned to introduce a new support mechanism to produce electricity from RES until the end of 2018, but until today no plans have been implemented.

Lithuania

The government of Lithuania focused the last years on decreasing the import of electricity (more than 50%). The key goal of the government is to increase electricity generation from CHP plants using RES for more than 2 TWh until 2030, instead of 1.1 TWh in 2017 (26.2% of the total share). From 2015 to 2017, Lithuania has made a rapid growth in CHP installation fueled by RES, from 33.8% in 2015 to 49.7 in 2017.

According to the Law on Energy from Renewable Sources⁴⁶, the government promotes power plants with a capacity between 10 kW – 5 MW, in a form of **feed-in-tariffs**, by participating in a tendering procedure (auctions). These auctions are organized by the National Energy Regulatory Council (NERC) and the tariffs revised every 3 months. The NERC sets the maximum feed - in tariffs and are guaranteed for 12 years. The amount of feed-in-tariff in the first quarter of 2019 is 0,040 EUR per kWh⁴⁷.

Slovakia

⁴⁵ http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=204718.345044

⁴⁶ <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/TAR.FC7AB69BE291/asr>

⁴⁷ <http://www.regula.lt/en/Pages/tariffs-for-electricity-from-res.aspx>

Slovakia was one of the most developed countries with a CHP share of around 25% in total electricity generation in 2011 but in the next years there was a decrease, which reached in 12.5% in 2017 and around 14% provided by RES CHP plants.

At country level, a **fixed feed-in-tariff is the main support scheme for electricity from RES**. The amount of tariff varies according to the year of commissioning of the plant. According to Decree No. 18/2017⁴⁸, which came into force in 2017, the amount of the tariff for CHP plants commissioned from 1 January 2017, is 0.08086 EUR/kWh and the eligibility period is 15 years, according to national RES Act⁴⁹.

In addition, a **tax regulation mechanism (exemption from tax)** is promoted for the renewable electricity generation technologies.

Slovenia

Slovenia has a **stable growth of the CHP generation during the last decade**, with a total share of 7.7% in the total electricity generation (1.2 TWh) and 21.7% from RES CHP plants, in 2017. Since the majority of the plants are district heating plants, industry has a large potential for further development of CHP.

In Slovenia, the Environmental Fund (Eko sklad) is available which supports RE installations through a tendering process. This support scheme provides **low interest loans** and the amount of the loan is depends on the amount of eligible costs, the type of investment, the evaluation of the environmental criteria and the total budget indicated in each tender call. The loan should be paid off in a period of 15 years and the interest rate is the three-month Euro Interbank Offered Rate (EURIBOR) rate plus 1.3%.

Poland

Poland has one of the largest share of CHP among the EU countries. In 2010, was the top country in installed capacity with more than 32 GW and the share of CHP electricity generation was around 28%. In 2017, the total CHP electricity generation was 28.43 TWh (16.7 total share of CHP) and the CHP plants fuelled by RES was 9.5%

The main support scheme for RE use in Poland are **tenders, in the form of a bidding process** and the winner of each tender gets a guaranteed price per kWh for 15 years, in case the power plants is up to 500 kW.

In addition, a **tax regulation mechanism (exemption from tax)**, is promoted for the renewable electricity generation technologies.

Croatia

Croatia has a slight decrease in the share of CHP in total electricity generation during the last 5 years, from 20.1% (2.21 TWh) in 2011 to 16.7% (2 TWh) in 2017. The respective share of CHPs fuelled by RES in 2011 was below 1% and in 2017 increased to 8%, but it is still remaining as one of the lowest share among the EU member states.

⁴⁸ <https://www.zakonypreludi.sk/zz/2017-18>

⁴⁹ <https://www.zakonypreludi.sk/zz/2009-309>

From the beginning of 2016, the government of Croatia, according to the Act on Renewable Energy Sources and High-efficiency Cogeneration, promotes RES investments with a capacity up to 500 kW, through an incentive in the form of a **premium tariff and a guaranteed purchase price (feed-in tariff), after a tendering procedure**. The amount of this price established by the Croatian Energy Market Operator (HROTE), which select the lowest bidder in the tendering procedure and it remains stable for 12 years.

Moreover, Croatia provides a **loan for the implementation of RES investments** by the Croatian Bank for Reconstruction and Development (HBOR) in cooperation with commercial banks. The minimum amount of this loan is approximately 13,000 thousand EUR and the maximum amount depends on the bank's financial capability, the specific investment programme and the creditworthiness of the end borrower, but in any case, will not exceed 75% of the investment value.

Conclusions

CHP market is a traditional market in all member states in Eastern region, with a share of CHP above the EU average in electricity generation. **Hungary** is the most promising countries in this region, resulting from the CHP development during the last years, which focused mainly in CHP fuelled by RES. Despite Czech Republic has a well-developed small-scale CHP market, the last 5 years the government's aim is almost zero. In Latvia there is a lack of support schemes, while in Lithuania, the government makes attempts to decrease electricity imports, but it is still at an early stage. Slovakia's, Slovenia's and Estonia's shares of CHP are in small rates.

5.3.4 South-West Europe

France

Due to the strong competition of other technologies, France has not been very active in CHP market. However, the government made an effort for the development of bio-CHP, targeted to 2.3 GW by 2020, instead of 877 MW in 2008. From 2008 to 2017, the total CHP electricity generation has a slight decrease from around 18 TWh (3.1% share of CHP) to 16.64 TWh (3% share of CHP). The total share of RES CHP plants in 2017 was 27.8%.

Unfortunately, **support schemes in France are not familiarized to small-scale CHP plants** and focused either on large scale applications (>12 MW) or in micro applications (less than 50 kW).

Italy

CHP is widely used in Italy, with an increase between 2004 to 2017 by almost half of the generation, from 27.39 TWh to 40.96 TWh, despite a stagnation in the beginning of 2010. In 2017, the share of CHP in total electricity generation was 15.8%.

At country level, a **premium tariff is the main support scheme for electricity from RES**. The power plant operator can sell the produced energy on the free market or sell it to the Gestore dei Servizi Energetici (GSE Energy Services Manager SpA), which is the manager of the support schemes. But, in case the market price is higher than the guaranteed minimum price, the producer receives an annual

adjustment. The amount of premium tariff is calculated according to AEEG 280/07⁵⁰ and depends on the value of the guaranteed price in the current and in the previous years.

Malta

CHP in Malta has not been yet developed due to some infrastructural and market barriers and legislative framework. In 2017, the CHP electricity generation was 0.21 TWh (12.6% CHP share) and the share of RES CHP was 2.7%. Malta is mainly focused on onshore and offshore wind and solar energy (solar photovoltaic and solar thermal energy). The government made several attempts to support the CHP market, in the form of green tariffs but until today **with no success**.

Portugal

CHP in Portugal is focused mainly in the industrial sector, with a few applications in buildings and district heating. The total CHP electricity generation in 2017 was 6.4 TWh and the total share was 10.8%, while the share of RES CHP was 46.3%.

At country level, a **feed-in-tariff is the only support scheme**, came into force in 2015, and promotes RE installations. Decree 153/2014 separates the installations in two categories according to their use, Small Production Units (UPP) and Self-consumption Units (UPAC). UPPs can have a maximum capacity of 250 kW and UPACs from 200 kW up to more than 1 MW. The amount of feed-in-tariff is 90% of the reference tariff, which is published at the end of each year by the government⁵¹.

Spain

Despite the economic crisis and no governmental aim, Spain has a small growth in the last 15 years, increasing the current CHP electricity generation from 23.21 TWh in 2005 (4% CHP share) to 28.77 TWh in 2017 (10.4%). The total share of RES CHP plants was 8.9% in 2017.

In Spain, the main support scheme's scope, established in 2014, is to grant a **specific remuneration regime (premium tariff) for new RE plants**. The premium tariff is given through tendering procedure and each tender clarifies the eligible technologies. Currently, no tenders are available for CHP.

Conclusions

According to the data presented above, **Italy** seems to be the most promising country.

5.3.5 South-East Europe

Bulgaria

Bulgaria has a long history in the CHP sector, focused mainly in district heating and in the energy-intensive industrial sector. After the implementation of the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), there are estimations for increasing the total share of CHP electricity generation from 7.7% (3.53 TWh) in 2017 up to 14% in 2030. The total share of RES CHP plants was 10.3% in 2017.

⁵⁰ <https://www.arera.it/allegati/docs/07//280-07ti.pdf>

⁵¹ <https://dre.pt/web/guest/pesquisa/-/search/66321165/details/normal?!=1>

Unfortunately, **small-scale CHP plants (up to 1 MW) are under-developed**, due to the fact that support schemes in the country focus on power plants with an installed capacity more than 4 MW.

Cyprus

Cyprus is **not considered as an active market in CHP market**. The share of CHP in total electricity generation is less than 1% in (0.03 TWh) in 2017 and the existing installations use biogas as a primary fuel.

Support schemes at country level **are not well-developed**, promoting mainly the net-metering system for CHP plants installation in buildings (including commercial and industrial buildings).

Greece

Despite the long tradition and the establishment of several support schemes for the promotion of CHP, Greece has one of the lowest shares of CHP electricity generation among EU countries (3.9% and 2.15 TWh in 2017) and the RES CHP share was 0.6%.

The main support scheme is the **feed-in-tariff**, came into force in 2015. The amount of feed-in-tariff is 198 EUR/MWh⁵² and is eligible for 20 years.

In addition, from 2014, a **net-metering system** was introduced for CHP plants. The amount of this depends on the electricity produced by the power plant and the energy consumed.

Moreover, the Development Law⁵³, published in 2016, provides **support in the form of a subsidy** for CHP plants. The amount of the subsidy can be up to 15% of the eligible costs. As concerned eligible costs include costs for the installation of the equipment needed for the CHP plant.

Also, the Development Law introduces a **tax regulation mechanism**, in the form of an income tax relief for 12 years or the stabilization of income tax coefficient, in 10% of the total investment cost.

Romania

The government of Romania has introduced a few support schemes for the further development of CHP sector. After 2008 and up to 2013, there is a small growth in share of the total electricity generation, from 9.6% to 11.2%, but since 2017 there was a slight decrease (9%), while the total RES CHP share was 5.6% in 2017.

The main support scheme for the promotion of **electricity from RES in Romania** is the **quota system**, which is based on **green and tradable certificates**. The amount of the quota for the following year is established by the Romanian Energy Regulatory Authority (ANRE) at the end of current year, depending on an estimation of the final energy consumption for the next year and the medium impact on consumers that should not exceed the price of 13 EUR/MWh in 2020. The exact number of green certificates depends on the used technology. For CHP plants

⁵² https://helapco.gr/ims/file/english/law_3468_2006_eng.pdf

⁵³ https://www.ependyseis.gr/anaptyxiakos/files/GR_Development_Law_En_2.pdf

fuelled by RES, 3 certificates/MWh⁵⁴ can be sold on the centralized market of the green certificates, as well as on the market of the bilateral contracts of the green certificates. For the period 2017-2032, the minimum amount of trading value may not be lower than the minimum amount of trading value applied in 2014, which was 29.4 EUR/certificate and the maximum 35 EUR/certificate⁵⁵.

Conclusions

The countries in the South-East region have a long tradition in CHPs, except Cyprus. However, the share of the electricity generation in those countries are one of the lowest among all the member states.

5.4 Cross-country comparative overview

Based on the above analysis, several Member States are active or have a long tradition with CHP applications using RES. A number of support schemes (feed-in-tariffs, subsidies, grants, etc.) to promote the development of CHP is available in many Member States. The following table provides a summary of support schemes that are in place in the Member states and a qualitative assessment for further analyses⁵⁶. From the analysis presented above, a colour code grading between the countries is applied and has the following meaning:

Meaning	Colour Code
Under-developed	
Moderate / needs improvements	
Fairly well developed / advanced	

Table 5-2: Colour code grading used for the country rating

EU Member State	Type of support	Comments	Country rating
Austria	Feed-in-tariff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RES CHP share: 40.3% Stable CHP development 	
Belgium	Subsidies (grants), Green certificates,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RES CHP share: 15.4% CHP sector in Belgium is growing in the last 15 years and in some regions, renewables are the most common fuel for CHP (Wallonia) 	

⁵⁴

http://www.dreptonline.ro/legislatie/oug_88_2011_modificare_stabilirea_sistemului_promovare_producere_energie_surse_regenerabile_energie.php

⁵⁵ <https://lege5.ro/Gratuit/ge2tkmjrgmzq/ordonanta-de-urgenta-nr-24-2017-privind-modificarea-si-completarea-legii-nr-220-2008-pentru-stabilirea-sistemului-de-promovare-a-produserii-energiei-din-surse-regenerabile-de-energie-si-pentru-modific>

⁵⁶ It is EXERGIA's opinion based on the analysis presented previously. In addition, most of the countries proposed, are also top rated in other reports that we reviewed, such as in the EU Handbook CHP Markets (https://ec.europa.eu/energy/intelligent/projects/sites/iee-projects/files/projects/documents/crossborderbioenergy_chp_eu_market_handbook_en.pdf)

EU Member State	Type of support	Comments	Country rating
	tax reduction		
Bulgaria	Lack of support schemes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 10.3% • Small-scale CHP plants (up to 1 MW) are underdeveloped 	
Croatia	Feed-in-tariff or premium tariff, loan for RES investments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 8% • Croatia has one of the lowest share of CHP fuelled by RES among the EU member states • Established a few support schemes to promote RES investments with a capacity up to 500 kW 	
Cyprus	Lack of support schemes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 93.8% • Use of biogas as a fuel • Support schemes are not so well-developed 	
Czech Republic	Tax regulation mechanism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 14.6% • Long tradition in CHP market • Government stopped the support for new RES plants, and as a result of this the total electricity generation decreased the last 5 years. 	
Denmark	Lack of support schemes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 50.8% • Denmark has the most developed CHP system among all the EU member states • Total share of CHPs fuelled by RES of more than 40% 	
Estonia	Reverse auctions (public tenders)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 65.1% • Very small share of CHPs in total electricity generation (about 7%) • Support schemes focus on CHP development, fuelled by RES 	
Finland	State grant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 62.4% • One of the top countries in CHP industry 	
France	Lack of support schemes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 27.8% • Not very active in CHP market • Support schemes are not familiarized to small-scale plants 	
Germany	Premium tariff, loan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 23.4% • Ranked in the 1st place in CHP electricity generation with a stable 	

EU Member State	Type of support	Comments	Country rating
		<p>growth the last 10 years</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful support schemes 	
Greece	Feed-in-tariff, subsidies, tax regulation mechanism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 0.6% • Long tradition • Establishment of a number of support schemes in CHP • One of the lowest share of CHP electricity generation among the EU countries 	
Hungary	Feed-in-tariff, Feed-in-premium, subsidies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 14% • Government promotes support schemes for micro- and bio-CHP, with a capacity up to 1 MW. 	
Ireland	Feed-in-tariff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 3.3% • Government made several attempts to support the CHP development, until today with no success. 	
Italy	Premium tariff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 15.8% • Italy is in 2nd place in CHP electricity generation (behind Germany) with around 40 TWh. 	
Latvia	Lack of support schemes (still pending)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 44.1% • One of the top EU countries with a share of around 50% in electricity generation • Government suspended subsidies • New support mechanism is still pending 	
Lithuania	Feed-in-tariff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 49.7% • Goal of the government is to increase electricity generation from CHP plants using RES 	
Luxembourg	Feed-in-tariff, investment grant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 38.6% • From 2005 until today, the total electricity generation is grown more than half • Implementation of support schemes 	
Malta	Lack of support schemes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 2.7% • Government of Malta was made several attempts to support the CHP market, in the form of green tariffs but until today with no success 	
Netherlands	Feed-in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 8.6% 	

EU Member State	Type of support	Comments	Country rating
	premium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large CHP electricity generation, mainly located in industry • Stagnation during the last 10 years 	
Poland	Tenders (bidding process), tax exemption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 9.5% • Share of CHP in total electricity generation is stagnated during the last 10 years • One of the largest share among the EU member states 	
Portugal	Feed-in-tariff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 46.3% • Portugal's CHP development is stagnated the last 10 years in a share in electricity generation of around 10% and more than 6 TWh 	
Romania	Green certificates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 5.6% • Establishment of a number of support schemes in CHP, from 2011 until 2016 • Slight decrease in CHP electricity generation during this period 	
Slovakia	Feed-in-tariff, tax exemption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 14.1% • A number of support schemes • Decrease in CHP electricity generation (from 25% in 2011 to 11% in 2016) 	
Slovenia	Loan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 21.7% • From 2005 to 2016, there is a stable growth in CHP electricity generation in around 7% 	
Spain	Premium tariff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 8.9% • CHP electricity generation is growing the last 15 years, despite the economic crisis and no governmental aim. • Share of CHP fuelled by RES is in a very small rate 	
Sweden	Quota system (energy certificates)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RES CHP share: 60% • Renewables is the most common fuel for CHP (around 60%) • Slight decrease in total electricity generation from 2010. 	

Table 5-3: Summary of support schemes for each Member state and a colour code grading

5.5 Electricity data in EU27

This section refers to parameters L5, M1, M2, M6.

5.5.1 Electricity prices for household sector in EU-27

The electricity produced by CHP plants in European Union is sold at various prices depending on the location of the site. These differences impact directly the revenues generated by the plant, thus its business plan. CHP owners have to find the optimum between fuel prices (gas, coal, bioenergy, etc.) and electricity prices.

Table below shows the evolution of the household electricity prices during the 2008-2017 decade in the EU-27 area. Electricity prices are depending on many market factors, like the national energy mix, import diversification, network costs, potential CO2 taxes, weather conditions and its impact on renewables generation, and the level of taxes.

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Austria	0.18	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Belgium	0.20	0.19	0.20	0.21	0.23	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.25	0.29
Bulgaria	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.10
Croatia	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.11	0.12	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.12
Cyprus	0.18	0.16	0.19	0.21	0.28	0.28	0.23	0.20	0.15	0.19
Czechia	0.14	0.15	0.15	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14
Denmark	0.26	0.27	0.27	0.29	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.31	0.31	0.30
Estonia	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.12
Finland	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.15	0.16
France	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.17
Germany	0.21	0.23	0.24	0.25	0.26	0.29	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Greece	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.16	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.19
Hungary	0.15	0.15	0.17	0.17	0.15	0.14	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.11
Ireland	0.18	0.20	0.18	0.19	0.22	0.23	0.24	0.24	0.23	0.23
Italy	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.23	0.24	0.25	0.23	0.21
Latvia	0.08	0.11	0.10	0.12	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.16	0.16	0.16
Lithuania	0.09	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.11
Luxembourg	0.16	0.19	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.16
Malta	0.10	0.17	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.13
Netherlands	0.18	0.20	0.18	0.18	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.20	0.16	0.16
Poland	0.13	0.11	0.13	0.15	0.14	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.14
Portugal	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.17	0.20	0.21	0.22	0.23	0.24	0.23
Romania	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.12
Slovakia	0.14	0.15	0.15	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.15	0.15	0.14	0.14
Slovenia	0.11	0.13	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16
Spain	0.14	0.16	0.17	0.20	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.23	0.22	0.23

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Sweden	0.17	0.16	0.18	0.21	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.19	0.19	0.19

Table 5-4: Electricity prices in household sector in EU-27 (in €/kWh)⁵⁷

In 2017, Denmark, Germany and Belgium present the highest tariff among the other countries, with an electricity price for households around 0.30 €/kWh, while Hungary, Lithuania and Bulgaria have the lowest prices around 0.10 €/kWh.

Figure 5.1: Electricity prices in household sector in EU in 2017 (in €/kWh)

During the 2008-2017 decade, Latvia, Greece and Spain known a significant increase of electricity prices, respectively 88%, 85% and 68%. In the meantime, three countries succeeded to decrease their electricity prices: Luxembourg (-2%), Netherlands (-12%) and Hungary (-27%).

When considering the five regions identified in the EU area, Northern countries have the most expensive electricity (0.23 €/kWh), while Eastern countries beneficiate of the lowest prices (0.14 €/kWh). The average price for the five regions is 0.18 €/kWh, Eastern and South-East regions are dragging the average price downwards.

EU region	2017
Northern	0.23
North-Western	0.21
South-West	0.19
South-East	0.15
Eastern	0.14

Table 5-5: Electricity prices in household sector per EU region in 2017 (in €/kWh)

⁵⁷ Source: EUROSTAT statistics, prices include taxes, levies and VAT

5.5.2 Electricity prices for industrial sector in EU-27

Table below shows the evolution of the industrial electricity prices during the 2008-2017 decade in the EU-27 area. These tariffs exclude the different taxes, on which industries are not submitted.

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Austria	0,09	0,10	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,08	0,07	0,07	0,06
Belgium	0,10	0,10	0,09	0,10	0,10	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,08
Bulgaria	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,07	0,08	0,07	0,07	0,10	0,08
Croatia	0,07	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,08
Cyprus	0,14	0,12	0,15	0,16	0,22	0,20	0,17	0,13	0,10	0,13
Czechia	0,11	0,11	0,10	0,11	0,10	0,10	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,07
Denmark	0,07	0,06	0,07	0,08	0,06	0,07	0,07	0,06	0,06	0,06
Estonia	0,05	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,06	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,07
Finland	0,06	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,06	0,06	0,06
France	0,06	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,07
Germany	0,09	0,10	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08
Greece	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,10	0,10	0,11	0,10	0,09	0,09
Hungary	0,11	0,12	0,10	0,10	0,09	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,06
Ireland	0,13	0,12	0,11	0,11	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,12	0,11
Italy	n/a	n/a	n/a	0,11	0,12	0,11	0,11	0,09	0,08	0,08
Latvia	0,07	0,09	0,09	0,10	0,11	0,10	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09
Lithuania	0,08	0,09	0,10	0,10	0,11	0,10	0,10	0,08	0,08	0,07
Luxembourg	0,09	0,11	0,10	0,10	0,10	0,09	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,07
Malta	0,12	0,15	0,17	0,18	0,18	0,18	0,18	0,16	0,14	0,13
Netherlands	0,09	0,10	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,07	0,06
Poland	0,08	0,09	0,09	0,10	0,09	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,07
Portugal	0,08	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,11	0,10	0,10	0,10	0,09	0,08
Romania	0,09	0,08	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,09	0,08	0,07	0,06	0,06
Slovakia	0,12	0,14	0,12	0,12	0,13	0,12	0,11	0,11	0,10	0,07
Slovenia	0,09	0,10	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,07	0,06
Spain	0,09	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,11	0,11	0,10
Sweden	0,07	0,07	0,08	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,06	0,06	0,06

Table 5-6: Electricity prices in industrial sector in EU-27⁵⁸

In industrial sector, prices are not as dispatched as in the household sector, and more than half of the EU-27 prices didn't exceed 0.07 €/kWh, among them countries from the 5 EU regions. Highest prices are in Cyprus and Malta, with 0.13 €/kWh.

Figure 5.2: Electricity prices in industrial sector in EU in 2017

During the 2008-2017-decade, price variations were not excessive due to the general low value of the prices in the regions. 17 countries faced a decrease of their prices, among them Hungary (-43%), Czechia and Slovakia (-38%), while other countries saw an increase of their prices, like in Bulgaria (+35%), Latvia (+38%) and Estonia (+40%).

Among the five regions identified in the EU area, South-East and South-West countries have the most expensive electricity (0.09 €/kWh), while Northern countries benefit of the lowest prices (0.06 €/kWh). The average price for the five regions is 0.08 €/kWh, with low standard deviation from the 5 regions.

EU region	2017
South-East	0,09
South-West	0,09
North-Western	0,08
Eastern	0,07
Northern	0,06

Table 5-7: Electricity prices in industrial sector per EU region in 2017

⁵⁸ EUROSTAT statistics, refundable taxes and levies and VAT not included

5.5.3 Electricity production in EU-27

In 2017, CHP represented 18% of electricity production in EU-27 area with around 500 TWh produced, over a total production of 2,700 TWh.

Figure 5.3: Electricity production from main producers by type of plants in 2017 (in GWh)

The share of CHP in electricity production is very different depending on the EU region. As we can see in the table below, electricity production in Eastern countries mainly comes from CHP (62%), while CHP only represent 10% of the electricity production in South-West countries.

in GWh	Electricity plant	CHP
Eastern	129 583	213 811
South-East	141 084	19 353
North-Western	167 752	30 260
Northern	768 554	135 438
South-West	1 006 730	103 071

Table 5-8: Electricity production in 2017 (GWh)⁵⁹

Over the last 2008-2017-decade, electricity production slightly decreased (-2%), mainly due to the economic downturn following the financial crisis of 2008.

There are strong disparities between all the countries considered. For instance, Netherlands, Denmark and Lithuania invested much more in electricity plant than CHP (see data in table below), as electricity production from electricity plants has more than doubled, while electricity production from CHP decreased. In the same period, Croatia, and Czechia faced a huge increase of their electricity production from CHP while their electricity plant saw their production decreasing.

⁵⁹ Source: EUROSTAT statistics: ‘main activity producers’ perimeter’, autoproducers not included in the analysis

	Electricity plant - variation 2008-2017	CHP - Variation 2008-2017
Austria	7%	34%
Belgium	-7%	-21%
Bulgaria	7%	-38%
Croatia	-21%	62%
Cyprus	-2%	n/a
Czechia	-31%	186%
Denmark	111%	-51%
Estonia	18%	75%
Finland	-7%	-24%
France	-2%	-9%
Germany	-3%	31%
Greece	-15%	-11%
Hungary	15%	-45%
Ireland	1%	n/a
Italy	-14%	6%
Latvia	43%	38%
Lithuania	134%	-94%
Luxembourg	-43%	-31%
Malta	-36%	n/a
Netherlands	56%	-45%
Poland	50%	2%
Portugal	28%	-33%
Romania	2%	-41%
Slovakia	10%	-13%
Slovenia	-5%	5%
Spain	-13%	n/a
Sweden	10%	12%

Figure 5.4: Variation of electricity production between 2008 and 2017⁶⁰

5.5.4 Compliance to the CO2 targets

In 2015, the first universal agreement on limitation of global warming was signed during the COP21 in Paris by representatives of 196 state parties. Commitments took by countries ambitioned to keep the increase in global average temperature to well below 2 °C above pre-industrial levels, and to limit the increase to 1.5°C, through the implementation of concrete measures in their own regulations regarding their industries, energy and building sectors, transport, etc.

4 years later, even though large CO2 emissions countries left the Agreement or don't respect their commitments (for instance United States, Brazil...), Paris Agreement remains the reference and is a great indicator to assess countries capacity to "turn green" their energy mix.

In European Union, restrictive measures adapted to the specificity of each country and directives have been firstly decided at EU scale (such as Clean Energy Package), and countries engaged to respect the targets and set up relevant action plans though the law. But today, specific observations on EU countries shows that most countries that advocate for more ambitious policies for the future are

⁶⁰ Source : DOWEL analysis

currently lagging behind in achieving targets for 2020 and reducing carbon emissions.

A smart way to rank EU-27 countries is to assess the role that these Member States play in setting ambitious climate and energy targets and policies, but also what progress they are making in reducing carbon emissions and promoting renewable energy and energy efficiency of the buildings. We obtain the following rank:

Figure 5.5: Ranking of EU countries in relation to fighting climate change⁶¹

As we can see, Sweden Portugal, France, the Netherlands and Luxembourg are well ranked, they led the debates on the EU’s future energy targets and started to implement serious improvements in their domestic policies.

Other countries such as Belgium, Denmark, and Germany remained silent or vague on the need to accelerate the zero-carbon transition in the EU, while the middle-ranked countries didn’t really act domestically or at the EU level to push green solutions in various targeted sectors.

Finally, most Central and Eastern European countries are still unambitious in terms of climate policies (even if Slovenia and Czech Republic have a more progressive voices in this region), mainly because they have received very low climate and energy targets at EU level. This is due to their low average income, but also, they often have low energy consumption and greenhouse gas emission numbers due to their economic situation. They are drastically missing ambition.

5.5.5 Presence of insular territories in EU27 countries

EU countries beneficiate of a various geographical context, and some of them are more adapted to increase their renewable energy share with biomass solutions.

⁶¹ Source: “Off Target”, Climate Action Network Europe (methodology described in the report)

Most of the island territories in EU countries are currently supplied by coal or fuel plants, while some of them could switch to a greener solution. It would be highly consistent to implement biomass plants, especially when it provides the same level of profitability and wood resources can be transported with few CO₂ emissions.

Greece comes first due to its numerous islands in Aegean, Ionian and Mediterranean seas. France has also a great potential with Corsica, but also its overseas departments and territories in Atlantic and Pacific Oceans. Large islands belong to Italy and Spain, such as Balearics, Sardinia and Sicilia. Nordic countries also have small islands, while the whole Irish, Maltese and Cypriot territories can be considered as an island.

Pyrolysis production should be considered on mainland and transport the high energy/ bulk density pyrolysis oil to the islands. For big islands, local pyrolysis oil production could be considered.

5.6 Results of the analysis of the EU27 countries

Several EU countries are active or have a long tradition in CHP installations. In this section, and through the analysis of specific characteristics of EU countries and with reference to a number of identified criteria, the identification of the most “promising” countries for further analysis with reference to the SmartCHP project has been made. Apart from the availability of biomass resource, the following criteria have been considered:

- Support schemes, through the analysis of the existing legislative framework and policies
- Electricity prices for the tertiary/commercial and household sectors for the period 2008-2017
- Electricity prices for the industrial sector for the period 2008-2017
- Share of CHP in the country’s overall electricity production
- Compliance with the CO₂ targets
- Geographical characteristics of the countries, e.g. existence of insular territories.

With reference to the above parameters, it is synthesized the conclusions from the above chapters and provides a selection of the most promising countries based on the analysed criteria and the expert’s views.

With reference to the above parameters, project participants have identified 10 (ten) countries which seem to be more favorable for the development of small-scale CHP systems. These countries, which are presented also in the table below, belong to all EU regions, display availability of the three lignocellulosic feedstock categories (agricultural residues, forest residues and organic waste residues), reasonable feasibility for bio-oil imports, but also have adopted ambitious but realistic CO₂ reduction targets.

- Central Europe : Austria, Croatia, Germany
- Northern Europe: Estonia (export scenario), Finland, Sweden
- Eastern Europe: Poland, Romania
- Western Europe: The Netherlands (import scenario)
- Southern Europe: Greece

No.	Country	Region	Rationale for their selection
1	Austria	Central Europe	Feedstock availability
2	Croatia	Central Europe	Unexploited land potential
3	Estonia	Northern Europe	Proximity to Finland
4	Finland	Northern Europe	Availability of woody biomass
5	Germany	Central Europe	Good public support & high electricity prices
6	Poland	Eastern Europe	Lack of reaching CO2 targets
7	Romania	Eastern Europe	Feedstock availability projection potential
8	Greece	Southern Europe	Olive kernel production
9	Sweden	Northern Europe	Island potential
10	Netherlands	Western Europe	Import scenario

Table 5-9: Top 10 selected countries (Experts view)

5.7 Selection of 5 focus countries

Following the narrow down process from EU 27 to 10 countries (presented above), and an analysis of each country, we selected 5 focus countries, which can become potential host for SmartCHP pilot installations. The selection process ensured a diversity of situations, first geographically according to macro-areas (one focus country per region), then by the feedstock nature.

- Northern Europe: Sweden has biomass availability, mainly in softwood and, in addition, can export produced oil to other countries (e.g. Netherlands)
- Central Europe: In Croatia, due to the recent war, there are large unexploited pieces of land, which can be used for dedicated biomass crops (Short Rotation Coppice, C4 crops, Miscanthus).
- Western Europe: Netherlands is considered as an oil importer from Sweden
- Eastern Europe: This region has high biomass potential and high land availability. Bulgaria has high potential in agriculture residues. Poland has not met its CO₂ targets, however, it needs to further invest in RES. Romania has sufficient agriculture waste potential, forest and a good support mechanism.

- Southern Europe: Spain is a leading producer of olive kernel. Greece is a good option too, due to large its olive kernel production potential and its insular territories. In this case the biomass can be converted to oil in the mainland and be “exported” to the islands.

After the above analysis, we concluded in the following 5 focus countries.

Focus country	Macro-region	Biomass feedstock
Croatia	Central Europe	Miscanthus
Greece	Southern Europe	Olive kernel
Netherlands	Western Europe	Pyrolysis oil import scenario from Sweden
Romania	Eastern Europe	Corn stover
Sweden	Northern Europe	Softwood forestry residues

Table 5-10: Selection of 5 focus countries (Experts view)

Highlights chapter 5:

- Ten priority areas corresponding to ten countries with a high potential have been selected according to a funnel type approach including successive criteria related to the local market barriers
- Each of them implies a specific scenario for biomass supply chain to the FPBO (e.g. local collection for import)
- They constitute the portfolio basis for the selection of the five focus countries, object of next section of the report
- Selected focus countries: Croatia, Greece, Netherlands, Romania and Sweden, each with a specific type of biomass to feed the pyrolysis process

6. Potential of SmartCHP in the 5 focus countries

6.1 Market segmentation for SmartCHP

6.1.1 From regional to customer segmentation

As already introduced, cogeneration market (and furthermore SmartCHP market due to the supply chain) is fragmented and heterogeneous. Market segmentation is a marketing technique to address such heterogeneity by dividing the market domain into smaller segments with common and homogeneous characteristics.

Previous chapter shown the first geographic segmentation, based on the priority areas. This chapter will concentrate on the customer segmentation, aiming to define the size and qualities of potential “customers” of i.e. a product or service. “Customers” are divided on the basis of certain criteria, e.g. a set of characteristics, geographical distribution, etc.

In particular, and in the context of this study, market segmentation and consequently quantification aims to assess the potential of the SmartCHP technology proposition.

6.1.2 A systematic scan of segments per sector of activity

Potential SmartCHP users are considered to be the same as the users of traditional CHP which could be found in various activities including but not limited to hospitals, hotels, academic and large educational facilities, the agro-food sector, etc.

A traditional approach of segmentation at two levels: “**sectors**” > “**customer segments**” is adopted starting with a systematic review of all sectors and for each sector the selection of the most promising segments.

As a result, it appears that SmartCHP technology can be applied to different end users, covering different sectors. Indicatively,

- **Tertiary sector**, including hotels, hospitals, office buildings, retail (e.g. shopping malls), educational buildings, (primary and secondary schools, high schools and universities, research laboratories, professional training activities and others), etc.
- **Industrial sector**, including food and beverage, pulp and paper, chemical, refining, ferrous and nonferrous metals, nonmetallic minerals, pharmaceuticals, etc.
- **Residential sector**, including small-scale District Heating / Cooling, large residential complexes, social housing, etc.
- **Agriculture sector**, including greenhouses.

The energy demand of facilities (thermal and/or electricity) that is consistent within the range of the SmartCHP power output (i.e. 0.1-1 MW) has been considered as the starting point for the quantification of the potential market for SmartCHP.

Quantification of the potential for CHP in the range of the SmartCHP technology offering has been considered for the Hotel sector, the Hospital sector, the Office buildings (both public and private), the Education buildings, the Retail sector, as well as the Greenhouses (agriculture sector).

The industrial sector has not at this point been considered. For the majority of the industrial sector the energy requirements fall much beyond the SmartCHP capacity range. Nevertheless, there are industrial sectors (e.g. agrofood business, etc), which would and could be considered for potential SmartCHP applications around Europe. Niche applications in industry cannot be *a priori* excluded. However for the assessment, priority was given to the most attractive segments, namely segments that are already acquainted to cogeneration⁶².

6.1.3 Estimating a market potential per segment

Four steps have been considered to assess the CHP / SmartCHP potential for each market segment.

- **Step 1:** Collection of information from official sources of data (e.g. Eurostat, EU Buildings Database, EU funded projects, etc.) on the overall capacity of each segment, e.g. number of bedrooms and bedplaces for the hotel sector, the number of available beds in health facilities, the number of office buildings or the number of educational buildings, or attributes such as information on the total floor area, etc.
- **Step 2:** Collection of relevant information published in the context of research projects or audit reports (energy or sectorial reports) on the energy consumption (electricity / thermal) per relevant unit, e.g. per bed, per square meter or other.
- **Step 3:** Potential CHP host facilities have been split according to their size and consequently according to their energy requirements.
- **Step 4:** The potential market for CHP/SmartCHP technology (as a range) has been evaluated for each market segment.

6.1.4 Presentation of results

Next sections display a synthetic information on the market potential for SmartCHP estimated on a combination of:

- each market segment considered of interest, and
- the 5 focus countries for SmartCHP.

Concluding *Table 6-1* details the key characteristics of such combination while a full analysis for each market segment is given in Annex 1.

6.2 Customer segment overview for the tertiary and agriculture sectors

Six customer segments appear promising as traditional market target for cogeneration.

⁶² See chapter 7 on competition for the distinction between these segments, called incremental segments and the end users having no track record on cogeneration, called disruptive, since requiring much more efforts to reach that segment.

Each segment is characterized by:

- ad hoc sizing indexes such as surface floor, number of beds or rooms in line with their activity: synthetic information is reported below
- unit energy consumption per unit (typically in kWh/sqm): see *Table 6-1*
- both defining energy needs per segment, which in turn could lead to an estimation of SmartCHP units (see section 6.4).

Hotels At EU level, there are more than 32 million bed places (2018), including hotels and similar accommodation, holiday and other short-stay apartments and camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. As regards hotels and similar accommodation, correspond to more than 14 million bed places and around 6,7 million bedrooms⁶³. Among this segment, main target for SmartCHP should be hotels with more than 25 rooms, corresponding to the SmartCHP foreseen electrical capacity.

Hospitals At EU level, the number of hospital beds in 2018 was around 2,5 million, including curative care beds, rehabilitative care beds, long term care beds and other beds. Among this segment, main target for SmartCHP should be hospitals with more than 200 beds.

Office Buildings Approximately 2,050 million sqm of office space is available in Europe. Due to the ever-changing nature and equipment of office space, e.g. new means of communication, automation of the equipment, higher comfort levels, etc. energy intensity of office buildings is higher compared to other types of buildings. Main target for SmartCHP should be Office Buildings above 1000 m² of surface floor.

⁶³ [Eurostat capacity of tourist accommodation establishments](#)

Educational buildings

Approximately 1 million educational buildings exist across EU-27, of which 100.000 are in the five focus countries. The educational building sector includes primary and secondary schools, high schools and universities, research laboratories, professional training activities and others and had a share of around 20% of non-residential sector in 2011⁶⁴. Large educational buildings are targeted (around and more than 1000 m²)

Retail

Retail sector is covering all types of stores that are selling final products, generally to individual customers. A large scope of stores is covered by the retail sector, from small stores located in traditional town centre shopping district to larger stores such as hypermarkets. For SmartCHP our main targets are malls, supermarket and retail up to 10,000 m²

Greenhouses

Greenhouses is included in the agriculture sector and consist of the vegetables, flowers and permanent crops under plastic or glass covered area. The number of greenhouses in EU27 in 2013 was above 160 thousand⁶⁵. SmartCHP should target greenhouses sized of about 8,000 m² and above.

6.3 Customer segment overview for the residential sector

Residential sector covers the highest total floor area, with a percentage around 75%. Out of this percentage, approximately 40% belongs to apartment blocks (including households consist of several units and social housing units) and the remaining to single family houses, including detached, semi-detached and terraced houses). A primary target shall be apartment buildings or group of buildings as detailed in section 6.3.3.

6.3.1 Building stock structure

Building stock structure matters. It is important to note that the share of single family and apartments buildings varies significantly from country to country. Among the EU 27 countries and as regards the apartment buildings, Latvia has the highest share (approx. 75%), following by Estonia (70%) and Spain (65%) while Ireland (around 10%), Greece (more than 10%) and Norway (15%) have the smallest ones.

6.3.2 Energy use

Regarding the energy in residential buildings is used mainly for space heating (range from 60 to 80%), followed by water heating (more than 10%) and electrical appliances (10%).

⁶⁴ Economidou et al, (2011), Europe's buildings under the microscope. A country-by-country review of the energy performance of buildings

⁶⁵ <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do>

6.3.3 Subsegments of interest for SmartCHP

Based on the above elements, single family houses (SFH) are out of the target for SmartCHP systems in the range of 0.1 to 1MW_e (they could however be interested in micro cogeneration⁶⁶). When focusing on multi-family houses (MFH), other segmentation criteria emerge such as ownership (landlord or tenant), social housing, or on the technical standpoint : age of the building or existence of a central heating systems or individual heating systems. The high diversity of situations makes an assessment complex. However, two subsegments appear as promising to fit to the sizing specifications of a SmartCHP system:

Social Housing

- **Social housing:** this segment is clearly an 'incremental' segment (meaning it has already experience of cogeneration systems) and constitutes thus a commercial target for SmartCHP future commercial deployment.

Emerging Energy Communities

- **Energy communities:** Citizen Energy Communities or Renewable Energy concepts. Aggregation of residential developments and domestic housing enables reaching the range of capacity for a SmartCHP system⁶⁷. A major trend for putting the customer in the centre and in control of its energy act is under way, which might open new opportunities for SmartCHP.

⁶⁶ See for example: Residential cogeneration systems: review of the current technology. H..I.OnovwionaaV.I.Ugursalb [link](#) in Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 2006.

⁶⁷ <https://www.clarke-energy.com/applications/residential-and-community/>

Market segment	EU27	Croatia	Greece	The Netherlands	Romania	Sweden
Hotels*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >14 million bed places ~6,7 million bedrooms Annual average energy consumption: 200 to 400 kWh/m² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~1,100 establishments, 81,000 bedrooms and 169,000 bed places ~30% from 25 to 100 bedrooms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~9,900 establishments, 421,000 bedrooms and 822,000 bed places ~40% from 25 to 100 bedrooms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~3,800 establishments, 132,000 bedrooms and 286,000 bed places ~35% from 25 to 100 bedrooms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~2,900 establishments, 116,000 bedrooms and 223,000 bed places ~35% from 25 to 100 bedrooms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~2,100 establishments, 125,500 bedrooms and 252,000 bed places ~45% from 25 to 100 bedrooms
Hospitals*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~2,5 million total available beds Total average energy consumption: ~11,500 kWh/bed/year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~23,000 total available beds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~45,000 total available beds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~54,500 total available beds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~135,500 total available beds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~22,000 total available beds
Office buildings (both public and private)**	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total floor area: ~ 2,000 million m² Average total energy consumption: ~250 kWh/m²/year ~75% of buildings are consuming less than 390 kWh/m² ~30% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~8,000 million m² total floor area ~20% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~16,000 million m² total floor area ~20% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~82,500 million m² total floor area ~15% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~5,500 million m² total floor area ~10% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~60,000 million m² total floor area ~30% share in non-residential sector
Educational buildings***	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~1 million ~15% share in non-residential sector Average energy consumption: 20 – 200 kWh/m² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of educational buildings: ~11,500 ~15% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of educational buildings: ~7,000 ~15% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of educational buildings: ~14,500 ~10% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of educational buildings: ~45,000 ~30% share in non-residential sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of educational buildings: ~16,000 ~25% share in non-residential sector
Retail sector****	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of retail stores ~ 2.7 million Total floor area of shopping centres: ~170,000 thousand m² Energy consumption: ~300 TWh Number of employees ~18.5 million 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of retail stores: ~19,000 Total floor area of shopping centres: ~1,500 sqm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of retail stores: ~160,000 Total floor area of shopping centres: ~900 sqm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of retail stores: ~235,000 Total floor area of shopping centres: ~6,500 sqm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of retail stores: ~104,000 Total floor area of shopping centres: ~3,000 sqm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of retail stores: ~53,000 Total floor area of shopping centres: ~5,500 sqm

Leisure sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Typical energy consumption for a swimming pool centre (based on UK source): 237 kWh/m² elec and 1336 kWh/ m² heat ○ Typical energy consumption for a fitness centre: 194 kWh/m² elec and 449 kWh/m² heat ○ Typical energy consumption for a leisure pool centre: 258kWh/m² elec and 1321 kWh/m² heat 					
Greenhouses**	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of greenhouses: ~165 thousand ○ Total surface area: >1,3 billion m² ○ Energy consumption per m²: 50 to 400 W/m² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of greenhouses: ~3,000 ○ Total surface area: ~5 million m² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of greenhouses: ~9,000 ○ Total surface area: ~47 million m² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of greenhouses: ~4,000 ○ Total surface area: ~93 million m² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of greenhouses: ~19,500 ○ Total surface area: ~33 million m² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of greenhouses: ~1000 ○ Total surface area: ~2,5 million m²

Table 6-1: Key features of the selected segments in the 5 focus countries: sizing and unit energy use

* 2018

** 2013

*** 2016

****2017

6.4 Quantification of SmartCHP potential

This section aims to conclude the quantification process by providing a maximum amount of equivalent SmartCHP units for the five focus countries

It should be noted that the displayed ranges in the below double entry table corresponds to a calculated potential for SmartCHP units. For the calculation of the respective CHP and SmartCHP potential, several data were collected and analyzed, based on external sources and internal assumptions (expert views), mainly in two different levels:

- The first level of data refers to the **volume** of each segment for the five focus countries in a unit corresponding to each segment's unit of measure (i.e. number of bedrooms and bedplaces for hotels, number of available beds in health facilities, total floor area, etc.).
- The second level refers to the **specific energy consumption** per unit (either per m² or per bed or other, according to the corresponding unit).

Assumptions were necessary for several purposes:

- Assumption 1: All buildings/facilities with energy needs out of the range offered by a SmartCHP system⁶⁸ are removed from analysis. This process is **specific to each segment** (see annex 1).
- Assumption 2: The fraction of the energy that could be served by a cogeneration system is estimated. The assumption made is that this fraction is **50%**. This level results from a number of constraints, e.g. seasonality in the hotel and educational sector, space availability in the office buildings sector, etc.
- Assumption 3: Target fraction for SmartCHP out of the total cogeneration potential is estimated at **10%**.

The resulting fraction of SmartCHP achievable market combining assumption 2 (50%) and assumption 3 (10%) appears to be as quite conservative but reasonable.

Based on the above information, and considering the volume and energy consumption for each segment for each of the five focus countries, as well as the energy produced by a SmartCHP system with capacity in the range between 0.1 and 1 MW_e, it was possible to estimate the number of systems for each focus country and for each market segment. It must be noted that the ranges displayed refer to the minimum and maximum size of the SmartCHP unit, i.e. the lower number refers to the 1 MW_e unit, whereas the higher number refers to the 100 kW_e unit.

A full analysis for the calculation of SmartCHP market potential for each market segment is given in Annex 1.

The resulting market potential is directly dependant on the above assumptions (1, 2 and 3). Modifying such input parameters will lead to modification of the table below. However it is believed that it constitutes a sound basis to get a first quantified perspective of the market capacity of SmartCHP for the focus countries

⁶⁸ 0.1-1 MWe for operations during 5000 hours over a year, meaning 0.5 GWh- 5GWh electricity and an equivalent amount of heat, assuming a P:H ratio of 1

and provides interesting insights for the sizing and geographical positioning of the FPBO plants.

Market segment	Croatia	Greece	The Netherlands	Romania	Sweden
Hotels (more than 100 rooms)	5 - 50	25 - 250	10 - 120	5 - 80	10 - 70
Hospitals (more than 200 beds)	2 - 3	4 - 5	5 - 6	10 - 15	2 - 3
Office Buildings (more than 1000 m ²)	50 - 100	25 - 150	25 - 400	25 - 300	25 - 800
Educational Buildings (more than 1000 m ²)	20 - 100	25 - 50	50 - 100	Up to 400	50 - 100
Retail sector	5-50	3-30	25-240	12-120	20-200
Greenhouses (more than 8000 m ²)	25 - 50	100 - 250	More than 100	200 - 500	10 - 15
Estimation of SmartCHP units	100 - 350	180 - 735	200 - 1000	350 - 1400	120 - 1200
Estimated potential of SmartCHP units in the 5 selected countries					950 - 4700

Table 6-2: Estimation of the potential of SmartCHP units

A draft estimation of the required quantity of FPBO (in tonnes) for the estimated potential SmartCHP units in the five selected countries is calculated. Based on the here above estimated number of the SmartCHP units and assuming a capacity factor of 60% and an overall efficiency of 80%, the total needed fuel in MWh is calculated.

Following that, converting⁶⁹ the calorific value of FPBO from GJ to MWh, with a full exploitation of energy demand, the annual FPBO quantity for a SmartCHP unit of 100 kW_e is estimated at around 150 tonnes per year and for 1 MW_e around 1,500.

⁶⁹ Calorific value of 16 GJ/ton and a Conversion factor (GJ-2-MWh) 0.2777

Highlights chapter 6:

- A quantification of the maximum number of SmartCHP systems for each of the priority area is carried out based publicly available information: first, on the collection of available data on volume (number of building / sites) in each focus country, second, on the collection of energy needs for each class of customer
- The data collection process was complemented by expert views from cogeneration industry and the market side
- This process provides useful insights for the geographical positioning of the FPBO plants and their potential.

7. Competition analysis

SmartCHP is an innovative energy system that offers different types of value: directly energy related (heat and electricity provision), and indirectly energy related (use of a liquid biofuel, flexible H:P ratio ⁷⁰ providing adaptability, clean flue gas). This value is produced by the combination of:

- An innovative cogeneration system;
- Upstream: the FPBO unit for the supply side for the non-fossil fuel production;
- Downstream: by targeted customers 'buying' this value whatever the contractual arrangement (energy services, selling of a turn-key system with or without operation and maintenance, etc.)

Competition analysis shall therefore include two levels.

First, technology wise. The SmartCHP unit (fed by a FPBO plant) shall prove its competitive advantage compared to conventional cogeneration technologies for each targeted customer. Conventional technologies are mature, so potentially widespread, less expensive, etc. *Competition battlefield is mainly on the calories produced in situ.*

Second, system wise. As an energy system, SmartCHP has to be competitive with other heat and electricity solutions (not combined) for the same targeted customers with all constraints of the supply side. *Competition battlefield goes beyond to the calories produced in situ but includes the raw material – the feedstock- with other economic agents that could also use the very same resources and impacting its availability or scarcity.* Indeed, other uses of biomass feedstock constitute indirect competition through the supply chain.

In the following sections, we first detail the comparison to conventional CHP technologies, then the non-cogeneration based heat and power solutions. The level of effort to be deployed to 'sell' a SmartCHP system depends on the current energy solutions already deployed in a particular market segment.

One could distinguish market segments with already CHP solution from market segments that have not yet experienced any CHP facility. We could refer to them by the respective qualifications 'incremental' or 'disruptive'⁷¹.

CHP penetration in the market segment	Current energy solution in the segment	Conventional Combined Heat and Power technologies	"SmartCHP"
Market segments presenting	CHP or distinct heat and	Incremental approach to increase the	Effort to convince about the value of

⁷⁰ Heat to Power ratio

⁷¹ 'incremental' meaning that in this market segment CHP is already used, and could be require a commercial effort to increase the penetration of conventional or innovative CHP; disruptive meaning that there is no or marginal penetration of CHP in that segment

already solution	CHP	electricity solution	penetration rate of CHP	SmartCHP in the continuity of conventional CHP
Market segments with underexploited CHP		Use of distinct heat and electricity solution	Disruptive approach for initiating CHP in these segments	Highly disruptive: gap to bridge is larger

Table 7-1: Effort to deploy CHP and SmartCHP facilities per market segment

In conclusion, the level of effort to be distinctive for a SmartCHP solution against a competitive energy offer will depend on the current penetration level of conventional cogeneration in a given market segment. The graduation in the color code in the above Table characterizes this effort (from orange color: lower effort to the dark red color for the most disruptive) and help designing a future Go-To-Market strategy.

7.1 Competing cogeneration technologies

This section focuses on the direct competition of conventional cogeneration.

7.1.1 An overview on Cogeneration

Cogeneration – meaning the simultaneous production of electricity and heat - is a mature technology. Indeed, the principle of using a single fuel to generate both electric power and thermal energy is well known. The basic idea is based on the fact that electricity production releases a large amount of heat, which is usually dissipated in the environment. In response to thermal demand (heating, industrial process, etc.), it proposes to use the electrical generation cycle also as a thermal source.

Cogeneration techniques consist in recovering and making the most of this residual and available thermal energy. The electrical energy from cogeneration is either self-consumed or reinjected into the public electricity network according to regulatory, technical and economic conditions in the considered area. The **local dimension matters**, and more specifically the local characterization of heat generation which makes an analysis at EU-wide scale quite difficult (e.g. scarcity and inhomogeneity of data).

On the technology standpoint, different technologies are available for a CHP system. Most of them are mature and commercially available, while some are still at lower maturity degrees. A more detailed review of the technologies for the heat engine and the primary fuels is presented in next sections.

The diversity of technologies has to be combined with the **different types of fuels** that could be used as supply. The fuel can be a fossil fuel as coal, natural gas, liquefied petroleum gas or fuel oil. It could also be biomass as wood, biogas or waste.

Cogeneration using **biomass** enables to convert a renewable energy source into heat and power which leads to reaching CO₂ emissions reduction when compared with fossil fuels. Biomass is transformed in energy either through **biochemical** (oil extraction, alcoholic or methanic fermentation) **or a thermochemical process**

(direct combustion, pyrolysis, gasification). **Biomass fuelling options** includes various lignocellulosic sources from wood industry, forestry by-products, agricultural wastes or organic sources: Biogas is a popular renewable cogeneration fuel for small scale application (usually located on farms and landfill sites with a direct source of biogas feedstocks anaerobically digested), solid biofuels (wood, wood chips, wood pellets through direct combustion or through a gasification system⁷²), wood gas or biodiesel.

Literature on cogeneration distinguishes various ranges in terms of capacity that correlate quite well to the potential applications in industry, heat network or decentralized for the tertiary or residential sectors. Thermal energy is most often used for heating buildings and / or for the production of domestic hot water or for industrial processes.

- Cogeneration: 1MW_e – 250 MW_e for industry and District Heating and Cooling
- Small-scale or mini cogeneration: below 1 MW_e for large buildings in agriculture, industry, tertiary or residential sectors⁷³
- Micro-cogeneration: below 50 kW_e for individual or small multifamily houses.

7.1.2 Sources of primary fuels for Cogeneration

Sources of primary energy for CHP generation technologies are one of the differences between them and conventional heat power plant. The most commonly used and the most promising ones are shortly introduced below.

Waste to energy

Incineration, meaning the combustion of organic material such as waste with energy recovery, is common. A plant primarily is designed for incineration of municipal solid waste (MSW) and non-hazardous wastes from trade and industry⁷⁴. Usually waste delivered by trucks are incinerated without pre-processing, except bulky items that are shredded before being fed into the waste bunker.

The maximum amount of energy recoverable through MSW incineration depends primarily on the lower calorific value of the waste, and on the system applied for energy recovery. Efficiency increases when both electricity and steam/heat are produced, while the yield is lowest when only electricity is generated, and the surplus heat is flared.

Biomass

⁷² The wood -chips or pellets - are fed into the gasifier unit where the charred wood reacts with carbon dioxide and air/oxygen/steam to produce carbon monoxide and methane. The so-called producer gas is then filtered through the cleaning system and can then be burned at higher efficiencies than would have been possible by the direct combustion of the wood chips

⁷³ Non exhaustive list of applications include residential buildings, administrative buildings, education and university buildings, office buildings, food processing, brewing, distilling, timber processing, motor, sewage treatment works, horticulture, greenhouses, drying crops or wood, animal shelters, textiles. See market segmentation.

⁷⁴ Some types of hazardous wastes may, however, also be incinerated.

Derived from living, or recently living organisms, it often refers to plants or plant-based materials which are specifically called ligno-cellulosic biomass originating from agricultural residues, energy crops, forestry residues, urban wood waste/mill residues⁷⁵.

Usual applications of biomass materials range from burning wood and agricultural residues as a fuel for cogeneration of steam and electricity in industry. Biomass is also used for power generation in the electricity sector (e.g. biomass co-firing) and for space heating in residential and commercial buildings.

Non-energy uses of biomass materials exist in a large variety of products, creating an upstream competition on its availability. As an energy-source, either directly by combustion or indirectly after conversion in a biofuel, it presents, in the long run, the potential to become a much more significant source of energy in the global energy supply.

Coal and Natural gas

Coal and natural gas technologies for producing electrical energy are well known. They are also a source of primary energy for CHP, as the technological process is the same, the only difference being the overall efficiency, legitimating its use.

It should be noticed that for gas engine, CHP systems are measured based upon the efficiency of conversion of the fuel gas to useful outputs. For example for a gas fed internal combustion engine, first, the energy in the fuel gas input is converted into mechanical energy via the combustion of the gas in the engine's cylinders and their resulting action in the turning of the engine's shaft. This mechanical energy is then used to turn the engine's alternator and produce electricity. The useful heat from the generator is extracted from various areas: Engine jacket cooling water, Engine lubrication oil cooling, First stage air intake intercooler, Engine exhaust gases.

Opportunity fuels

An opportunity fuel is any type of fuel that is not widely used when compared to traditional fossil fuels as a CHP supply. Opportunity fuels primarily consist of biomass fuels⁷⁶, industrial waste products and fossil fuel derivatives. These fuels have the potential to be an economically viable source of power generation in various CHP applications.

7.1.3 A review of the main cogeneration technologies

A Combined Heat and Power system is composed of different blocks: the heat engine that constitutes the prime mover, the generator, the heat recovery system and finally the electrical interconnection. The CHP system is characterized by the technology for the heat generation. CHP overall systems can thus be grouped into six main families.

⁷⁵ At the core of SmartCHP supply it was thoroughly studied in Work Package 2 as well as all the conversion process to a liquid form.

⁷⁶ already mentioned hereabove since promising

Reciprocating
Internal
Combustion
Engines

Reciprocating engines: A reciprocating engine refers to an engine that uses one or several pistons in order to convert pressure into rotational motion. The reciprocating (up-and-down) motion of the pistons is used to translate this energy. Among the various types, the internal combustion engine is used in most motor vehicles, or external engines such as the Stirling or the steam engine.

They constitute the most widespread technology and make up over half of the CHP systems in place (but due to smaller system sizes they represent a low share in terms of total capacity). They are typically used in mobile and stationary applications (especially for producing hot water due to exhaust heat characteristics). They generally have a power range from 1 kW_e to a dozen of MW_e. As a result of a high maturity, experience curve and high production levels reciprocating engines present a relatively low investment cost. Higher efficiency and lower emissions improvements have been achieved resulting from technology improvements over the last decades.

In the same category, **Internal Combustion Engine (ICE)** can be described as an engine in which the combustion of a fuel occurs (usually fossil) with an oxidizer (usually air) in a combustion chamber part of the working fluid flow circuit.

The best IC engines, running on natural gas, offer efficiencies in the 38-44 % range. When using IC engines for CHP purposes the major advantage results from the operation mode of the ICE: the exhaust gas temperature will be in the 700°C region in a non-supercharged engine and about half the waste heat from the engine comes in this high temperature form. The exhaust gases pass through a heat exchanger, producing hot water used for space heating or low pressure steam.

With up to 50% thermal efficiency, highest of any standard internal or external combustion engine, the diesel engine is able to run at compression ratios in the 13-17 ranges which endows the diesel with efficiencies in the 42 to 48% range for the type of unit used in CHP systems. Such engines are usually turbocharged with exhaust temperatures below 450°C. The higher electrical efficiency results in less heat being available, but overall, the power plus heat, or "CHP" efficiency, is similar to natural gas IC engines, at 90-95%. Since electricity is more valuable than heat, the relatively small increase in electrical efficiency from diesels compared to IC engines is valuable. The major drawback of diesels is that they only operate on liquid fuels.

Steam Turbines

Steam turbines: They provide the advantage of being very versatile, easily adaptable and customizable. Their capacity ranges from 50 kWe to several hundred MWe. Finally, they offer a wide range of fuel flexibility and a long lifespan (over 50 years). Steam turbines are commonly used in the industry: they are used for systems matched to solid fuel boilers, industrial waste heat, or the waste heat from a gas turbine (making it a combined cycle.) with a wide spectrum of designs and complexity enable matching the desired application and performance specifications. In terms of penetration they represent about one third of installed CHP capacity. The overall CHP efficiency of steam turbines is approximately 80%.

Gas Turbines and Combined Cycles

Gas turbines: Gas turbines generally have a power range from 500 kWe to more than 300 MWe and represent the main technology in terms of capacity. The technology is derived from aerospace industry (variants of the turbojet and turboprop used in aircrafts) and commonly use gas or fuel oils. They offer a large power output with sizing ranges from micro-turbines (see below) to very large frame turbines used for central station power generation. Typically, the 5-60 MW range is often too high for most CHP schemes. High heat temperature from the turbine exhaust are typically used for producing high pressure steam, suitable for process industries less for district heating application⁷⁷. Most economic applications for CHP applications are for sizes above 5 MW which is much beyond the SmartCHP range and are not directly competing.

They present several advantages in terms of engine reliability which is beneficial for maintenance, in addition the higher output turbines offers electrical efficiencies over 30%. But they suffer from intrinsic problems: Overall the CHP efficiencies of even the larger gas turbines are mediocre, and not much above 85%, noise disturbances requiring installation away for residential areas, requirements upstream for a gas compressor since the fuel gas has to be at high pressure, 20-30 bar and downstream need of oversized heat exchanger to absorb the pressure drop effects.

MicroTurbines

Microturbines: Microturbines are same gas turbines, available from 30 to 330 kWe, multiple turbine package could reach 1 000 kWe. They are easily adjustable depending on the power required and to provide a stable and reliable power. Microturbines are less widespread in terms of capacity. Developed for stationery and transportation power sources in the last decades, they consist in a compact, mechanically simple, clean-burning mechanism which make them well suited for medium to small cogeneration. In terms of the overall CHP efficiency, microturbines could not reach more than 75%.

⁷⁷ A gas turbine is a machine that works best at above 85% of its nominal rating. It follows that in a typical district heating scheme, where there are big variations during a 24 hour period, gas turbines are not necessarily the optimum choice

Micro-CHP ORC Stirling

A micro-CHP system is a small heat engine (power plant) which provides all the power for an individual building: heating, ventilation, air conditioning and electric power. Micro-CHP engine systems are usually based on several different technologies described in this section.: Internal combustion engines, Stirling engines, Steam engines (using either the traditional water or organic chemicals such as refrigerants), Microturbines, Fuel cells. Many types of fuels and sources of heat are used for micro-CHP, just as for regular CHP installations with properties varying in terms of system cost, heat cost, environmental effects, convenience, ease of transportation and storage, system maintenance, and system life. One could mention biomass, LPG, vegetable oil (such as rapeseed oil), wood gas, solar thermal, and natural gas, as well as multi-fuel systems.

These systems are not direct competitors for SmartCHP since below the 50 kWe (sometimes the threshold goes up to 100 kWe) and address the residential and small-scale commercial applications to fulfil their electricity and heat consumption. The overall CHP efficiency of those systems is around 85%.

ORC: At smaller sizes, electric power range below 1 MWe, that is the range of SmartCHP for applications in decentralized heat and power generation ORC (Organic Rankine Cycle) plants are commercially available systems ensuring good conversion efficiencies. Indeed, the classic water Rankine Cycle at small scales is not efficient leading to the replacement of water as the working medium by an low boiling point organic compound (e.g. a silicone oil or organic solvent). Efficiency is thus improved at the operating range of temperature, pressure and scale. Several manufacturers commercialise small biomass ORC-CHP plants with electrical outputs in the range of 100-160 kWe with thermal to electric ratio around 5:1.

Stirling Engines: They are external combustion engines, in which the working gas is alternately compressed and expanded respectively in a cold cylinder volume and a hot cylinder volume. Heat is produced externally and transferred into the engine. The engine heat exchanger working temperature is in the range of 700- 800 °C. In the engine, the heat is converted into work and lower temperature-level heat is rejected in the cooler that could be used for cogeneration with low temperatures (40-60°C). Commercial Stirling engines are available with a net electrical output ranging from 35 to about 140 kWe

Fuel Cells

Fuel cells: Fuel cells are an emerging small-scale power generation technology, mostly under 1 MW although larger applications do exist. The Fuel Cell technology is the most disruptive when compared to the previous technologies. Indeed, fuel cells produce a current through an electrochemical reaction instead of using the combustion. Fuel cells use hydrogen for operation and convert its chemical energy into water and electricity.

Hydrogen can be obtained from other hydrogen-rich sources such as gasoline, coal gas or natural gas methanol and other hydrocarbon fuels. Cost effective, efficient fuel reformers that can convert various fuels to hydrogen are necessary to allow fuel cells increased flexibility and better economics. Fuel cells have very low levels of NOx and CO emissions, all resulting from the reforming process. Using gasifiers

to produce hydrogen fuel from sources such as biomass could help to increase flexibility and market share of fuel cells.

Different technologies compete among Fuel Cells, each with a specific electrochemical process: phosphoric acid (PAFC), molten carbonate (MCFC), solid oxide (SOFC), proton exchange membrane (PEMFC), alkaline (AFC), etc. The main advantages of fuel cells consist in their low emissions and low noise. They have a capacity from around 5 kW_e to 2 MW_e but all do not present the same Technology Readiness Levels. PAFC and MCFC systems are commercially available in different sizes (PAFC 200 kW_e and 400 kW_e, MCFC 300 kW_e and 1200 kW_e).

Although fuel cells were first designed as purely electric generators, there are mainly developed for transportation applications today. Fuel cells primarily used for power generation, such as Phosphoric Acid, Solid Oxide, and Molten Carbonate fuel cells, are generally not suited for transportation use.

For Fuel Cells used in CHP applications, heat is generally recovered in the form of hot water or low-pressure steam with a quality of heat dependent on the fuel cell type and operating temperature. Fuel cells can be used in two different types of industrial cogeneration applications: to produce hot water at around 60°C, or to produce hot water at around 60°C and low temperature steam at 120°C. Overall efficiency for both is around 80-85 %.

This technology is not mature yet and fuel cell capital costs remain high⁷⁸ due to low-volume custom production methods, several EU-funded projects deal with the next generation of solid oxide fuel cells (e.g. EC funded OxiGEN project for small scale applications) but they remain in demand for CHP applications because of their low air emissions, low-noise, and a strong public support.

7.1.4 Potential competitors for SmartCHP

Three main parameters are considered at first analysis when comparing a SmartCHP unit to a conventional CHP system:

- **capacity,**
- **flexibility in operation**
- **and use of non-fossil fuel supply.**

For a complete analysis, additional parameters have to be taken into account:

- **the local factor** and the surrounding context (support scheme to CHP or to green energy, availability of the feedstock, vicinity to a FPBO plant)
- **the end user segment and the specific needs in terms of heat and electricity demand** in a given market segment: they could indeed differ in a large manner depending on the end user.

Three out of the above technology families are the most represented technologies for CHP: Reciprocating engines, steam turbines and gas turbines and cover a capacity range much wider beyond the 0.1 MW_e-1 MW_e range of SmartCHP.

⁷⁸ In the eHighway2050 study, supply block generation, by VGB, October 2013 the following CAPEX were mentioned for Fuel Cells roadmap. 2013: Capex 3700 EUR/kW and 79% efficiency; projection 2030: 2500 EUR/kW and 80% efficiency; projection 2050: 2100 EUR/kW and 80% efficiency

When considering the targeted capacity range, three families - Fuel cells, microturbines and reciprocating engines - are most likely to be competitors for SmartCHP systems.

The size factor does not exclude *a priori* the other technologies, since available at a wide range of sizes but a second key parameter needs to be considered: the heat to electricity ratio which typically differs from device to device. Conventional technologies as reciprocating engines, steam or gas turbines tend to provide more heat than electricity, contrary to fuel cells which provide a higher proportion of electricity.

By offering a highly flexible Power to Heat ratio (P:H) and a broad spectrum of operating modes – heat- or electricity-driven with the possibility to shift from one to another operating mode according to the conditions constitutes a key advantage for a SmartCHP unit in comparison to ‘frozen’ P:H ratios.

Fuel supply also matters and offers a new competitive advantage to SmartCHP. Concerning fuel types, gas is the most widespread among conventional cogeneration technologies. Heating networks using biomass as wood pellets are also developing. They can be, in a way, important competitors. Of course, they often operate on a different scale but claim the same advantages as the CO₂ reduction. However, SmartCHP keeps the competitive advantage of flexibility since heating networks focus on heat.

7.1.5 Competitive advantages and disadvantages of SmartCHP technology

The following table enlarge an analysis of pros and cons of a conventional CHP technology⁷⁹ with additional features specific to SmartCHP. CHP systems above or beneath the SmartCHP ranges are indicated in a light grey colour since a competition analysis does not make sense

The value proposition of SmartCHP consists in Offering a combined heat and electricity energy system in the class of **100-1000 kW_e** which is clean, cost-efficient thanks to **bioliquid-fuel fed CHP** with highly flexible Power to Heat ratios.

Main components are:

- Small-scale CHP (Combined Heat & Power) unit (100 - 1,000 kW_e)
- Flexible ratio between heat & electricity bringing more adaptability
- Adaptability to variations of the demand
- Use of a liquid biofuel (FBPO)
- Annual electricity production: 500 - 1,000 MWh
- Annual heat production: 750 - 2,000 MWh
- Electricity price below 0.10 €/kWh
- High resource conversion efficiency
- Provides energy security

⁷⁹ Source: Long term prospects of CHP, dated 2016, VGB. Access: <https://www.vgb.org/vgbmultimedia/FE398-p-12476.pdf>

- ROI less than 7 years
- Clean flue gas.

SmartCHP offers a combined heat and electricity energy system which is clean, cost-efficient thanks to biofuel CHP with highly flexible H:P ratio. This product is targeted in the class of 100 kW_e to 1000 kW_e for commercial and residential customers.

SmartCHP adds two important characteristics to the current CHP market, energy flexibility and fuel flexibility. For the traditional CHP, the CHP economic fundamentals require that the thermal energy from the system be used for many hours a year—sometimes close to a full 8,760 hours—to justify the expense of setting up the thermal part of the system in the first place. In addition, efficiencies tend to fall for systems that have low or variable output rates. However, SmartCHP could have a flexible heat and electricity ratio which is suitable for integrating with renewables and adjust the different demand according to the user requirement. What's more, biofuel CHP is demanding increased fuel flexibility in order to maximize utilization of local renewable biomass and recycled fuels.

In next table distinctive advantages of a SmartCHP solution are presented face to several cogeneration technologies⁸⁰. In addition, there are some generic arguments for advantage /disadvantage of SmartCHP in comparison to any competing CHP system. For the sake of readability of the table, these arguments are not repeated in all rows of the table.

- Distinctive advantage of smartCHP: Opportunity to get lower OPEX based on low cost fuel in some regions (FPBO prices)
- Possible disadvantage of SmartCHP: Supply require processing (FPBO), Lower maturity and experience curve.

⁸⁰ Gas Turbines & Combined Cycle 500 kW – 400 MW, offering -High reliability -Low emissions -High grade heat available with no necessity of cooling are not reported in the table since this technology is not directly a competitor for SmartCHP. Just for the lower band. But even in the small scale a combined cycle would be hard to operate.

Table 7-2: Pros and cons of conventional CHP technologies

CHP system (Capacity range)	Advantages of CHP	Disadvantages of CHP	P:H ratio	Start- up time	Use of produced heat					Distinctive advantage of smartCHP	Possible disadvantage of smartCHP
	<i>compared to non CHP energy systems</i>				Space Heating	Hot water	LP steam	HP steam	Distri- ct Heating		
Reciprocating engines - Spark ignition 1 kW_e to 5 MW_e	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High power efficiency with part-load operational flexibility - Fast start-up. - Relatively low investment cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -High maintenance costs -Lower temperature heat cogeneration -Relatively high emissions 	0.5 to 2	10 sec	X		X			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible ratio between heat & electricity -Adaptability to variations of the demand -Use of a liquid biofuel Clean flue gas (specific process) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start-up time might be longer Likely OPEX (maintenance) might be higher with some uncertainty in the OPEX (high variability in terms of FPBO prices) Supply requires processing (FPBO) Lower maturity and experience curve
Steam turbine 150 kW_e – several hundred MW_e	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fuel flexibility -Heat extraction at multiple temperatures -Long working life and high reliability - Variable power to heat ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slow start up -Requires a boiler or other steam source 	0,07 - 0.57	1h to 1d				X	X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Not a direct competitor since just for the lower band. (most of Steam Turbines are for higher applications) -Same as above - Quicker start up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heat extraction as for a diesel ICE (no multiple temperature) Lower maturity and experience curve
Micro-turbine 30 kW_e - 300 kW_e up to 1 MWe with multiple units	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Few moving parts - Compact size -Low emissions - No cooling required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High costs -Relatively low mechanical efficiency - Limited to lower temperature 	0.2 to 0.5	60 sec	X	X				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Same as above especially the flexibility on power to heat ratio -Competitive in CAPEX 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher temperature could be extracted

		cogeneration applications - Very low P:H ratio								-Range partially matching Wide range of heat uses (temperature, pressure)	
Fuel Cells below 5 kW_e to 2 MW_e	-Low emissions and noise -High efficiency overload range -Modular design	- High costs - Fuels require processing - Sensitive to fuel impurities - Low power density	1 - 2	3h - 2d	X		X	X		-Same as above -Competitive in CAPEX (lower CAPEX of SmartCHP) It is technically challenging to feed Fuel cells with renewable resources	Emissions of FC are very low, thus clean flue gas of smartCHP is not any longer a competitive advantage vs. Fuel Cells
ORC 1 kW_e - 3 MW_e	-Low temperature operation - Fuel flexibility -Low maintenance costs -Modular design	- High investment costs - Low power to heat ratio - Poor efficiency at low loading - Dependence on ambient temperature	0.1 - 0.4	20 min - 1h	X	X				-Same as above - ORC is quite costly -High flexible P:H ratio -SmartCHP is competitive in CAPEX	Possibly higher maintenance costs depending on the origin of the heat
Stirling Engine 1 kW_e – 1,5 MW_e	- Few moving parts - Compact size -Low emissions - No cooling required	- High costs, High temperature operation - Relatively low mechanical efficiency - Limited to lower temperature CHP applications	0.1 - 0.4	20 min - 1h	X	X				Limited developments of Stirling Engines, impacting the experience curve and the reduction of Capex	Possibly higher maintenance costs

7.2 Indirect competition

7.2.1 Supply chain with other competing energy solutions

This section focuses on the indirect competition and mainly the factors impacting the supply chain and the availability of the biomass.

Face to the energetic use through the production of a liquid fuel from fast pyrolysis, competing valorisation modes need to be listed:

- Material valorisation (for wood waste from carpentry: chipboard or plywood or pallet packaging; manufacture of paper pulp).
- Second-hand use (recycling of crates or boxes by individuals)
- Organic valorisation (e.g. manure from poultry farming)
- Direct thermal use (incineration of fruit stones, grinding of spreading wood)
- Valorisation by transformation into other sources of energy (other biofuels from fast growing crops, biogas)
- Food use for livestock.

7.2.2 Other competing energy solutions

Conventional heat production system that are fully mature and available at a competitive CAPEX and OPEX constitute serious competitors for SmartCHP in all market segments requiring high level of heat decoupled from electricity.

The competition strength will be even stronger for segments highly sensitive to cost of energy and which not value the green image that conveys SmartCHP solution.

More generally all barriers mentioned in literature for implementing CHP are fully applicable to SmartCHP. According to Code 2 projects, four main types for barriers impede or slow down an active market roll-out of CHP in Europe:

- When the reward of CHP for its energy savings at the system level from electricity and heat markets is not sufficient
- When there are issues related to grid connection or network charges or permitting
- When a regulatory or even legislative uncertainty remains for energy stakeholders
- When the focus on heat or on primary energy savings is less considered in comparison to energy end use consumption.

To go further the consideration of the local factor and the surrounding context in all its components, policy and regulation context (support scheme to CHP or to green energy, availability of the feedstock, vicinity to a FPBO plant) has to be taken into account as well as the requirements of a given end user segment. It is likely that non-technical considerations will play a greater role in the decision-making act for adopting a SmartCHP energy system.

Highlights chapter 7:

- SmartCHP offers a distinctive value proposition against other CHP technologies adding two important characteristics to the current CHP market, energy flexibility and fuel flexibility
- It offers a combined heat and electricity energy system which is clean, cost-efficient thanks to biofuel CHP with highly flexible H:P ratio. This product is targeted in the class of 100 kW_e to 1000 kW_e for commercial and residential customers
- Assessing the economics benefits for the end consumer cannot be done theoretically and requires to be performed on a specific use case with an actual electricity and heat end consumer with its specific load characteristics and surrounding context.

8. Conclusions

SmartCHP aims to become a leading technological CHP proposal which, through its flexible nature can provide heat and electricity at high efficiency, while at the same time it contributes to the significant reduction of the carbon footprint both at user, Country and European level, complying with EU policy towards climate-neutrality by 2050 and the European Green Deal, for at least 40% reduction of greenhouse gas emissions compared the 1990 levels, at least 32% share for renewable energy and at least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency.

This Market Assessment enabled an understanding of the size of the potential for the application of the SmartCHP technology offering in the European Market. The methodology adopted for the assessment involves an analysis of market trends and factors affecting the employment of CHP technology, a market segmentation based on geographic and on customer features, the quantification of the CHP / SmartCHP market as well as the existing or upcoming technology competitors.

CHP market analysis provides a solid foundation to any market assessment for SmartCHP. The share of CHP in total electricity generation at EU-27 level during last decade has remained fairly stable 11.5 – 12,4 % during last decade attributed to a combination of reasons, such as the variations of the international primary fuel prices or the increasing penetration of the electricity produced from Renewable Energy sources. The CHP penetration level differs considerably between countries.

There are several factors driving CHP market, ranging from purely technical and inherent to CHP factors up to the normative/legislative environment including also any incentives in favour of CHP. Policy expressed at central EU level or local/country level has proven to be a prime market driver. CHP penetration has largely been supported by incentives such as Feed-in-tariff and Feed-in Premium schemes, loans or grants, Tax mechanisms, among others. Such schemes combined with the inherent to CHP advantages, i.e. efficiency improvement, thus reduction of fuel related operating costs, etc. have proven to be key drivers for the penetration of CHP. On the other hand, regulatory and legislative uncertainty or inconsistency, or the volatility of primary fuel prices can adversely affect CHP penetration / reduce its share at local or EU level.

In the context of this project, and for testing and assessing the efficiency and effectiveness of the SmartCHP technological proposal, five focus countries have been selected based on techno-economic and policy criteria including the supply chain for oil pyrolysis and availability of the biomass in proximity. These countries are Croatia, Greece, the Netherlands, Romania and Sweden.

For the selected countries the theoretical market potential for a CHP system in the range of 0,1 to 1 MW_e has been evaluated (tens of thousands units), in order to serve as a basis for the SmartCHP potential. Following that, it is estimated the potential of SmartCHP units in the five focus countries ranges from 950 to 4,700. Such estimated penetration potential has to be considered jointly with the quantity of FPBO needed for operation. The annual FPBO quantity per tonne needed for one SmartCHP unit with respective capacity of 0.1 kW_e and 1 MW_e amounts to a range of approximately 150 to 1,500 tonnes per year, from the lowest to highest engine's capacity, respectively.

Competition analysis that was carried out confirms such potential through the distinctive value proposition of SmartCHP facing conventional CHP and especially the value of a flexible operation.

Such market potential will be further elaborated and assessed considering the bio-oil availability and the logistics and limitations involved in its supply chain, e.g. biomass availability, production capacity, transportation, price of fuel at the user's facility, as well as the competition at technology level (i.e. tested and mature technologies, such as engine driven or gas turbine driven CHP, or fuel cells among others) and at system wise level (i.e. systems supplying separately heat or electricity with high efficiency).

Assessing the economics benefits for the end consumer indeed requires focusing on a specific use case with actual electricity and heat end consumer load characteristics and surrounding context. This will precisely be the object of the techno-economic analysis to be deployed in the project.

Annex 1 – Quantification of SmartCHP potential

Introduction

This Annex provides the background for the quantification the SmartCHP potential in the five focus countries, it provides details for data collection and the calculation process for each of the considered market segments. The quantification process is the similar for all market segments, including:

- Description of the market segment
- Information referring to each segment at EU27 and country level sourced from Eurostat. The information provided is given in units suited to the segment (e.g. bedrooms for a hotel or surface floor for an office building).
- Quantification of the potential for SmartCHP units in the five focus countries.

Segment: Hotels

Hotels

Description

As per Eurostat definition the hotel sector includes hotels and similar accommodation, holiday and other short-stay apartments and camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks.

EU27 market potential

At EU level in 2018 the number of bed places was more than 32 million, including hotels and similar accommodation, holiday and other short-stay apartments and camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. In terms of hotels and similar accommodation, there were more than 14 million bed places and around 6,7 million bedrooms⁸¹.

	Tourist accommodation establishments		Hotels and similar accommodation		
	Establishments	Bed places	Establishments	Bedrooms	Bed places
EU-28	684.737	32.237.438	201.676	6.771.021	14.094.303
Austria	21.494	1.045.637	12.003	292.458	615.541
Belgium	9.211	389.826	1.536	60.702	136.406
Bulgaria	3.458	335.597	2.102	124.148	286.219
Croatia	108.212	1.115.659	1.065	81.223	169.108
Cyprus	802	87.240	800	42.353	86.252
Czechia	9.426	741.235	6.277	141.450	327.572
Denmark	1.167	426.075	565	48.523	97.642
Estonia	1.535	61.193	418	16.084	34.108
Finland	1.372	260.071	788	60.166	143.256
France	29.652	5.111.960	18.090	652.957	1.305.914
Germany	50.020	3.473.630	32.433	976.745	1.846.611
Greece	38.180	1.340.451	9.910	420.991	822.075
Hungary	4.587	419.199	2.357	74.956	183.557
Ireland	3.145	199.756	2.348	64.643	150.083
Italy	216.141	5.113.197	32.898	1.091.541	2.260.893
Latvia	1.145	53.948	342	12.979	26.475
Lithuania	3.616	89.813	387	14.944	30.900
Luxembourg	425	63.612	225	7.535	15.543
Malta	211	45.239	194	19.057	43.522
Netherlands	9.145	1.397.897	3.760	131.903	286.069
Poland	11.076	798.723	4.179	170.640	353.785
Portugal	5.964	648.530	2.406	154.145	358.723
Romania	7.720	348.592	2.867	116.170	223.177
Slovakia	3.087	190.773	1.599	41.720	101.590
Slovenia	3 699(u)	117 137(u)	698	22.908	46.639
Spain	51.418	3.599.886	19.657	930.172	1.940.264
Sweden	4.249	819.055	2.057	125.623	251.894

The total number of hotels and similar accommodation establishments 201,676., These are split in 3 categories:

- Less than 25 bedrooms
- From 25 to 99 bedrooms
- More than 100 bedrooms

In the first category (less than 25 bedrooms), there are 130,686 establishments (out of a total of 201,676), which amounted to almost 65% out of the total. Respectively, in the second category (25 to 99 bedrooms) there are 56,268

⁸¹ [Eurostat: capacity of tourist accommodation establishments](#)

establishments (28% of the total), and in the third category (i.e. above 100 bedrooms) 14,722 establishments (7.3% of the total)⁸².

	Total number of hotels and similar accommodation establishments	Less than 25 rooms	From 25 to 99 rooms	From 100 to 249 rooms
EU-28	201.676	64,8	27,9	7,3
Austria		12.003		
Belgium		1.536		
Bulgaria	2.102	20,0	46,8	17,2
Croatia	1.065	45,4	30,0	17,5
Cyprus	800	54,4	26,5	15,5
Czechia	6.277	77,5	19,6	2,4
Denmark		565		
Estonia		418		
Finland		788		
France		18.090		
Germany	32.433	67,7	26,2	5,3
Greece	9.910	51,0	40,7	6,2
Hungary	2.357	68,9	24,4	5,4
Ireland		2.348		
Italy	32.898	54,6	41,1	4,4
Latvia	342	62,3	28,4	8,2
Lithuania	387	55,8	34,6	9,0
Luxembourg	225	61,8	30,7	7,6
Malta	194	33,5	33,5	20,6
Netherlands		3.760		
Poland	4.179	48,0	44,2	6,9
Portugal		2.406		
Romania	2.867	53,3	36,6	8,5
Slovakia		1.599		
Slovenia		698		
Spain	19.657	61,6	25,9	9,0
Sweden	2.057	18,9	44,3	22,9

*For Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Ireland, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovakia and Slovenia there are no available data for the classification of the hotels

Potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries

In the 5 focus countries the number of bedrooms and bed places in 2018 are the following:

- Croatia: 81,223 bedrooms and 169,108 beds
- Greece: 420,991 bedrooms and 822, 075 beds
- Netherlands: 131,903 bedrooms and 286,069 beds
- Romania: 116,170 bedrooms and 223,177 beds
- Sweden: 125,623 bedrooms and 251,894 beds.

⁸² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Tourism_statistics_-_annual_results_for_the_accommodation_sector#More_than_32_million_bed_places_in_EU_tourist_accommodation

	Tourist accommodation establishments		Hotels and similar accommodation		
	Establishments	Bed places	Establishments	Bedrooms	Bed places
Croatia	108.212	1.115.659	1.065	81.223	169.108
Greece	38.180	1.340.451	9.910	420.991	822.075
Netherlands	9.145	1.397.897	3.760	131.903	286.069
Romania	7.720	348.592	2.867	116.170	223.177
Sweden	4.249	819.055	2.057	125.623	251.894

In addition, the share (%) of total number of hotels and similar accommodation establishments in the 5 focus countries, is presented in the following table.

	Total number of hotels and similar accommodation establishments	Less than 25 rooms	From 25 to 99 rooms	From 100 to 249 rooms
Croatia	1.065	45	30	17
Greece	9.910	51	41	6
Netherlands	3.760			
Romania	2.867	53	37	8
Sweden	2.057	19	44	23

In terms of energy consumption, hotels have one of the highest specific consumption, compared to other commercial buildings. Their energy consumption varies from hotel to hotel, depending on size, provided facilities and location. From a survey implemented in EU, it is estimated that the annual average energy consumption ranges from 239 to 300 kWh/m², where 50% is consumed for electricity needs⁸³. Electricity is one of the most consumed sectors in hotels due to fact that it is needed for the operation of the facilities, provided from each hotel (i.e. restaurants, laundries, lighting, etc.).

In addition, several studies for different countries have been implemented to assess the energy consumption in the hotel sector. These are given in the following table.

In Greece, according to a survey from 158 hotels, the total annual energy consumption was 4,3 TWh, with an average of 273 kWh/m² per year, with an average of around 70% used for heating⁸⁴. Another study from 5 hotels in Greece, concluded that the energy consumption ranged from 70 to 520 kWh/ m², with an average of around 290 kWh/ m².

Source	Energy consumption (kWh/m ²)
I. Farou et. al (2012), "A method for energy classification of hotels: A case-study of Greece"	United States: 401 (52% for gas and 41% for electricity)
Bohdanowicz et al (2007), "Determinants and benchmarking of resource consumption in hotels— case study of Hilton International and Scandic in Europe"	Canada: 610 - 689 (30% for electricity, 36% for gas and 44% for heat)

⁸³ I. Farou et. al (2012), "A method for energy classification of hotels: A case-study of Greece"

⁸⁴ I. Farou et. al (2012), "A method for energy classification of hotels: A case-study of Greece"

Deng et al (2000), "A study of energy performance of hotel buildings in Hong Kong"	Hong Kong: 260 – 370
Priyadarsini et al (2009), "study on energy performance of hotel buildings in Singapore"	Singapore: 430 (360 for electricity)
Lagoudi et al (2004), "Development of An Audit Tool for Hotel Buildings and the Promotion of RUE and RES"	Europe: total energy consumption is 39 TWh (50% for electricity)
Santamouris et al (1996), "Energy conservation and retrofitting potential in Hellenic hotels"	Greece: 273
Karagiorgas et al (2006), "A simulation of the energy consumption monitoring in Mediterranean hotels Application in Greece"	Italy: 215 Spain: 287 France: 420

For the calculation of the potential SmartCHP market, above information has been considered.

As a starting point, it is considered that the average size of a bedroom (including the common areas) is approximately 50 m². Taking into account also the total number of hotels (161,961), the share of electricity consumption (from existing studies) is found to be around 60% out of the total energy consumption. Sourcing information from several reports and studies referring to different countries in the EU, the average electricity consumption is 179 kWh/m²/yr.

Based on Eurostat statistics, it was calculated that around 55% of the hotels have 0-25 bedrooms, 35% have 25-100 bedrooms and 10% more than 100 bedrooms. Considering the share of bedrooms in each category and the total number of hotels, total floor area and the total and average electricity consumption per category, it has been considered that target hotels are those with more than 25 bedrooms having average electricity electrical capacity demand of more than 100 kW.

Taking a fraction for energy 50%, and target fraction for SmartCHP 5-10%, SmartCHP target potential is in the range from 400 to 4,500 units in the EU.

The same calculations were followed for the 5 focus countries.

Conclusions

Based on the size of the hotels, we assumed that the most suitable hotels for the implementation of the SmartCHP technology are those with more than 25 bedrooms.

Taking into account the share of establishments per number of rooms, it is indicated that around 70,000 hotels form a potential market in EU27.

More specifically, and based on the data above, it is assumed that the potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries, will be as followed.

- Croatia: 5-50 hotels
- Greece: 25-250 hotels
- Netherlands: 10-120 hotels
- Romania: 5-80 hotels
- Sweden: 10-70 hotels

Segment: Hospitals

Hospitals

Description

This market segment includes curative care beds, rehabilitative care beds, long term care beds and other beds.

EU27 market potential

At EU level, the number of hospital beds in 2018 was around 2,5 million, including curative care beds, rehabilitative care beds, long term care beds and other beds, as presented in the following figure for 2018.

Country	Total Available beds	Curative care beds	Rehabilitative care beds	Long-term care beds	Other beds
EU27	2.401.257	1.752.982	435.488	-	-
Austria	64.285	47.276	11.288	5.721	-
Belgium	64.248	56.758	6.325	1.165	0
Bulgaria	53.173	43.870	6.819	2.484	0
Croatia	22.960	14.337	4.624	3.999	0
Cyprus	2.872	2.872	0	0	0
Czechia	70.351	43.367	4.832	20.821	1.331
Denmark	14.077	13.659	168	250	0
Estonia	6.046	4.444	318	1.181	103
Finland	19.921	15.667	205	3.782	267
France	395.670	203.662	105.550	31.081	55.377
Germany	-	-	-	-	-
Greece	45.053	39.011	334	5.708	0
Hungary	68.555	41.727	14.896	11.932	0
Ireland	14.475	13.560	179	736	0
Italy	189.753	156.216	25.119	8.418	0
Latvia	10.587	6.198	750	1.279	2.360
Lithuania	18.025	14.861	1.697	1.467	0
Luxembourg	2.740	2.251	489	0	0
Malta	2.088	1.546	416	126	0
Netherlands	54.547	46.323	1.932	6.292	0
Poland	248.239	179.796	67.461	982	0
Portugal	35.429	33.850	581	-	998
Romania	135.691	102.913	12.850	19.928	0
Slovakia	31.026	26.201	797	4.028	0
Slovenia	9.183	8.574	200	293	116
Spain	139.061	116.841	1.769	20.451	0
Sweden	21.754	20.020	1.623	-	111

Following the total available number of beds, there is also a further categorization of the number of beds based on type of ownership. Hospitals which categorized under the public ownership class, are those which operated or controlled under the government or another public corporation. Private hospitals distinguished in two sub-categories. The first one refers to not-for-profit hospitals which provide services with no financial gain for the unit that establishes, controls or finances those and the second one refers to for-profit hospitals⁸⁵. The percentage of the number of beds in public healthcare facilities is approximately 65%, and the percentage in the not-for-profit and in the for-profit private healthcare facilities was approximately 15% and 20% respectively.

Potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries

⁸⁵ [Eurostat Healthcare resource statistics](#)

In the 5 focus countries, the total available beds, as well as the beds per category, are presented in the following table.

Country	Total Available beds	Curative care beds	Rehabilitative care beds	Long-term care beds	Other beds
Croatia	22.960	14.337	4.624	3.999	0
Greece	45.053	39.011	334	5.708	0
Netherlands	54.547	46.323	1.932	6.292	0
Romania	135.691	102.913	12.850	19.928	0
Sweden	21.754	20.020	1.623	-	111

In the five focus countries, the split of the number of beds is presented in the following:

- Croatia: 22,960 total
 - Beds in public hospitals: 22,552
 - Beds in private hospitals: 408
 - Not-for-profit private hospitals: 140
 - For-profit private hospitals: 268
- Greece: 45,053
 - Beds in public hospitals: 29,566
 - Beds in private hospitals: 15,487
 - Not-for-profit private hospitals: 828
 - For-profit private hospitals: 14,659
- Romania: 127,082
 - Beds in public hospitals: 22,552
 - Beds in private hospitals: 8,609
 - Not-for-profit private hospitals: 584
 - For-profit private hospitals: 8,025
- The Netherlands: 54,547 (all of them are in not-for-profit private hospitals)
- Sweden: 21,754

Several studies conducted in the past provide analyses of the energy consumption in healthcare facilities⁸⁶. According to those, the split of total energy consumption for electricity and thermal needs is approximately 40% and 60%, respectively^{87, 88, 89}.

Source	Minimum Energy consumption (kWh/bed)	Maximum Energy consumption (kWh/bed)
International Federation of Hospital Engineering (IFHE-EU) ⁹⁰	4,015	21,900
Application Models for Power Distribution, 2016 ⁹¹	Italy: 5,100 Netherlands: 9,800 Belgium: 10,200 Sweden: 20,000 Canada: 23,000 Australia: 27,500	
Average	15,500	

⁸⁶ Bawaneh et al (2019), “Energy Consumption Analysis and Characterization of Healthcare Facilities in the United States”

⁸⁷ Siemens (2016), “Application Models for Power Distribution – Hospitals”

⁸⁸ Calcedo, (2014), “Analysis on Energy Efficiency in Healthcare Buildings”

⁸⁹ IFHE, (2017), “Meeting the goals set by energy efficiency”

⁹⁰ ENERGY - QUESTIONNAIRE IFHE-EUROPE

⁹¹ Siemens (2016), “Application Models for Power Distribution – Hospitals”

Source	Minimum Energy consumption (kWh/ m ²)	Maximum Energy consumption (kWh/ m ²)
International Federation of Hospital Engineering (IFHE-EU)	44	183
IFHE (Vienna General Hospital, 600,000 m ² total area)	203	
Energy Consumption Analysis and Characterization of Healthcare Facilities in the United States ⁹²	640	780
Saidur et al, 2010, "An end-use energy analysis in a Malaysian public hospital"	234	
Chirarattananon et al, 2010, "Assessment of energy savings from the revised building energy code of Thailand"	149	
Chung et al, 2015, "Comparison of building energy demand for hotels, hospitals, and offices in Korea" ⁹³	128 for electricity demand and 452 for heat demand	
Gonzalez et al, 2018, "A quantitative analysis of final energy consumption in hospitals in Spain"	270	
Calcedo, 2014, "Analysis on Energy Efficiency in Healthcare Buildings" ⁹⁴	270 (average from 55 healthcare facilities in Spain, size between 500 to 3,500 m ²)	
Bakaimis et al, 2017, "Electrical Energy Saving Policies, Initiatives, Results, Challenges and Lessons Learned for the Grevena Hospital" ⁹⁵	105 (110 beds from a hospital in Grevena, Greece)	
Application Models for Power Distribution, 2016 ⁹⁶	Switzerland: 65 Netherlands: 85 Belgium: 85 Sweden: 100 United Kingdom: 105 Greece: 110 Canada: 335 USA: 230 Australia: 175	

For hospitals, the share for electricity needs is approximately 40%. The average electricity consumption, which is (4,645 kWh/bed/yr).

Hospitals are categorized according to their capacity. i.e. in 5 categories i.e. 51-99 beds, 100-199, 200-299, 300-499 and more than 400 beds. The share of hospitals belonging to each size category has been calculated for the scope of assessing the number of hospitals per category.

⁹² [Healthcare facilities in the US](#)

⁹³ [Comparison of building energy demand in Korea](#)

⁹⁴ <http://downloads.hindawi.com/journals/jhe/2014/485701.pdf>

⁹⁵ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S187802961730186X?via%3Dihub>

⁹⁶

<https://assets.new.siemens.com/siemens/assets/api/uuid:83f5975549e5055ceddca99fab7d09d70c1acf88/application-models-for-hospitals.pdf>

To assess the average electricity consumption per category, the total kWh per category and per hospital has been considered. As a result of those calculations, hospitals with more than 100 (close to 200) beds have been considered as a potential market for our scope.

The overall potential for CHP installations has been assessed to be around 5,000 in EU-27. Considering space or other (e.g. load profile, capacity factor) limitations, approximately half of this potential is considered exploitable, i.e. approximately 2,500 CHP Units. Furthermore, as it is assumed that SmartCHP could acquire 5-10% of this potential, up to 250 units across EU27.

Conclusions

Considering that the total available beds in hospitals correspond to around 2.5 million, we estimated that there are around 8,000 hospitals in EU. For the range of the SmartCHP technology, we should focus on hospitals with more than 200 beds, which form a potential market of around 5,000 facilities.

More specifically, and based on the data above, it has been calculated that the potential for SmartCHP in the 5 focus countries is as follows.

- Croatia: 2 – 3 hospitals, out of a potential of 25 CHP applications
- Greece: range 4 – 5 hospitals out of a potential of 40-50 CHP applications
- Netherlands: range 5 – 6 hospitals out of a potential of 40-60 CHP applications
- Romania: range 10 – 15 hospitals out of a potential of 100-120 CHP applications
- Sweden: range from 2 – 3 hospitals out of a potential of 20-25 CHP applications.

Segment: Office buildings

Office
Buildings

Description

Office building description includes public and private office buildings.

In the last two decades, significant changes impacted the office buildings sector (both public and private), especially in the users' equipment: new means of communication, automation of the equipment, quality of use, highest comfort. Energy consumption in office buildings is one of the highest compared to other building types.

EU27 market potential

The number of offices (both public and private) estimated at around 2,5 million in EU 27 for 2013.

Number of offices in EU27			
Country	2013		
EU27	2,471,413	Ireland	24,495
Austria	-	Italy	407,848
Belgium	69,981	Latvia	7,150
Bulgaria	20,256	Lithuania	45,693
Croatia	23,325	Luxembourg	6,425
Cyprus	6,384	Malta	2,888
Czech Republic	55,570	Netherlands	108,946
Denmark	60,425	Poland	478,783
Estonia	8,777	Portugal	80,994
Finland	67,078	Romania	85,053
France	-	Slovakia	2,695
Germany	294,557	Slovenia	13,517
Greece	47,779	Spain	283,352
Hungary	58,795	Sweden	210,647

At EU level, the total floor area of the offices (both public and private) estimated at approximately 2,050 million m².

Total floor area of offices (m2)		
Country	2012	2013
EU28	2,032,000,000	2,050,000,000
Austria		
Belgium	72,509,394	71,982,601
Bulgaria	24,753,000	25,693,000
Croatia	7,975,000	8,003,000
Cyprus	2,261,000	2,190,000
Czech Republic	54,402,000	54,704,000
Denmark	43,884,000	44,314,000
Estonia	2,693,000	2,771,000
Finland	19,230,000	19,308,000
France	210,429,000	214,103,000
Germany	642,630,000	642,630,000
Greece	17,127,000	16,392,000
Hungary	61,605,000	64,002,000
Ireland	22,688,000	22,897,000
Italy	56,770,000	56,228,000
Latvia	6,416,000	6,464,000
Lithuania	12,426,000	13,181,000
Luxembourg	5,749,000	5,794,000
Malta	950,000	991,000
Netherlands	81,119,000	82,457,000
Poland	133,326,000	139,324,000
Portugal	27,030,000	27,788,000
Romania	5,280,000	5,376,000
Slovakia	14,226,000	15,152,000
Slovenia	4,599,000	4,638,000
Spain	97,025,000	97,215,000
Sweden	54,858,000	59,769,000

Regarding the unit consumption ranges, it appears that values are very dispersed, and can go from 100 to 1000 kWh/m². Average total energy consumption is about 280 kWh/m² per year, and it appears that 75% buildings are consuming less than 390 kWh/m².⁹⁷

The graph below illustrates the ranges of consumption in office building per m².

With these assumptions of consumption per m², **the total consumption of the whole sector (private and public) in 2013 could be estimated at around 570 million of MWh (570 TWh)**. This illustrates the high potential for SmartCHP in the sector.

The share of offices in the non-residential sector in EU and in the focus countries, respectively, are presented in the following.

⁹⁷ Source: FP6 funded EUDEEP project

Share of offices in non-residential sector in EU (%)		
Country	2012	2013
EU28	29.23	29.23
Austria	-	-
Belgium	38.80	38.83
Bulgaria	27.62	28.97
Croatia	22.50	22.38
Cyprus	27.89	26.34
Czech Republic	31.04	31.17
Denmark	38.42	38.43
Estonia	21.57	22.16
Finland	16.09	15.88
France	22.43	22.59
Germany	38.47	38.47
Greece	22.34	22.30
Hungary	42.44	43.88
Ireland	27.76	27.82
Italy	19.76	19.75
Latvia	27.26	27.23
Lithuania	24.57	25.39
Luxembourg	40.94	40.65
Malta	30.60	31.55
Netherlands	14.92	15.01
Poland	27.57	27.93
Portugal	26.00	26.60
Romania	8.49	8.60
Slovakia	14.48	14.84
Slovenia	32.57	32.42
Spain	27.85	27.84
Sweden	29.34	28.67

As regards the total floor area of the private offices, there are no available data for the majority of EU countries. Data are provided only for Greece, Netherlands, Sweden, Denmark and Germany and are presented in the following table.

Total floor area of private offices (Mm ²)							
Country	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Denmark	63.040	63.810	64.520	65.140	65.870	66.460	67.040
Germany	130.000	135.000	137.630	137.630	137.630	-	-
Greece	3.410	3.440	3.470	3.520	3.560	-	-
Netherlands	11.480	11.630	11.770	11.880	12.210	12.840	-
Sweden	6.670	6.930	6.740	6.560	7.420	7.420	7.421

The share of private offices in the non-residential sector in EU and in the focus countries is displayed in the following table.

Share of private offices in non-residential sector in EU (%)		
Country	2012	2013
EU28	20.90	20.89
Austria	-	-
Belgium	26.39	26.26
Bulgaria	13.98	14.80
Croatia	5.45	5.34
Cyprus	20.85	19.69
Czech Republic	22.45	22.30
Denmark	6.40	6.28
Estonia	9.94	10.14
Finland	3.31	3.25
France	17.53	17.65
Germany	30.23	30.23
Greece	14.72	14.45
Hungary	26.85	27.56
Ireland	21.29	21.25
Italy	16.96	16.97
Latvia	15.12	14.70
Lithuania	19.58	19.98
Luxembourg	32.74	32.48
Malta	25.25	26.38
Netherlands	10.97	11.03
Poland	20.64	21.05
Portugal	19.93	20.54
Romania	6.15	6.36
Slovakia	4.90	4.84
Slovenia	26.85	26.76
Spain	5.82	5.64
Sweden	24.52	24.38

Potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries

The number of offices (both public and private) in the focus countries in 2013 is presented below.

Number of offices in EU27	
Country	2013
Croatia	23,325
Greece	47,779
Netherlands	108,946
Romania	85,053
Sweden	210,647

The total floor area of the offices (both public and private) in the 5 focus countries is given in the following table.

Total floor area of offices (m2)		
Country	2012	2013
Croatia	7,975,000	8,003,000
Greece	17,127,000	16,392,000
Netherlands	81,119,000	82,457,000
Romania	5,280,000	5,376,000
Sweden	54,858,000	59,769,000

The share of offices in non-residential sector in the 5 focus countries, is as follows.

Share of offices in non-residential sector in the 5 focus countries (%)		
Country	2012	2013
Croatia	22.50	22.38
Greece	22.34	22.30
Netherlands	14.92	15.01
Romania	8.49	8.60
Sweden	29.34	28.67

The share of private offices in non-residential sector in the 5 focus countries, is as per next table.

Share of private offices in non-residential sector in the 5 focus countries (%)		
Country	2012	2013
Croatia	5.45	5.34
Greece	14.72	14.45
Netherlands	10.97	11.03
Romania	6.15	6.36
Sweden	24.52	24.38

Concerning the energy consumption of private offices, only data for a few countries are available.

Energy consumption of private offices in EU (Mtoe)							
Country	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Denmark	0.40	0.38	0.38	0.35	0.33	0.34	
Germany	6.88	6.45	6.66	6.86	6.39	6.77	6.41
Malta	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04
Netherlands	1.84	1.67	1.69	1.67	1.49	1.53	1.60
Sweden	0.56	0.50	0.51	0.55	0.54	0.54	0.58

The energy consumption per m² in offices, both public and private, according to ODYSSEE-MURE⁹⁸ database, ranges between 30 and 390 kWh/m².

⁹⁸ <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/services/offices-specific-energy-and-electricity-consumption.html>

Source	Energy consumption (kWh/ m ²)
ODYSSEE-MURE	Denmark: 29 Germany: 61.3 (2005) Netherlands: 119 (2005) France: 167 Sweden: 167 Spain: 389

In order to calculate the number of SmartCHP units, it is considered that the share for electricity and heating consumption is 45 and 55%, respectively.

From the total number of office buildings (2,471,413) and the total energy consumption from existing case studies, it is extracted that the average electricity consumption for electricity is 72 kWh/m²/yr and thermal needs is 88 kWh/m²/yr.

Considering as an input the share of offices of different countries per surface category, it is estimated that 25% of office buildings have up to 200 m² surface area, 45% have a surface area between 200 and 1000 m² and 30% a surface area more than 1000 m². These shares correspond to 617,853 office buildings in the small class, 1,112,136 in the medium class and 741,424 in the high class.

Considering the average electricity demand of the office buildings, it is assumed that CHP / SmartCHP could be applied in office buildings with a surface area more than 1000 m².

Overall, in EU27 the CHP potential could reach approximately 80,000 units considering a CHP unit capacity of 100 kW_e or 800-900 units considering a CHP unit capacity of 1 MW_e.

Conclusions

As regards the 5 focus countries, the estimated a market potential for SmartCHP is:

- Croatia: 50 – 100 office buildings
- Greece: 25 – 150 office buildings
- Netherlands: 25 – 400 office buildings
- Romania: 25 – 300 office buildings
- Sweden: 25 – 800 office buildings.

Segment: Education buildings

Educational
buildings

Description

The educational building sector includes primary and secondary schools, high schools and universities, research laboratories, professional training activities and others and had a share of around 20% of non-residential sector in 2011⁹⁹.

EU27 market potential

The number of educational buildings in EU28 from 2012 to 2016 is presented in the following table.

Number of educational buildings					
Country	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
EU28	957,067	955,243	968,389	973,852	973,492
Austria	22,957	24,480	25,575	25,789	26,099
Belgium	14,835	14,554	15,652	15,434	15,596
Bulgaria	8,659	8,462	8,645	8,301	7,759
Croatia	9,808	10,717	11,848	11,818	11,441
Cyprus	385	397	427	374	349
Czech Republic	20,922	20,645	20,976	20,842	21,418
Denmark	25,063	25,523	25,889	25,796	24,222
Estonia	233	213	213	236	229
Finland	10,936	11,267	11,748	11,909	11,827
France	132,811	134,201	140,887	143,474	144,306
Germany	124,200	124,935	127,034	127,502	126,064
Greece	7,144	7,015	7,122	6,946	6,822
Hungary	31,634	30,473	30,373	29,046	29,031
Ireland	8,301	8,291	8,383	8,384	8,446
Italy	54,387	54,886	55,518	54,614	55,039
Latvia	2,142	2,295	2,161	2,151	2,195
Lithuania	4,525	4,686	5,147	5,953	6,922
Luxembourg	594	628	647	597	582
Malta	226	232	242	270	303
Netherlands	15,078	15,076	14,901	14,659	14,476
Poland	39,133	40,781	41,798	41,297	40,330
Portugal	15,760	15,388	15,003	15,483	15,304
Romania	48,235	45,374	43,834	46,631	45,131
Slovakia	4,317	4,383	4,408	4,528	4,524
Slovenia	2,594	2,640	2,635	2,738	2,763
Spain	113,315	111,925	109,164	107,789	111,951
Sweden	15,251	15,351	15,538	15,907	16,161

The total floor area of the educational buildings in Mm² is given in the following table.

⁹⁹ Economidou et al, (2011), Europe's buildings under the microscope. A country-by-country review of the energy performance of buildings.

Total floor area of educational buildings					
Country	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
EU28	1,225,570,251	1,229,597,907	1,250,686,964	1,254,462,096	1,251,261,931
Austria	22,865,759	24,382,765	25,473,303	25,685,919	25,994,738
Belgium	22,990,504	22,555,313	24,256,518	23,918,757	24,168,801
Bulgaria	11,188,754	10,935,381	11,171,525	10,727,086	10,026,773
Croatia	5,867,968	6,411,511	7,088,489	7,070,509	6,844,800
Cyprus	462,188	476,454	512,715	448,566	419,039
Czech Republic	20,877,037	20,600,126	20,930,253	20,797,054	21,371,161
Denmark	21,020,000	21,190,000	21,500,000	21,580,000	21,728,000
Estonia	3,690,428	3,363,039	3,368,030	3,727,713	3,621,781
Finland	18,100,000	18,270,000	18,330,000	18,610,000	18,949,000
France	183,550,000	184,720,000	185,910,000	186,910,000	188,017,000
Germany	208,000,000	208,000,000	208,000,000	308,857,142	305,373,943
Greece	32,000,000	33,000,000	33,000,000	29,400,603	28,875,048
Hungary	35,774,562	34,461,571	34,348,497	32,848,700	32,830,778
Ireland	11,552,222	11,538,150	11,665,916	11,668,047	11,753,392
Italy	68,295,941	68,922,361	69,715,539	68,580,389	69,115,030
Latvia	3,607,475	3,864,761	3,639,006	3,622,630	3,696,747
Lithuania	5,845,015	6,052,347	6,648,210	7,689,084	8,941,008
Luxembourg	777,534	822,800	848,101	782,654	762,910
Malta	808,530	828,132	864,602	964,940	1,081,497
Netherlands	30,740,000	30,970,000	31,120,000	31,310,000	-
Poland	83,776,600	87,303,925	89,482,073	88,408,278	86,339,156
Portugal	20,887,445	20,394,267	19,883,840	20,521,161	20,283,422
Romania	10,532,776	9,907,981	9,571,839	10,182,467	9,854,991
Slovakia	8,572,333	8,701,951	8,752,173	8,990,148	8,981,609
Slovenia	5,871,804	5,976,719	5,965,600	6,198,328	6,256,215
Spain	50,150,000	50,430,000	50,730,000	51,040,000	51,339,000
Sweden	48,210,000	53,110,000	45,650,000	45,650,000	45,651,000

The share of education buildings as a percentage of the buildings in the non-residential sector in EU 28 is presented below.

Share of education buildings in non-residential sector (%)				
Country	2012	2013	2014	2015
EU28	16.06	16.04	-	-
Austria	-	-	-	-
Belgium	17.85	17.94	-	-
Bulgaria	16.22	16.14	-	-
Croatia	14.08	14.08	-	-
Cyprus	12.40	13.38	-	-
Czech Republic	14.79	14.78	-	-
Denmark	18.40	18.37	-	-
Estonia	17.94	17.13	-	-
Finland	15.15	15.02	-	-
France	19.56	19.49	-	-
Germany	12.45	12.45	-	-
Greece	16.19	16.20	-	-
Hungary	18.41	17.92	-	-
Ireland	15.77	15.81	-	-
Italy	24.94	25.27	-	-
Latvia	29.09	29.62	-	-
Lithuania	25.80	23.96	-	-
Luxembourg	10.98	10.82	-	-
Malta	20.40	20.89	-	-
Netherlands	6.62	6.63	6.60	6.55
Poland	23.23	23.02	-	-
Portugal	21.00	20.11	-	-
Romania	31.42	31.18	-	-
Slovakia	57.84	57.83	-	-
Slovenia	20.44	20.83	-	-
Spain	14.40	14.44	-	-
Sweden	26.23	26.14	-	-

Potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries

The number of educational buildings in the 5 focus countries from 2012 to 2016 and the total floor area (m²) are presented in the following tables, respectively.

Number of educational buildings					
Country	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Croatia	9,808	10,717	11,848	11,818	11,441
Greece	7,144	7,015	7,122	6,946	6,822
Netherlands	15,078	15,076	14,901	14,659	14,476
Romania	48,235	45,374	43,834	46,631	45,131
Sweden	15,251	15,351	15,538	15,907	16,161

Total floor area of educational buildings					
Country	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Croatia	5,867,968	6,411,511	7,088,489	7,070,509	6,844,800
Greece	32,000,000	33,000,000	33,000,000	29,400,603	28,875,048
Netherlands	30,740,000	30,970,000	31,120,000	31,310,000	-
Romania	10,532,776	9,907,981	9,571,839	10,182,467	9,854,991
Sweden	48,210,000	53,110,000	45,650,000	45,650,000	45,651,000

The share of education buildings in non-residential sector is presented below.

Share of education buildings in non-residential sector (%)				
Country	2012	2013	2014	2015
Croatia	14.08	14.08	-	-
Greece	16.19	16.20	-	-
Netherlands	6.62	6.63	6.60	6.55
Romania	31.42	31.18	-	-
Sweden	26.23	26.14	-	-

In terms of electricity consumption per m² in education buildings ranges from 20 to 130 kWh/m², as per ODYSSEE-MURE¹⁰⁰ database.

Source	Energy consumption (kWh/ m ²)
ODYSSEE-MURE	Denmark: 40 Germany: 19 (2005) Netherlands: 51 (2005) France: 35 Sweden: 50 Spain: 56 Greece: 68 Luxemburg: 93 Cyprus: 116 Slovenia: 192 Norway: 127 (2005)

Assuming that the share of electricity consumption is approx. 35% out of the total consumption of the establishment, which has been derived from several case

¹⁰⁰ [Odyssee Mure publications on energy efficiency per sector](#)

studies from different European countries, an average electricity consumption in kWh/m²/yr is calculated.

A share of 5% of education buildings have a surface area less than 200 m², 20% have a surface area 200 to 1000 m² and 75% of those more than 1000 m²

On the basis of the specific energy consumption per square meter, it is assumed that the target for SmartCHP units, consists of buildings with more than 1000 m² surface area.

Considering a capacity factor of 70% and three typical engine capacities (100, 500 and 1000 kW) and the assumed consumption of the buildings CHP/SmartCHP has been calculated.

Conclusions

In EU27 the potential for CHP is calculated to be approximately 7,000 to 8,000 units, whereas up to 10% of this potential could be acquired by SmartCHP.

As regards the 5 focus countries, the estimated market potential for SmartCHP is as below:

- Croatia: 20 – 100 education buildings
- Greece: 25 – 50 education buildings
- Netherlands: 50 – 100 education buildings
- Romania: up to 400 education buildings
- Sweden: 50 – 100 education buildings.

Segment: Retail sector

Retail

Description

Retail sector is covering all types of stores that are selling final products, generally to individual customers. A large scope of stores are covered by the retail sector, from small stores located in traditional town center shopping district to larger stores such as hypermarkets.

EU27 market potential

At the EU scale, the number of retail stores was around 2.7M in 2017, slightly decreasing compared to 2012. The 5 selected countries are highlighted in green.

Number of retail stores in EU countries ¹⁰¹		
	2012	2017
EU-27	2 791 451	2 714 314
Belgium	88 302	-
Bulgaria	-	92 475
Czech Republic	-	-
Denmark	-	30 460
Germany	423 028	423 865
Estonia	6 965	-
Ireland	20 674	24 860
Greece	182 190	160 204
Spain	505 259	492 599
France	313 199	327 948
Croatia	20 239	19 201
Cyprus	12 860	10 721
Latvia	16 085	-
Lithuania	15 354	16 326
Hungary	114 772	106 591
Netherlands	-	236 107
Austria	58 213	61 814
Poland	298 816	55 917
Portugal	140 076	127 683
Romania	111 348	104 411
Slovakia	58 195	18 237
Finland	28 860	27 101
Sweden	57 775	53 390
United Kingdom	287 105	294 265
Norway	32 136	30 139
Serbia	-	-

The typical targets for SmartCHP technology are large stores in the selected countries, as heat and electricity generations are dimensioned for large surfaces. Heat and electricity generated could cover the consumption of hypermarkets and large stores of major companies, as their surfaces exceed 2,500 sq meters with a consumption between 150-200 MWh_e per year.

The table below indicates the total floor space of shopping centres in Europe in 2017. In the selected countries, the Netherlands and Sweden have the largest potential compared to Croatia and Greece, while Romania has an intermediary position among these five countries.

¹⁰¹ Source : Eurostat

Total floor space of shopping centres in Europe (in thousand m2)¹⁰²	
	2017
Belgium	2 838
Bulgaria	837
Czech Republic	2 961
Denmark	1 902
Germany	18 287
Estonia	861
Italy	16 200
Ireland	2 802
Greece	921
Spain	14 465
France	25 430
Croatia	1 455
Cyprus	-
Latvia	670
Lituania	1 156
Hungary	2 035
Netherlands	6 516
Austria	4 143
Poland	11 513
Portugal	3 538
Romania	3 262
Luxembourg	385
Slovakia	1 434
Slovenia	799
Finland	2 568
Sweden	5 308
United Kingdom	27 910
Norway	4 930
Switzerland	2 822
Serbia	954
Total	168 902

Electricity consumption per employee in the wholesale/trade sector are indicated in the table below for the years 2005 and 2017. It shows a decreasing trend in most of the EU countries, except for Cyprus, Italy and France.

Electricity consumption per employee in wholesale and trade sector in EU countries (in MWh/year) ¹⁰³		
	2005	2017
EU-27	7,21	5,1
Belgium		
Bulgaria		
Czech Republic		
Denmark	7,95	-
Italy	6,09	6,17
Germany	5,55	3,81
Estonia		
Ireland		
Greece		

¹⁰² Source: statista.com

¹⁰³ Source : ODYSEE-MURE

Spain	8,49	7,03
France	7,94	8,46
Croatia		
Cyprus	5,64	5,75
Latvia		
Luxembourg	10,81	7,57
Lituania		
Hungary		
Netherlands	6,75	-
Austria		
Poland		
Portugal	5,56	4,89
Romania		
Slovakia		
Finland		
Sweden	11,01	10,27
United Kingdom	8,08	5,43
Norway		
Serbia		

Two sanity checks are proposed to build assumptions for retail sector. First, a similar study carried out in FP6 project EU-DEEP (2005) showed that specific energy intensity average in terms of electricity and heat in the retail sector is respectively corresponding to:

- 5.5 MWh electricity /employee/year,
- 10 MWh heat /employee/year

As indicated in the table below, around 18.5 M persons are employed by the retail sector in the EU With a breakdown per size as follows:

Number of persons employed in the retail sector in the EU (in millions) 104	
	2015
Total number of employees in large retail stores	6.8
Total number of employees in other stores	11,7
Total number of employees in the retail sector	18.5

According to the figures above, the total consumption of retail sector in the EU can be evaluated around 287 TWh/y. The table below indicates the breakdown in TWh in the EU.

Energy consumption in the retail sector in the EU related to persons employed (in TWh)¹⁰⁵	
	2015
Energy consumption in large retail stores	126
Energy consumption in other stores	161
Energy consumption in the retail sector	287

¹⁰⁴ Source: ERRT (European Retail Round Table) Position on the EU Single Market (Dec 2015)

¹⁰⁵ Source : SmartCHP partner analysis

Potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries

Country data are provided in previous section for the five countries and reported in the table below with synthesizes the market assessment potential for the segment based on the collected data.

RETAIL	Volume: nb of sites units	Volume: Surface floor Mm2	Average size m2/unit	Assumption 1				Assumption 2		Assumption 3		Resulting nb of SmartCHP unit @1MWe in the five focus countries units	Resulting nb of SmartCHP unit @100kWe in the five focus countries units		
				Estimated specific annual energy consumption MWh per employee	Nb of employees millions	Energy consumption - all retail TWh	Estimated fraction of segment fitting to SmartCHP size %	Estimated energy consumption - only large retail TWh	Estimated fraction for CHP %	Target fraction for smartCHP %	Annual SmartCHP energy production assuming 5000 h of operation @100kWe GWh			Annual SmartCHP energy production assuming 5000 h of operation @1MWe GWh	
EU27	2714000	169	62	15,51	18,5	287	44%	126	50%	10%	1	10			
NL	236 107	6,516	28			11,1	44%	4,9					NL	243	24
Greece	160 204	0,921	6			1,6	44%	0,7					Greece	34	3
Croatia	19 201	1,455	76			2,5	44%	1,1					Croatia	54	5
Romania	104 411	3,262	31			5,5	44%	2,4					Romania	122	12
Sweden	53 390	5,308	99			9,0	44%	4,0					Sweden	198	20
ratio NL/EU27				3,86%				1,70%							

When considering the collected data for all retail stores, the estimation of 287 TWh of annual energy consumption over Europe corresponds to 168 million of sqm of surface floor.

Let's consider only one country, e.g. the Netherlands with the highest surface floor for retail (out of the five focus countries): the country has 236 000 stores and 6.5 million of sqm of surface floor, we could assess by the fraction 3.86% (corresponding to the share NL/EU27) for that country for all retail and 1.7% when considering only the large ones¹⁰⁶. The order of magnitude is estimated to be close to 5 TWh of annual energy needs in the Netherlands for large retail.

If we assume 5000 hours of operation for a SmartCHP unit of 100 kWe (resp. 1 MWe), we obtain 0.5 GWh_e (resp. 5 GWh_e). If we assume a P:H at 1, the range would be 1-10 GWh in energy over one year.

The resulting potential would be of 500 to 5000 SmartCHP units for that segment in the Netherlands at first approximation based on energy volumes needed.

The same calculation for the other countries leads to the rounded figures: Romania 250-2500; Sweden 400-4000; Croatia 100-1000; Greece 70-700 potential units (range 100-1000 kW_e).

Conclusions

Among the large variety of stores existing, from small stores in districts to hypermarkets, the largest potential for SmartCHP is with the large retailers. 6.8 M persons work in these stores, which represents 44% of the consumption (126 TWh), as presented in the graph below.

¹⁰⁶ 44% considered to be large in Europe: see below

In this category, the market actors to target are large brand retailers (IKEA, clothing brand...), supermarket and hypermarket (food retailers), shopping centre as well as ESCOs already addressing the large retailers.

Large brand retailers are looking for efficient technology to increase the renewable share in their energy mix, and SmartCHP technology would also improve their brand image.

Recently, strong regulations were put in place for these companies. Most of the EU countries are implementing restrictive measures for the retail sector to increase renewables in their energy mix, and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) politics are introduced so the large retailers need to take actions to improve their carbon footprint.

The energy department's existing in some of these big companies would be relevant contact points to promote the SmartCHP technology.

Segment: Leisure sector

Description

The leisure industry can be summed up into four main sectors: entertainment, tourism, travel and recreation. It includes facilities such as swimming pools, dry sports halls, exercise rooms, internal and external courts, ice rinks, team game pitches and associated changing and social functions. They may exist either as single activity centres or as combined centres with more than one facility.

The energy intensive equipment and infrastructure required to run a recreational centre are numerous and energy costs are significant within sports and leisure sector. Among the required consumption for these assets, both electricity and heat are needed.

Concerning electricity, the following functions are needed:

- **Ventilation and air conditioning:** A/C and ventilation accounts for 39%¹⁰⁷ of energy costs for a typical leisure centre with a pool. Wet and dry leisure centres rely on efficient air conditioning (A/C) and ventilation to regulate air temperature, which is often higher than other cases due to the heat gains from staff, customers, electrical equipment and lighting. This is particularly true of wet centres, where an air conditioning system is vital in ensuring the optimum temperature of the pool hall and changing facilities
- **Lighting:** Adequate lighting is essential to the comfort and safety of a fit-for-purpose leisure centre, lighting accounts for around 20%¹ of total energy spend in sport and leisure facilities

Regarding heat consumption:

- **Heating:** One source mention that heating accounts for around 17%¹ of energy consumed by leisure centres. Regarding heating management, many different temperatures are appropriated for different zones within the leisure centre. The table below provides some recommended heating temperatures, totally appropriate with a SmartCHP unit.

Heating zone	Temperature (°C)
Multi-purpose sports hall	12-18 (depending on the activity)
Pool hall	25-30 (depending on pool temperature)
Gym and fitness area	16-18
Weight training suite	12-14
Squash courts	16-18
Secondary sports halls	12-21 (19-21 for non-sport activities)
Changing areas	20-25
Reception and offices	16-20
Nursery	21
Refreshment areas	18-20

- **Swimming pools:** Swimming pool water temperatures should range from 25°C for training and competition pools to 40°C for specialist spa and hydrotherapy pools. Maintain a constant temperature for the swimming pool is one of the most significant energy expenses for wet leisure centres

¹⁰⁷ Source : Gazprom Energy

EU27 market potential

Seven reference types range from a local dry sport centre to a regional leisure centre:

- Local dry sport centre: size suitable for four badminton courts, which can accommodate five-a-side football, basketball and other sports.
- 25 m swimming pool centre
- Leisure pool centre: wave area, adjoining learning pool, splash pool for the flume run-off, changing area, café and bar.
- Combined centre: includes a 25 m five-lane pool and a learning pool, plus a six-court sports hall and a six-lane indoor bowls hall. There is a licensed bar and snack bar, fitness room and health suite with jacuzzi, sauna and solarium.
- Fitness centre: fitness studios and a suite of exercise rooms with exercise machines, the centre has a sauna, solarium, licensed bar and a snack bar
- Sports ground changing facility: free-standing changing room/pavilion for team games pitches
- Ice rink.

The table below shows the electricity and heating use.

Typical annual energy use for reference types of leisure centres ¹⁰⁸		
	Electricity use (kWh/m ²)	Heating fuel use (kWh/m ²)
Local dry sport centre	105	343
25 m. swimming pool centre	237	1336
Leisure pool centre	258	1321
Combined centre	152	598
Fitness centre	194	449
Sports ground changing facility	164	216
Ice rink	255	217

Potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries

Swimming pools, spas and leisure centres are 'incremental' segments with a penetration of cogeneration systems. This is fully justified by the high levels of energy uses for electricity and heat in the above table. One could also notice that their structure of energy loads remains quite stable during operations: the specific value offered by a flexible very adaptative system might be seen as less relevant when compared to conventional cogeneration.

Lack or dispersed statistical information on the number of installations per type prevented to carry out a similar analysis as the one made for more homogeneous segments such as hospitals and hotels.

¹⁰⁸ Source : Report "Best practice programme UK: Energy use in sports and recreation buildings"

Segment: Greenhouses

Greenhouses

Description

Greenhouses is included in the agriculture sector and consists of the vegetables, flowers and permanent crops under plastic or glass covered area.

EU27 market potential

The evolution of the number of greenhouses in EU27 from 2005 to 2013 is presented in the following table¹⁰⁹.

Number of greenhouses				
Country	2005	2007	2010	2013
EU 27	232.170	187.130	151.640	164.780
Austria	700	1.450	1.400	1.480
Belgium	3.690	3.380	2.850	1.420
Bulgaria	7.750	7.730	6.720	6.040
Croatia		1.550	2.560	2.990
Cyprus	670	650	570	530
Czechia	840	580	0	0
Denmark	730	720	840	700
Estonia	700	380	240	190
Finland	1.780	1.580	1.370	1.270
France	15.350	13.850		13.860
Germany	9.980	8.920	6.570	5.770
Greece	10.240	12.150	8.890	9.180
Hungary	12.050	8.760	9.430	13.950
Ireland	380	270	180	170
Italy	31.080	26.650	32.720	28.270
Latvia	320	420	260	340
Lithuania	34.850	11.890	10.000	9.770
Luxembourg	30	30	10	10
Malta	290	300	280	310
Netherlands	8.600	7.410	4.980	4.120
Poland	29.370	24.530	14.880	16.120
Portugal	4.110	3.770	3.700	5.340
Romania	18.630	16.670	17.970	19.570
Slovakia	830	930	270	200
Slovenia	5.150	1.440	570	630
Spain	32.510	30.460	23.610	21.680
Sweden	1.540	660	770	870

The total surface area of the greenhouses in m² is presented in the following¹¹⁰.

¹⁰⁹ <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do>

¹¹⁰ <http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do>

Total surface area (m2)				
Country	2005	2007	2010	2013
EU 27	1.266.900.000	1.298.100.000	1.214.800.000	1.340.100.000
Austria	2.900.000	5.800.000	6.200.000	7.200.000
Belgium	21.400.000	21.200.000	20.600.000	18.000.000
Bulgaria	9.000.000	11.400.000	-	-
Croatia		2.500.000	4.100.000	5.000.000
Cyprus	4.200.000	4.300.000	4.500.000	4.200.000
Czechia	1.800.000	1.900.000	0	0
Denmark	4.500.000	4.700.000	4.600.000	4.000.000
Estonia	600.000	600.000	400.000	400.000
Finland	4.500.000	4.400.000	4.200.000	4.000.000
France	96.200.000	97.900.000	-	111.900.000
Germany	-	34.300.000	31.700.000	31.100.000
Greece	46.700.000	53.400.000	42.900.000	47.300.000
Hungary	19.100.000	17.600.000	19.600.000	22.600.000
Ireland	600.000	300.000	600.000	1.800.000
Italy	286.400.000	265.000.000	391.000.000	389.100.000
Latvia	-	800.000	-	-
Lithuania	10.100.000	4.500.000	3.100.000	3.300.000
Luxembourg	0	100.000	0	0
Malta	700.000	700.000	800.000	1.000.000
Netherlands	105.400.000	103.700.000	98.200.000	93.300.000
Poland	71.700.000	75.600.000	66.300.000	80.800.000
Portugal	23.100.000	22.200.000	23.600.000	24.900.000
Romania	27.900.000	32.500.000	30.200.000	33.000.000
Slovakia	2.500.000	1.900.000	1.500.000	1.000.000
Slovenia	1.700.000	1.800.000	1.700.000	1.600.000
Spain	521.700.000	527.200.000	457.000.000	452.000.000
Sweden	4.200.000	1.800.000	2.000.000	2.600.000

Potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries

The number of greenhouses in the focus countries and the total floor area, are given in the following tables.

Number of greenhouses				
Country	2005	2007	2010	2013
Croatia		1.550	2.560	2.990
Greece	10.240	12.150	8.890	9.180
Netherlands	8.600	7.410	4.980	4.120
Romania	18.630	16.670	17.970	19.570
Sweden	1.540	660	770	870

Total surface area (m2)				
Country	2005	2007	2010	2013
Croatia		2.500.000	4.100.000	5.000.000
Greece	46.700.000	53.400.000	42.900.000	47.300.000
Netherlands	105.400.000	103.700.000	98.200.000	93.300.000
Romania	27.900.000	32.500.000	30.200.000	33.000.000
Sweden	4.200.000	1.800.000	2.000.000	2.600.000

In terms of energy consumption per m² in greenhouses, ranges from 50 to 400 W/m², depending on the region where the country is located. In greenhouses the total energy consumption could also reach up to 400 W/m², including heating, lighting and cooling.

Source	Energy consumption (W/ m ²)
SUSTAINABLE GREENHOUSE HORTICULTURE IN EUROPE ¹¹¹	Southern region: 50 – 150 Northern and Central region: 200 - 280

For greenhouses, the share of thermal needs is relatively high (around 70-80% of the overall energy demand) compared to other market segments.

Through existing information and measurement of the size of a sample of greenhouses around EU (using aerial images) greenhouses could be split in 3 different classes. First class are those with less than 4,000 m² surface area, second class from 4,000 to 8,000 m² and the third class those with more than 8,000 m². The majority of greenhouses (approx. 50%) belong to the second class (4,000 to 8,000 m²) and the other 2 classes are split equally (25% each).

The total surface area for the whole segment is already known from Eurostat statistics (1,340,100,000 m²).

For the calculation of the potential for greenhouse applications, a capacity factor of 70% is considered. For different engine electrical capacities, i.e. 100, 500 and 1000 kW. Combining the produced kWh_e and the total electricity consumption/requirement of greenhouses, the number of CHP units has been calculated.

Considered one more time the two fractions (the one for energy and the other for SmartCHP), it is estimated a range from 200 to 4,000 greenhouses in whole Europe could become SmartCHP users.

Conclusions

Of the total of 160,000 greenhouses across EU27, more than 10,000 can be potential CHP users, of which 1,000 could be SmartCHP users.

In the 5 focus countries, the following market potential for SmartCHP is estimated, as followed.

- Croatia: 25 – 50 greenhouses
- Greece: 100 – 250 greenhouses
- Netherlands: more than 100 greenhouses
- Romania: 200 – 500 greenhouses
- Sweden: 10 – 15 greenhouses

¹¹¹ <https://arpi.unipi.it/retrieve/handle/11568/788029/92641/v3-n3-7.pdf>

Segment: Residential sector

Description

Residential sector covers the highest total floor area, with a percentage around 75%. Out of this percentage, approximately 40% belongs to apartment blocks (including households consist of several units and social housing units) and the remaining to single family houses, including detached, semi-detached and terraced houses).

EU27 market potential

It is important to note that the share of single family and apartments buildings varies significantly from country to country. Among the EU 27 countries and as regards the apartment buildings, Latvia has the highest share (approx. 75%), following by Estonia (70%) and Spain (65%) while Ireland (around 10%), Greece (more than 10%) and Norway (15%) have the smallest ones.

Source: *Europe's buildings under the microscope. A country-by-country review of the energy performance of buildings*

When considering the split of the total energy consumption by end-use in residential buildings, space heating has the highest share with a range of 60-80%.

In terms of energy consumption per surface floor (m²), there are large variations from country to country due to significant climatic conditions: as indicated in the following table, Southern countries (Malta, Cyprus, Portugal, etc.) have a low average total energy consumption, while in Northern countries such as Romania, Latvia, Estonia, etc., the total energy consumption are higher than the EU, respectively¹¹².

Energy consumption per m ²			
Country	kWh/m ²		
EU28	184.14	Ireland	165.68
Belgium	262.71	Italy,	174.99
Bulgaria	121.09	Latvia	292.28
Croatia	249.57	Lithuania	204.42
Cyprus	69.45	Luxembourg	205.42
Czech Republic	234.4	Malta	46.62
Denmark	168.69	Netherlands	152.48
Estonia	289.59	Poland	237.6
Finland	248.49	Portugal	69.61
France	190.16	Romania	308.09
Germany	199.73	Slovakia	172.98
Greece	120.8	Slovenia	228.4
Hungary	149.98	Spain	103.04
		Sweden	214.81

Potential for SmartCHP units in the 5 focus countries

The specific energy consumption per m² in the five focus countries for the residential sector is presented in the following.

Energy consumption per m ²	
Country	kWh/m ²
Croatia	249.57
Greece	120.8
Netherlands	152.48
Romania	308.09
Sweden	214.81

¹¹² EU buildings factsheets

Conclusions

Based on the above data, and on the fact that the single-family houses (SFH) are out of the SmartCHP scope, we estimate that the market potential could be a percentage of around 5-10% of the apartment building. Promising segments are social housing since already a commercial target for cogeneration. In the future energy communities could also be a route to further explore according to their development.

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